

UNIVERSITÀ
DI PAVIA

Università degli Studi di Pavia
Dipartimento di Scienze della Terra e dell'Ambiente

SCUOLA DI ALTA FORMAZIONE DOTTORALE

MACRO-AREA SCIENZE E TECNOLOGIE

DOTTORATO DI RICERCA IN SCIENZE DELLA TERRA E
DELL'AMBIENTE

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Investigation of Microscale fracture opening in host inclusion systems

Anno Accademico 2023-2024

Ciclo XXXVII

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ABSTRACT

Diamond-hosted inclusions provide a unique window into the Earth's interior, with their preserved residual pressures serving as key indicators of entrapment conditions. This thesis investigates the fracture mechanisms in such systems, addressing discrepancies between numerical models and experimental observations, and advancing geobarometric methodologies.

Using Extended Finite Element Methods (XFEM) and Phase-Field Modeling (PFM), this study explores the interplay between inclusion geometry, material properties, and fracture behavior. XFEM simulations revealed that brittle fractures alone contribute marginally (~5–6%) to residual pressure relaxation, leaving pressures significantly higher (~0.76 GPa) than observed in natural systems (<0.5 GPa). These models identified inclusion shape and size as key drivers of stress concentration and fracture propagation but highlighted the limitations of brittle fracture assumptions.

To address the limitations of XFEM, Phase-Field Modeling (PFM) was employed, integrating advanced damage models to simulate both brittle and quasi-brittle fractures. PFM 3D results underscored the critical influence of geometric singularities, such as sharp edges in cuboidal inclusions, in enhancing pressure relaxation (~0.72 GPa) and aligning fracture properties more closely with experimental values. Additionally, stress interactions in systems with multiple inclusions revealed fracture coalescence as a key mechanism for facilitating further relaxation. However, these effects, while significant, remain insufficient to fully reconcile numerical predictions with the lower residual pressures observed in natural systems. A comparative analysis of ellipsoidal inclusions under cohesive fracture

conditions further demonstrated the enhanced relaxation potential of quasi-brittle fractures, bridging some of the gaps between models and experimental findings. Despite these advancements, the modeled relaxation still falls short, underscoring the need to incorporate additional mechanisms, such as fluid-mediated weakening and inelastic deformation, to capture the complexity of natural inclusion-host systems.

These findings suggest that mechanisms such as viscous or plastic deformation, preexisting defects, and fluid-mediated weakening likely play a critical role in the relaxation of residual stresses in natural olivine-diamond systems. They underscore the need for advanced numerical tool/algorithm capable of capturing the complex interplay of host-inclusion geometry, fracture properties, and the influence of fluids and defects.

This work establishes a comprehensive framework for modeling fracture mechanics in diamond-hosted inclusions, bridging critical gaps in geobarometric models. By advancing numerical methodologies and addressing key challenges, it lays the foundation for future research integrating inelastic processes and the complex dynamics inherent in natural systems.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This thesis marks the end of a long and transformative chapter, and I would like to begin by expressing my deepest and most heartfelt gratitude to **Prof. Matteo Alvaro**. More than just a supervisor, Matteo believed in me when I doubted myself. He gave me the space to explore and the freedom to fail and learn, and through that freedom, I was able to find my own voice as a researcher. He funded my work for several months and supported me not just academically but personally - with trust, kindness, and his characteristic calmness. His mentorship has left a lasting mark on how I approach science and life.

I would also like to sincerely thank **Prof. Alessandro Reali**, who first introduced me to the world of computational modeling. His excellent teaching opened a door I didn't know existed. From that point on, he has been a steadfast supporter throughout this journey, offering sharp insight, wise guidance, and a quiet confidence in my potential. A very special thank you goes to **Dr. Alessia Patton**, whose presence and support were immediate, effective, and always warm. Alessia never hesitated to help - even at a moment's notice - and her consistent availability made a world of difference during challenging phases of my work. She showed me what it means to be rigorously committed while remaining empathetic and human.

I am deeply thankful to **Dr. Mattia Luca Mazzucchelli**, who has been with me from the very beginning. With infinite patience, he helped me understand concepts far outside my background, guiding me through Earth sciences and through every major step of the thesis. His dedication and support were essential to my learning and to keeping me grounded. My appreciation also goes to **Prof. Simone Morganti** for his contributions during the thesis process. His eye for detail and his insistence on clarity helped sharpen the way I present and communicate my work.

To my incredible research group - **Mara, Stefy, Giulia, Lisa, Oliver, and Mattia** - thank you for being far more than colleagues. From daily lunches to spontaneous advice, work

Sessions to random acts of help, you've been an essential part of this experience. Your support -both practical and personal -made the long days lighter.

To my dear friends -**Maithree, Rita, Du, Giorgio, Davide, Basar, Diego, Maria, Moe, Deniz, Yildirim, Bryan, and Ricardo**—thank you for being who you are. Each of you gave me joy, comfort, and the sense that I was never alone, even when far from home.

A quiet part of my gratitude belongs to my sister, **Apa**, who passed away in 2021 while I was in the middle of my master's studies. Her life, though short, was filled with strength, kindness, and grace. I grew up wanting to be like her. Though her absence still confuses me, her presence quietly endures in everything I do.

To my **parents** - thank you. You gave us stability and strength, even when life gave you little. You encouraged me to return to my studies -and continue to support me, always, with quiet faith and the freedom to grow in my own way. I don't believe in personal gods, but if I did, they would look like you -building a future for your children with steady love and silent resilience.

Finally, I want to acknowledge **myself**.

Through every high and low, I stayed present -with my thoughts, my doubts, and the quiet determination that carried me forward. During these years in Pavia, it was mostly me and Romea Café -my quiet corner, my refuge, my thinking space.

In the long hours between research and reflection, I stopped chasing certainty and began learning to live with the questions. I didn't always feel understood -not even by myself -but I kept going.

Through this thesis, this city, its streets and this solitude, I didn't find all the answers. But I found enough of myself to continue.

To all those named and unnamed: thank you.

Bhanu

Pavia, June 2025

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

- BFGS Broyden–Fletcher–Goldfarb–Shanno
- CVD Chemical Vapor Deposition
- CZM Cohesive Zone Model
- EBSD Electron BackScatter Diffraction
- EoS Equation Of State
- EPFM Elastic-Plastic Fracture Mechanics
- FEA Finite Element Analysis
- FEM Finite Element Method
- HRR Hutchinson-Rice-Rosengren
- KKT Karush-Kuhn-Tucker
- LEFC Linear Elastic Fracture Criterion
- LEFM Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics
- PF-CZM Phase-Field regularized Cohesive Zone Model
- PFM Phase-Field Modeling
- SDVs Solution-Dependent Variables
- SEN Single Edge Notch Test
- SIFS Stress-Intensity Factors
- SMART Separating, Morphing, Adaptive, and Remeshing Technology
- STATEV State Variables
- SVARS solution-dependent variables
- TSL Traction Separation Law
- UEL User Element
- UMAT User Material
- VCCT Virtual Crack Closure Technique

- XFEM eXtended Finite Element Method

LIST OF SYMBOLS

Latin Characters

- E [Pa]: Young's Modulus
- G_{IC} , G_{IIC} , and G_{IIIC} [J/m²]: Critical energy release rates for each fracture mode
- K_{IC} , K_{IIC} , and K_{IIIC} [MPa·m^{0.5}]: Fracture toughness parameters for each fracture mode
- P [Pa]: Pressure
- T [K]: Temperature
- P_{end} [Pa]: Final pressure after exhumation
- T_{end} [K]: Final temperature after exhumation
- P_{thermo} [Pa]: Overpressure of the inclusion
- P_{trap} [Pa]: Pressure at entrapment conditions
- T_{trap} [K]: Temperature at entrapment conditions
- $V_{host}(P, T)$ [m³]: Unit-cell volume of the host mineral at pressure (P) and temperature (T)
- P_{inc} [Pa]: Residual inclusion pressure
- $V_{inc}(P, T)$ [m³]: Unit-cell volume of the inclusion mineral at pressure (P) and temperature (T)
- H [J/m³]: Local history field variable
- l [m]: Length scale parameter
- \mathbf{b} [N/m³]: Macroscopic body force
- \mathbf{h} [N/m²]: Boundary tractions
- \mathbf{n} [-]: Outward normal vector
- I [-]: Second-order identity tensor
- K^{uu} , $K^{\phi\phi}$ [N/m]: Tangent matrices

- f_t [Pa]: Uniaxial tensile strength or the failure strength
- $g(\phi)$ [-]: Energetic degradation function
- k_0 [N/m³]: Initial slope of the softening curve

Greek Characters

- ν [-]: Poisson's Ratio
- σ^{thermo} [Pa]: Isotropic stress tensor in Voigt notation representing uniform overpressure within the inclusion
- α [-]: Power-law criterion parameter for mixed-mode fracture behavior
- ϕ [-]: Damage-like crack phase-field
- $\alpha(\phi)$ [-]: Crack geometric function
- $\epsilon(\mathbf{x})$ [-]: Strain field
- σ [Pa]: Cauchy stress tensor
- Δ [-]: Laplacian operator i.e. $\Delta\phi = \nabla \cdot \nabla\phi$
- Γ [-]: A crack/jump set, or the sharp crack surface
- $\gamma(\phi, \nabla\phi)$ [-]: Crack surface density function
- Γ_0 [-]: Initial state of a crack/jump set or the predefined crack
- Γ_1 [-]: Regularised crack surface
- λ_0, μ_0 [-]: Lamé constants
- Π [J]: Total energy
- Ω [-]: Domain occupied by the solid with volume V
- $\partial\Omega_h, \partial\Omega_u$ [-]: Neumann/Dirichlet boundary
- $\Psi_0(\epsilon)$ [J/m³]: Initial energy density function
- $\Psi^\pm(\epsilon)$ [J/m³]: Positive/negative parts of the initial energy density function

INTRODUCTION

Beyond their allure as precious gemstones, diamonds serve as invaluable geological archives. Trapped within their crystal lattice, mineral inclusions such as olivine offer a unique glimpse into the extreme conditions of pressure (P) and temperature (T) present deep within the Earth's mantle at the time of their formation. These inclusions act as time capsules, allowing geoscientists to reconstruct the geological history of diamond growth, mantle dynamics, and the processes of exhumation (Nestola et al., 2018; Pearson et al., 2014; Shirey et al., 2013). Determining these entrapment conditions is fundamental for advancing our understanding of Earth's interior and refining geobarometric models.

Elastic geothermobarometry has emerged as a cornerstone for estimating the conditions under which inclusions were encapsulated. This method leverages the contrast in elastic properties between diamond hosts and their inclusions to calculate the residual stresses locked within the inclusion during exhumation (Angel, Alvaro, et al., 2015; Angel et al., 2022; Howell, Wood, et al., 2012). Diamonds, being stiffer and having lower thermal expansion than their inclusions, constrain the inclusions to a smaller volume than they would occupy as free crystals at ambient conditions. As a result, inclusions studied at surface conditions are often overpressurized compared to their equilibrium state. These residual stresses, referred to as residual pressures, serve as a proxy for the conditions at the time of encapsulation (Angel et al., 2018b; Anzolini et al., 2019; Howell, Wood, et al., 2012). By measuring these residual stresses, researchers can reconstruct the pressure-temperature conditions at which diamonds formed.

Elastic geothermobarometry has been successfully applied to a variety of diamond inclusions (Anzolini, 2018; Anzolini et al., 2016; Cohen & Rosenfeld, 1979; Howell et al., 2010; Izraeli et al., 1999; Nestola et al., 2011; Sobolev et al., 2000), assuming that the behavior of both the diamond and the inclusion remains purely elastic throughout exhumation. However, this assumption often fails to account for discrepancies between observed and predicted residual pressures in natural inclusions. For example, inclusions

from the Udachnaya mine exhibit residual pressures below 0.5 GPa (Angel et al., 2018b, 2022; Rustioni, 2016; Rustioni et al., 2016), which would suggest entrapment conditions below the diamond stability field if modeled elastically (see Figure 0.1). These discrepancies highlight the role of inelastic mechanisms—such as plastic deformation, brittle fractures, and viscous relaxation—in reducing residual stress during exhumation (Campomenosi et al., 2023; Nimis et al., 2016; Zhong et al., 2024). Properly accounting for these mechanisms is critical for improving geobarometric interpretations and accurately estimating entrapment conditions.

Among inelastic mechanisms, fractures may play a particularly significant role in the inelastic relaxation of residual stresses in diamond-hosted inclusions. These fractures often form during exhumation due to stress concentrations, thermal contraction, or pre-existing flaws in the diamond host. By altering the stress distribution within the host-inclusion system, fractures can reduce residual pressures, leading to the underestimation of entrapment conditions in geobarometric models (Angel et al., 2022; Rustioni et al., 2016). Additionally, fractures frequently serve as conduits for fluid infiltration, resulting in secondary phases filling the cracks. These fluid-mediated processes further impact the inclusion's stress state and exacerbate pressure relaxation (Nimis et al., 2016; Rustioni et al., 2016).

The formation and characteristics of fractures have been extensively studied using advanced techniques. X-ray micro-tomography has provided three-dimensional insights into fracture networks and fluid pathways (Mazzucchelli et al., 2016; Rustioni et al., 2015; Wenz et al., 2019), while EBSD has revealed crystallographic evidence of deformation patterns within diamond hosts (Howell, Piazzolo, et al., 2012). Raman spectroscopy has further complemented these observations by quantifying residual stress and strain states in inclusions (Anzolini et al., 2019; Murri et al., 2018). Together, these techniques have demonstrated the prevalence of fractures in modifying stress states and influencing geobarometric interpretations (Angel et al., 2022).

Understanding when and how these fractures form is critical for refining geobarometric interpretations. Fractures typically initiate when local stresses exceed the critical fracture strength of the diamond. However, their nucleation and propagation are governed by a complex interplay of factors, including the inclusion's geometry, material properties, and external conditions such as fluid presence (Rustioni, 2016; Zhong et al., 2018). By investigating fracture formation, researchers can better assess the effects of these processes on residual stress and refine estimates of entrapment pressure and temperature.

The fracture mechanics of diamond-hosted inclusions, where stress concentrations drive crack nucleation and propagation are not unique to geological systems. They are fundamental to composite materials, where a stiff matrix encloses a softer inclusion. The numerical modeling approaches that will be adopted and developed in this study extends naturally to advanced ceramics, cementitious materials, and aerospace composites, where fracture-driven stress redistribution governs material performance. In ceramics, thermal and mechanical stresses dictate crack growth and failure resistance (Evans, 1990; Lawn, 1993). Cementitious composites, such as Layered Engineered Cementitious Composites (LECC), exhibit stress-driven fracture relaxation, which can be modeled using methods developed for geological inclusions (Y. Wu et al., 2022). Similarly, in aerospace composites, stress redistribution at matrix-inclusion interfaces determines structural reliability (Alam et al., 2022). More broadly, any system with a stiff host and a softer inclusion follows similar fracture dynamics, from geological inclusions to engineered composites and biomaterials. The Extended Finite Element Method (XFEM) and Phase Field Modeling (PFM) frameworks in this study bridge geoscience and materials science, providing a unified approach to stress evolution, failure prediction, and damage modeling (Ashby & Sammis, 1990; Handin, 1969).

Building on the foundational understanding of fractures and stress relaxation in diamond-hosted inclusions, this thesis employs advanced computational modeling techniques to explore these complex systems. The XFEM and PFM are applied to investigate fracture initiation, propagation, and their effects on residual pressures. These methods address the limitations of traditional elastic models, offering deeper insights into the mechanical behavior of host-inclusion systems.

XFEM, a versatile tool capable of modeling fractures without remeshing, was initially used to study ellipsoidal inclusions in both two and three dimensions. However, XFEM simulations are known to encounter convergence issues and limitations in accurately modeling complex fracture propagation. This prompted the adoption of PFM, a method better equipped to handle such challenges. Furthermore, while XFEM primarily modeled

idealized ellipsoidal inclusions, real inclusions often have geometric complexities such as edges and corners. These features introduce localized stress concentrations, or singularities, which can lead to earlier fracture initiation—an aspect observed in natural samples but not captured in XFEM models. Including these geometric effects was a critical step toward creating more realistic simulations of host-inclusion systems.

The findings from these models reveal critical insights into the mechanics of diamond-hosted inclusions. XFEM results demonstrate fracture properties significantly lower than expected and residual pressure relaxations that fail to explain observed values below 0.5 GPa. PFM, on the other hand, aligns more closely with natural observations but highlights the role of additional mechanisms—such as plastic deformation, viscous flow, and fluid-mediated processes—in stress relaxation. By integrating these complementary techniques, this thesis refines geobarometric interpretations and broadens the framework for understanding entrapment conditions in diamond-hosted inclusions.

This work not only enhances the applicability of geobarometry but also establishes a foundation for future investigations into the complex deformation behaviors of diamonds and their inclusions. It bridges the gap between computational models and natural systems, advancing the understanding of how brittle, ductile, and viscous mechanisms interact to govern stress relaxation.

Part I: Brittle Fractures and Point Singularities: Insights from Extended Finite Element Modelling (XFEM)

The Extended Finite Element Method (XFEM) was the first numerical approach used in this study to model fractures in diamond-hosted inclusions. XFEM allows fracture simulation without remeshing, making it an efficient tool for analyzing brittle failure and stress relaxation in host-inclusion systems. However, while XFEM captured fracture initiation and propagation, it struggled with modeling multiple interacting fractures and stress redistribution, necessitating the transition to Phase-Field Modeling (PFM) in Part II.

This section of the thesis follows a structured progression:

- Chapter 1: Exhumation and Computational Framework – Introduces the geological and computational framework, explaining how inclusions retain residual stress due to differential decompression. This provides the necessary pre-stress conditions for all XFEM and PFM simulations.
- Chapter 2: Fracture Mechanics and Numerical Methods – Covers the theory of fracture mechanics, presenting various numerical approaches available in finite element-based software and discussing their applicability to host-inclusion systems.
- Chapter 3: XFEM 2D Simulations – Implements XFEM in 2D, investigating stress concentration, fracture initiation, and crack propagation in a simplified host-inclusion system.
- Chapter 4: Extension to XFEM 3D – Expands the model to 3D ellipsoidal inclusions, providing a more realistic representation of fracture behavior in diamond-hosted inclusions.

XFEM simulations revealed that brittle fractures alone resulted in minimal pressure relaxation, with residual pressures remaining too high compared to natural observations. Fracture strength and toughness values were significantly lower than expected, yet stress redistribution was insufficient to reduce inclusion pressures meaningfully. The transition to 3D modeling in Chapter 4 confirmed these limitations, highlighting the need for additional relaxation mechanisms beyond brittle failure. Moreover, XFEM encountered convergence issues when simulating complex fracture interactions, reinforcing the necessity for alternative modeling techniques, such as Phase-Field Modeling (PFM), introduced in Part II.

Part II: Brittle Fractures and Edge Singularities – Novel Simulation Framework via Phase-Field Modelling (PFM)

XFEM's difficulty in capturing multiple fractures, stress redistribution, and quasi-brittle behavior led to the adoption of Phase-Field Modeling (PFM)—a more advanced numerical framework that enables continuous fracture evolution and improved numerical stability. Unlike XFEM, which represents cracks discretely, PFM provides a diffuse fracture representation, making it well-suited for simulating cohesive fractures and stress relaxation in host-inclusion systems.

This section follows a structured progression:

- Chapter 5: Fundamentals of Phase-Field Modeling – Introduces PFM theory and governing equations, discussing its numerical implementation and how it is adapted for host-inclusion systems.
- Chapter 6: PFM 2D Simulations – Validates the PFM framework using standard fracture tests such as the Single Edge Notch (SEN) test before applying it to 2D host-inclusion systems.
- Chapter 7: Extension to PFM 3D – Expands PFM to 3D, investigating the role of geometric singularities (edges and corners) in cuboidal inclusions and their effect on fracture initiation and stress relaxation.

PFM simulations revealed that cuboidal inclusions with sharper edges exhibited higher stress concentrations, leading to earlier fracture initiation and more effective pressure relaxation (~ 0.72 GPa for cuboidal inclusions). However, while PFM outperformed XFEM in fracture modeling, it still could not fully explain observed residual pressures below 0.5 GPa in natural inclusions. To further investigate stress interactions, PFM 3D was extended to systems with two interacting inclusions, revealing that mutual stress weakening facilitated additional relaxation but still left residual pressures above 0.5 GPa.

Finally, ellipsoidal inclusions were modeled using PFM to provide a direct comparison with XFEM results under reduced fracture strength (cohesive fractures). While PFM exhibited greater consistency with natural observations, it still highlighted the need for additional relaxation mechanisms, such as plastic deformation, fluid-mediated weakening, and host anisotropy effects, to achieve full agreement with natural inclusions.

**PART I: BRITTLE FRACTURES
AND POINT SINGULARITIES:
INSIGHTS FROM EXTENDED
FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING
(XFEM)**

1. EXHUMATION AND COMPUTATIONAL FRAMEWORK

1.1 INTRODUCTION

The exhumation of a host-inclusion system is a dynamic process, where rocks ascend from mantle depths (>60 km) to near-surface conditions. This process is governed by decreasing pressure and temperature, leading to an evolving stress and strain state in both the host and inclusion.

Since the host and inclusion have different material properties (Morganti et al., 2020a), they decompress at different rates, generating internal stresses in the inclusion due to the pressure vessel effect (Bower, 2009). While exhumation is intrinsically time-dependent, modeling it as a fully dynamic problem would require solving transient stress evolution. However, this is computationally expensive and impractical for large-scale simulations.

To overcome this challenge, the exhumation process is approximated as a quasi-static problem, where the focus is placed on two key equilibrium states:

- Entrapment Conditions (P_{trap} , T_{trap}): The moment when the inclusion was first trapped inside the host at high pressure and temperature.
- Final Conditions (P_{end} , T_{end}): The near-surface state after exhumation, where the inclusion experiences residual stress due to differential decompression.

This simplification leads to an equivalent static model, where the stress state of the inclusion at the end of exhumation is computed as a static prestress condition rather than solving the entire time-dependent process. The resulting prestress in the inclusion is referred to as P_{thermo} and serves as the input for numerical simulations in this thesis.

1.2 EXHUMATION AND STRESS EVOLUTION IN THE HOST-INCLUSION SYSTEM

During subduction, rocks undergo high-pressure metamorphism, and minerals recrystallize to form new phases. Figure 1.1 (a) illustrates the host-inclusion system at entrapment

conditions ($P_{\text{trap}}, T_{\text{trap}}$), where both the host and inclusion experience the same pressure. As the system ascends to the surface, it reaches its final conditions ($P_{\text{end}}, T_{\text{end}}$), as shown in Figure 1.1(b).

Figure 1.1. Illustration of the host-inclusion system(a) when the inclusion entrapped with entrapment temperature and pressure; (b) The host and inclusion system after exhumation

Since the host and inclusion have different elastic and thermal properties, they decompress at different rates. Figure 1.2(a) shows the host-inclusion system at entrapment conditions, where both share the same pressure. However, as exhumation progresses (Figure 1.2 (b)), the inclusion retains a higher residual stress than the host, creating a stress drop at the interface.

- If the inclusion is softer than the host → it decompresses less, retaining higher residual pressure.
- If the inclusion is stiffer than the host → it decompresses more, leading to a lower residual pressure.

This stress imbalance is a direct consequence of the pressure vessel effect and is mathematically formulated in the following sections.

Figure 1.2. Sketches of radial stress against radius in an ideal host-inclusion system (a) The inclusion host system at the entrapment temperature and pressure (b) The stress along radius of host inclusion system after exhumation of the system, P_I is the inclusion stress and P_{en} is the stress of the host leaving a stress drop (Figure recreated from (Angel et al., 2014b))

The stress drop (P_{thermo}) in Figure 1.2 (b) represents the input prestress condition used in all of the numerical simulations.

1.3 COMPUTATIONAL FRAMEWORK: THE EQUIVALENT STATIC MODEL

1.3.1 Mathematical Formulation Using Voigt Notation

The static modeling framework simplifies the problem as follows:

1. **Entrapment:** At (P_{trap}, T_{trap}) , the inclusion and host are in equilibrium.
2. **Final State:** The system is exhumed to ambient conditions ($P_{tambient} = 0 \text{ GPa}, T_{ambient} = 298 \text{ K}$) via intermediate states at P_{end}, T_{end} .
3. **Homogeneous Temperature:** The temperature, T_{end} is assumed to act uniformly across both host and inclusion.
4. **Hydrostatic Pressure:** The host is subjected to P_{end} , while the inclusion undergoes stress interactions with the host.

The objective is to calculate the inclusion's strain, stress, and pressure fields under final conditions (P_{end}, T_{end}) .

The derivation employs Voigt notation to express tensors and begins by defining the changes in pressure and temperature during the transition from one state to another:

We first define some quantities:

1. Change in pressure and temperature:

From ambient conditions to end

$$\Delta P^{ae} = (P_{end} - P_{room}), \Delta T^{ae} = (T_{end} - T_{room}) \quad (1.1)$$

The superscript *ae* means ambient-end.

From end to entrapment

$$\Delta P^{et} = (P_{trap} - P_{end}), \quad \Delta T^{et} = (T_{trap} - T_{end}) \quad (1.2)$$

The superscript et means end-trap.

2. The strain of a free inclusion crystal from end conditions to entrapment

The stress applied to the crystal is:

$$\sigma^{et,inc} = [-\Delta P^{et} - \Delta P^{et} - \Delta P^{et} \ 0 \ 0 \ 0]^T \quad (1.3)$$

The resulting strain is

$$\varepsilon_i^{et,inc} = S_{ij} \sigma_j^{et,inc} + \alpha_{inc} \Delta T^{et} \quad (1.4)$$

Where S_{ij} is the compliance matrix of the inclusion, α_{inc} is the expansion coefficient of the inclusion.

The strain of a free inclusion crystal from ambient conditions to end conditions The stress applied to the crystal is:

$$\sigma^{ae,inc} = [-\Delta P^{ae} - \Delta P^{ae} - \Delta P^{ae} \ 0 \ 0 \ 0]^T \quad (1.5)$$

The resulting strain is

$$\varepsilon_i^{ae,inc} = S_{ij}\sigma_j^{ae,inc} \quad (1.6)$$

Where S_{ij} is the compliance matrix of the inclusion

3. The strain of the host crystal from end conditions to entrapment
The stress applied to the crystal is:

$$\sigma^{et,host} = [-\Delta P^{et} - \Delta P^{et} - \Delta P^{et} \ 0 \ 0 \ 0]^T \quad (1.7)$$

The resulting strain is

$$\varepsilon_i^{et,host} = S_{ij}\sigma_j^{et,host} + \alpha_{host}\Delta T^{et} \quad (1.8)$$

Where S_{ij} is the compliance matrix of the host, α_{host} is the expansion coefficient of the host.

With the abovementioned quantities, one can calculate the strain and stress in the inclusion, before and after the mutual elastic interaction between the host and the inclusion.

1.3.2 Unrelaxed strain and stress (i.e. before the elastic interaction)

The strain can be either referred to a crystal at P_{end}, T_{end} or to a crystal at $P_{ambient}, T_{ambient}$.

The strain referred to a crystal at P_{end}, T_{end} is:

$$\varepsilon^{ue,inc} = \varepsilon_i^{et,inc} - \varepsilon_i^{et,host} \quad (1.9)$$

The superscript *ue* means unrelaxed end.

The strain referred to a crystal at $P_{ambient}, T_{ambient}$ is:

$$\varepsilon^{ua,inc} = \varepsilon^{ue,inc} + \varepsilon_i^{ae,inc} \quad (1.10)$$

The superscript *ua* means unrelaxed-ambient.

The stress in the inclusion is:

$$\sigma_i^{ua,inc} = C_{ij} \varepsilon_j^{ua,inc} \quad (1.11)$$

The value of $\sigma^{ua,inc}$ will be taken as an input value to put in our numerical simulations and will be called P_{thermo} from here onwards.

The equivalent static model of the dynamic problem is shown in Figure 1.3.

1.4 CHOICE OF MINERALS AS HOST AND INCLUSION SYSTEMS

1.4.1 Olivine Inclusion in Diamond Host

The host-inclusion system analyzed in this study consists of olivine inclusions encapsulated within a diamond host, as shown in Figure 1.4. This combination is chosen due to the following key factors:

- Fracture occurrence in natural samples: Diamonds which contain olivine inclusions frequently exhibit fractures, making them an ideal system for studying stress relaxation and crack propagation.

- **Minimal Phase Transformations:** Unlike other minerals, olivine and diamond maintain stable chemical compositions during exhumation, preventing phase transitions that could introduce additional complexities in stress modeling.
- **Simplified Elastic Behavior:** Diamond is an isotropic material, meaning its elastic response is uniform in all directions. This characteristic simplifies computational modeling and allows for a controlled study of fracture evolution and stress relaxation.

Figure 1.4. Olivine inclusions inside the Diamond host (Nestola et al., 2014)

1.4.2 Further Model Simplifications

To ensure a controlled investigation, this study primarily models a single olivine inclusion in a diamond host, reducing computational complexity and parameter variability for a clearer understanding of crack initiation. A two-inclusion case is introduced in one study to examine stress interactions while keeping external variables minimal, allowing for a focused analysis of fracture formation mechanisms.

Furthermore, two geometric approximations are employed to explore different singularity effects:

1. Ellipsoidal inclusion → Used to simulate point singularities.
2. Cuboidal inclusion → Used to study edge singularities.

This structured approach allows for a progressive understanding of fracture evolution and stress relaxation, starting from a simplified single-inclusion system and gradually introducing additional complexity where necessary.

1.4.3 Entrapment Conditions and Overpressure Estimation

For this study, we assume that olivine inclusions were entrapped within their diamond host at 5.5 GPa and 1473.15 K (P_{trap} and T_{trap}). These conditions represent typical values for olivine inclusions in diamonds from the Udachnaya kimberlite (Agrosi et al., 2016; Nestola et al., 2011).

Since diamond is significantly stiffer than olivine, the inclusion decompresses at a slower rate than the host during exhumation, leading to internal stress buildup. Our elastic calculations (Section 1.3) indicate that upon exhumation to ambient conditions, the olivine inclusions develop a maximum overpressure (P_{thermo}) of 1 GPa, which is the difference between the internal inclusion pressure and the external pressure acting on the diamond host. Unless stated otherwise, we adopt 1 GPa as the default upper limit of inclusion overpressure in our models.

2. FRACTURE MECHANICS: THEORY AND FINITE ELEMENT-BASED COMPUTATIONAL APPROACHES

2.1 THEORY OF FRACTURE MECHANICS

Fracture mechanics is the field of study concerned with the initiation, growth, and propagation of cracks in materials. It integrates the principles of solid mechanics to evaluate stress, strain, and energy release around crack tips, providing insights into the conditions leading to fracture.

Fracture mechanics can be broadly divided into Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics (LEFM) & Elastic-Plastic Fracture Mechanics (EPFM). Super brittle materials such as glass and ice can be categorised under LEFM, and ductile materials such as metals and polymers can be categorised under EPFM. Besides that, quasi-brittle material such as rock and concrete can be categorised into the Cohesive Zone Model (CZM).

2.1.1 Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics (LEFM)

After Inglis's ground-breaking work on a linear elastic solution for stresses around an elliptical hole (Inglis, 1913), there is a concerning discussion among the scientific community about the viability of the results, which shows infinity stress around the crack tip, making it practically impossible for any material to sustain even a small amount of load. Alan Arnold Griffith approaches the same problem with the Energy-based criterion (Griffith, 1921). So, Griffith proposed a failure criterion based on energy using the same *Linear Elastic Solution* proposed by Inglis. He compared the work required to break atomic bonds to the strain energy release as the crack grows. The result found can be seen in equation (2.1), where σ is the failure stress of the material, a is crack length, and E is the Modulus of Elasticity. He elegantly represented the Energy release rate (G) to the material's failure stress (σ) and crack length (a).

$$G = \frac{\pi\sigma^2 a}{E} \quad (2.1)$$

Equation (2.1) can be further modified to represent failure stress (σ) in terms of strain energy release rate (G).

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{GE}{\pi a}} \quad (2.2)$$

Two important observations can be made from Equation (2.2)

- The critical stress level for a given crack length varies with the material.
- The critical stress level decreases with crack length; the larger the crack, the easier it to become unstable

Irwin later invented a way to calculate the amount of available energy in terms of asymptotic stress and displacement fields around crack tips in a linear elastic solid material. In Equation (2.3) asymptotic stress field (σ) is shown in terms of stress intensity factor (K), where r is the distance from the crack tip.

$$\sigma_{ij} = \left(\frac{K}{\sqrt{2\pi r}} \right) f_{ij}(\theta) \quad (2.3)$$

The numerator of equation (2.1) can also be represented with stress intensity factor (K) as in Equation (2.4)

$$K = \sigma\sqrt{\pi a} \quad (2.4)$$

Equation (2.5) ultimately gives a relation between critical Energy release rate (G_c) and critical stress intensity factor (K_c) as shown below in Equation (2.25(2.5)).

$$G_c = \frac{K_c^2}{E} \quad (2.5)$$

2.1.2 Elastic-Plastic Fracture Mechanics (EPFM)

The principles of Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics (LEFM) are limited to materials exhibiting linear elasticity. However, most engineering materials are ductile, where the plastic zone near the crack tip is significant relative to the cracked body's dimensions. Griffith's original theory did not account for energy dissipation due to plasticity, which was later incorporated by Orowan, (1949) as shown in equation (2.6), where G_s represents elastic dissipation and G_p represents plastic dissipation energy release rates.

$$G = G_s + G_p \quad (2.6)$$

Cherepanov (1967) and Rice (1968) proposed the J -integral as a fracture characterising parameter for nonlinear materials. The J -integral can be proven path independent, which can be seen as a line integral (Figure 2.1) around the crack tip.

$$J = e \int_{\Gamma} w \cdot dy - T_i \cdot \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x} \cdot ds \quad (2.7)$$

Equation (2.7) shows the formulation for J integral, where w is the strain energy density, T_i are the components of the traction vector, u_i are the displacement vector components, and ds is a length increment along the contour Γ .

Rice demonstrated that the J -integral could be interpreted as energy release rate, and for linear elastic material, the J -integral is equal to the linear elastic energy release rate as shown in equation (2.8), where G is the energy release rate as expressed in the previous section, U is the potential energy, and A is the cracked area.

$$J = G = -\frac{\partial U}{\partial A} \quad (2.8)$$

Figure 2.1. J-integral: contour around the crack tip

When the plastic zone ahead of crack tip becomes comparable in size with other cracked body dimensions, Elastic-Plastic Fracture Mechanics (EPFM), based on the work of

Hutchinson and Rice-Rosengren, uses the J-integral to describe the stress field (HRR field (Hutchinson, 1968; Rice & Rosengren, 1968) as:

$$\sigma_{ij} = \sigma_y \cdot \left(\frac{J}{\alpha \sigma_y \varepsilon_y I_n} \right)^{\frac{1}{n+1}} \cdot f_{ij}(\theta) \quad (2.9)$$

Where σ_{ij} and I_n are tabulated functions of strain hardening exponent n and the parametric angle θ . The conditions for the validity of the HRR singular field is known as the J-dominance conditions (Figure 2.2), and different studies had been performed to characterise the J-dominance condition for different cracked specimens subjected to bending and tension loading.

Figure 2.2. Effect of plasticity on the crack-tip stress fields: (a) small-scale yielding, (b) elastic-plastic conditions, and (c) large-scale yielding (Anderson, 2017).

2.2 COMPUTATIONAL FRACTURE MECHANICS: NUMERICAL APPROACHES AVAILABLE WITHIN FINITE ELEMENT-BASED SOFTWARE

2.2.1 Classical Finite Element Method

In the conventional Finite Element Method (FEM), cracks must be explicitly modeled, meaning the mesh must conform to the crack geometry. Commercial FEM software like ABAQUS and ANSYS typically use the J integral and Stress Intensity Factor (K) to analyze crack initiation and propagation.

(a) Numerical computation of J integral

The J integral is calculated using the domain integral method (Shih et al., 1986), which employs area integration for 2D problems and volume integration for 3D problems. These methods are more accurate and efficient than contour or surface integrals. The domain integral representation for the J integral is provided in ANSYS documentation(ANSYS, 2020).

$$\begin{aligned}
 J = & \int_A \left[\sigma_{ij} \cdot \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_1} - w \delta_{1i} \right] \frac{\partial q}{\partial x_i} dA \\
 & + \int_A \alpha \sigma_{ii} \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial x_1} q_1 dA - \int_A \sigma_{ij} \frac{\partial \varepsilon_{ij}^0}{\partial x_1} q_1 dA - \int_A t_j u_{j,1} q_1 dS
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.10}$$

σ_{ij} =Stress Tensor

u_j =Displacement vector

w =Strain Energy density

δ_{ij} =Kronecker delta

x_i =Local coordinate axis

q =Crack extension vector

α =Coefficient of thermal expansion

ε_{ij}^0 =Initial strain tensor

t_j = Crack face traction

A = Integration domain

C = Crack faces upon which tractions act

(b) Numerical computation of Stress-Intensity Factors (SIFS)

The calculation of Stress Intensity Factors (SIFs) uses the Interaction Integral Method, which is an extension of the domain integral method. This approach applies an auxiliary field to separate K_I and K_{II} addressing the domain integral's inherent limitation in distinguishing these components (Bjørtheim, 2019). The interaction integral is defined as

$$I_0 = - \frac{\int_V q_{i,j} [\sigma_{kl} \varepsilon_{kl}^{aux} \delta_{ij} - \sigma_{kj}^{aux} u_{k,i} - \sigma_{kj} u_{k,i}^{aux}] dV}{\int_S \delta q_n dS} \quad (2.11)$$

$\sigma_{ij}, \varepsilon_{ij}, u_i$ = stress, strain, and displacement (respectively)

$\sigma_{ij}^{aux}, \varepsilon_{ij}^{aux}, u_i^{aux}$ = stress, strain, and displacement (respectively) of the auxiliary field

q_i = Crack extension vector

The value of the interaction integral can be different if there are thermal and initial strains. Equation (2.11) has been derived from the domain integral of the previous section.

The Interaction Integral can be shown in terms of Stress Intensity Factor (K) as shown in Equation (2.12) and from there SIF can be computed.

$$I = \frac{2}{E^*} (K_1 K_1^{aux} + K_2 K_2^{aux}) + \frac{1}{\mu} K_3 K_3^{aux} \quad (2.12)$$

K_i = (i=1,2,3), Mode I, II, III stress intensity factors

K_i^{aux} = (i=1,2,3), Auxiliary mode I, II, III stress intensity factors

E^* = E for plane stress and $E/(1 - \nu^2)$ for plane strain

E = Young's modulus

ν = Poisson's ratio

μ = Shear modulus

(c) Application of conventional FEM in commercial software

Commercial software like ABAQUS and ANSYS use conventional methods to calculate fracture parameters such as Stress Intensity Factors (K) and the J integral for stationary cracks. However, their approaches to crack propagation differ. ABAQUS employs the Extended Finite Element Method (XFEM) (Section 0), while ANSYS Workbench relies on the conventional FEM method. In ANSYS, crack propagation requires remeshing at each sub-step, a process handled by the SMART (Separating, Morphing, Adaptive, and Remeshing Technology) method.

In the SMART method, the crack initiation occurs when stress Intensity factors (K) or J integral becomes equal to critical stress intensity factor (K_C) and critical J integral (J_C), respectively. The crack propagates by the following condition shown in equation (2.13) (Bjørheim, 2019)

$$\theta = \cos^{-1} \frac{(3(K_{II}^{max})^2 + K_I^{max})\sqrt{(K_I^{max})^2 + 8(K_{II}^{max})^2}}{(K_I^{max})^2 + 9(K_{II}^{max})^2} \quad (2.13)$$

K_i^{max} ($i=1, 2 \& 3$) are maximum stress intensity factors in mode I, II and III

(d) Concerns of application of SMART method or FEM

The SMART method is limited to 3D crack growth and assumes linear elastic isotropic material behavior with only one material in the crack growth domain. It does not account for plasticity or nonlinear geometric effects (ANSYS, 2020). Further details are discussed in Section 2.2.4.

2.2.2 Inter Element Method

Interelement methods like the Virtual Crack Closure Technique (VCCT) and Cohesive Zone Model (CZM) use interface and contact elements to model crack behavior. Interface

elements are zero-thickness cohesive elements inserted between material interfaces. Figure 2.3 illustrates the incorporation of these zero-thickness elements.

The interfacial separation is defined as the displacement jump, δ (that is, the difference of the displacements of the adjacent interface surfaces):

$$\delta = u^{Top} - u^{Bottom} \quad (2.14)$$

From Equation (2.14) δ is the interfacial deformation.

The definition of the separation is based on the local element coordinate system, shown in Figure 2.4. The normal of the interface is denoted as local direction n , and the local tangent direction is denoted as t .

$$\delta_n = n \cdot \delta \quad (2.15)$$

$$\delta_t = t \cdot \delta \quad (2.16)$$

From Equation (2.14) δ_n is the normal separation and from equation (2.14) δ_t is the tangential (shear) separation.

Contact elements are shown in Figure 2.5, which are unlike interface elements, purely penalty-based contact elements. The interfacial separation is defined in terms of contact gap or penetration and tangential slip distance.

(a) Virtual Crack Closure Technique (VCCT)

The Virtual Crack Closure technique was initially proposed by Irwin (Irwin, 2021) based on the idea that the energy required to open a crack is the same as the energy required to close it. The energy needed to open a crack is nothing but the strain energy release rate (G). The energy required to close a crack is the work done by the nodal forces at the crack tip (R_{x_i}, R_{y_i}) to the displacements around it ($\Delta u_i, \Delta v_i$) as shown in Figure 2.6.

Figure 2.6. Two-dimensional schema of VCCT for the four-node square elements (ANSYS, 2020)

With the help of the assumption stated, the mode I and mode II components of the strain energy release rate are easily obtained from the following equations

$$G_I = \frac{1}{2\Delta a} R_Y \Delta v \quad (2.17)$$

$$G_{II} = \frac{1}{2\Delta a} R_X \Delta u \quad (2.18)$$

For 3D, an additional equation in the z-direction will be just added.

The Numerical Implementation of the VCCT method uses interface elements only. The crack initiation happens with the multiple combinations of the ratio of modes of Energy release rate to the critical energy release rate.

e.g.,

$$f = \frac{G_I}{G_I^c} + \frac{G_{II}}{G_{II}^c} + \frac{G_{III}}{G_{III}^c} \quad (2.19)$$

Equation (2.19) is the Linear Elastic Fracture Criterion (LEFC). The crack nucleates when $f > 1$. The crack propagation is already predefined by the interface elements.

(b) Cohesive Zone Model (CZM)

Cohesive Zone Modeling (CZM) introduces a novel approach by focusing on the process zone where damage development occurs. Unlike traditional crack propagation, where no stress is transferred between crack planes after initiation, CZM allows stress transfer

between planes during crack initiation and evolution within the fracture process zone (Figure 2.7). This zone is governed by a stress-displacement relationship known as the Traction Separation Law (TSL). Cohesive models, however, rely on phenomenological traction-separation laws that do not account for microstructural changes in the material (Wciślik & Pała, 2021).

Dugdale (Dugdale, 1960) first coined the cohesive zone concept, by introducing a plastic zone around the crack tip (Figure 2.8). The plastic zone is defined by the traction (σ_y) which is the yielding strength of the material. There is no strain hardening and the Dugdale model was limited by plane stress conditions only with the assumption of elastic-perfectly plastic material. Later Barenblatt replaces the plastic zone with the cohesive zone, as shown in Figure 2.9.

Figure 2.9. Barenblatt model (Barenblatt, 1962)

Figure 2.10. Crack propagation using Cohesive zone model

Figure 2.10 shows if the displacement (δ) is less than δ_m^0 there will not be any separation between two crack planes, but when displacement is greater than δ_m^0 there will be crack formation which will go for evolution under different TSL as shown in Figure 2.11.

Different researchers have given different models for Traction and separation behaviour, such as (Figure 2.11). The basic factor in between the nature of the TSL curve is the 'ductility' of the material. In the brittle material, the maximum strength (cohesive strength) is achieved with $\delta_m^0 = 0$ (Figure 2.11(a)) which means the failure process begins without local deformations. For ductile material, the maximum strength is achieved with non-zero displacement (δ_m^0) value.

The Numerical Implementation of CZM uses both interface elements and contact elements in commercial software. The application of the Cohesive model does not require the manual insertion of an initial crack, as it can be automatically computed through Traction

Separation Law (TSL) with given crack initiation criteria such as ‘Maximum Principal Stress’, ‘Maximum Principal Strain’ or combinations of stresses and strains. The crack propagation is already predefined.

(c) Concerns of Inter Element Method

Both methods, VCCT and CZM, need a crack path a priori. This means that the propagation path cannot be predicted; that is why both inter-element methods have limited applicability in the delamination of composites. In addition to that CZM method is very sensitive to mesh size and VCCT needs a manual insertion of crack.

2.2.3 Extended Finite Element Method (XFEM)

XFEM is an extension of the conventional finite element method developed by Belytschko & Black (1999), based on the partition of unity method introduced by Melenk & Babuška, (1996). This method ensures the summation of shape functions equals unity, allowing XFEM to incorporate a priori knowledge of the solution into the finite element space. It enables modeling of discontinuities and singularities independent of the mesh.

This capability makes XFEM particularly effective for simulating crack propagation, as it eliminates the need for mesh updates to conform to discontinuity geometries. Cracks can propagate along solution-dependent paths. XFEM achieves this by adding enrichment functions in the region of the crack, which account for both singularities and discontinuities (Figure 2.12). These functions include asymptotic crack tip functions to capture singularities at the crack tip and a discontinuous Heaviside function to represent the gap between crack surfaces.

The displacement function for the conventional finite element method is as following

$$u^h(x) = \sum N_I(x)u_I \quad (2.20)$$

The two additions of the enrichment functions are as following to represent the crack tip singularity and discontinuity

$$u^h(x) = \sum N_I(x)u_I + \sum N_J(x)H(x)a_J + \sum N_k(x)\left(\sum_{\alpha=1}^4 B_\alpha b_K^\alpha\right) \quad (2.21)$$

Where

$$H(x) = \begin{cases} +1 & \text{if } (x - x^*) \cdot n \geq 0 \\ -1 & \text{Otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2.22)$$

Heaviside function is there two represent a crack discontinuity.

The solution of the Westergaard (2021) formula was employed ((2.23) to derive the enrichment functions representing the singularity at the crack tip,

$$B_\alpha = \sqrt{r}\sin\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right), \sqrt{r}\cos\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right), \sqrt{r}\sin\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right)\sin(\theta), \sqrt{r}\cos\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right)\sin(\theta) \quad (2.23)$$

The numerical implementation of the XFEM is done through the phantom mode method (Hansbo & Hansbo, 2004; J. Song et al., 2006). Singularity based method (Equation (2.21) applies to stationary cracks only—the Phantom node method is used to propagate cracks through cohesive segment approach, which follows the equation (2.24).

$$u^h(x) = \sum N_I(x)u_I + \sum N_J(x)H(x)a_J \quad (2.24)$$

We can see the enrichment function representing singularity has been dropped out so that crack now can propagate. Phantom nodes are superposed to the standard node, which produces the discontinuity with the enrichment element intact. When crack starts to

propagate by cutting the elements, the superposed nodes are divided into two different parts, as real and phantom nodes, as shown in Figure 2.13 (Equation (2.25)).

$$u(x, t) = u^1(t)N_I(x)H(-f(x)) + u^2(t)N_I(x)H(f(x)) \quad (2.25)$$

$u^1(t)$ = Displacement vector in sub-element 1

$u^2(t)$ = Displacement vector in sub-element 2

$f(x)$ = Crack surface definition ($f(x) = 0$)

$H(f(-x))$ and $H(f(x))$ are the Heaviside functions as shown in Equation (2.22)

Concerns of application of XFEM

XFEM requires enrichment of critical regions expected to fail. However, due to uncertainties in crack propagation, users often enrich larger domains than necessary, increasing computational cost (Elruby et al., 2018). Additionally, XFEM has limitations in handling complex scenarios, such as elements with multiple cuts, crack branching, and crack turning angles greater than 90 degrees (Gigliotti, 2012).

2.2.4 The Selection of the appropriate Numerical Tool and Method

This thesis evaluates two widely used commercial software packages, ABAQUS and ANSYS, for their suitability in addressing the research problem. Benchmark analyses, detailed in [insert reference], and a review of existing literature highlighted significant limitations in ANSYS for computational fracture mechanics. Inter-element methods were excluded from this analysis due to their reliance on predefined crack paths, which restrict modeling of arbitrary crack propagation.

ANSYS Workbench offers only the SMART method (Section 2.2.1) for crack propagation along unknown paths. This conventional FEM-based technique requires manually defining cracks for initiation, with propagation relying on J integral calculations. However, as cracks approach each other, the contour integral becomes unreliable, yielding erroneous results (G. Song et al., 2015). Additionally, the need for mesh conformation at each iteration demands significant computational resources and results in accuracy loss during data mapping to updated meshes (Ahmed, 2009). Consequently, modeling arbitrary crack propagation is impractical with SMART.

XFEM, commercially available in ABAQUS since 2009, overcomes many of these limitations. While ANSYS offers XFEM in APDL, it is restricted by significant limitations (ANSYS, 2020) and lacks integration into the Workbench interface (Gigliotti, 2012). ABAQUS's XFEM, despite its challenges (section 2.2.3), remains the dominant numerical

tool for computational fracture mechanics, supported by extensive research across various domains.

Based on this evaluation, the analyses in the subsequent chapters will use XFEM in ABAQUS as the primary numerical method.

3. XFEM 2D SIMULATIONS OF FRACTURE IN HOST-INCLUSION SYSTEMS

3.1 INTRODUCTION

This section applies the Extended Finite Element Method (XFEM) to model crack nucleation, propagation, and coalescence in diamond-hosted olivine inclusions. These fractures result from deviatoric stresses caused by mismatches in thermoelastic properties during exhumation. Using a 2D representation of the host-inclusion system, these simulations provide key insights into stress distribution and fracture behavior, establishing a foundation for future 3D modeling.

3.1.1 Geometry and Meshing

The geometries analyzed for this study include setups with one and two inclusions embedded within a diamond host. Key dimensions are designed to ensure that boundary effects on crack initiation and propagation are negligible. To achieve this, the ratio of the host length to the inclusion length is maintained at 40:1. This configuration ensures that the simulation accurately represents stress interactions around the inclusion without undue influence from boundary constraints.

(a) Geometry Configurations

Single Inclusion Setup: A single olivine inclusion is embedded within the diamond host. This configuration is used to study isolated stress and crack propagation patterns.

Two Inclusion Setup: Two inclusions are arranged within the host with a defined spacing, enabling the investigation of interactions between stress fields and potential crack coalescence.

The corresponding geometrical configurations are illustrated in the following figures:

(b) Meshing Strategy

The meshing approach was carefully designed to capture the stress distribution and crack propagation with high precision while maintaining computational efficiency. ABAQUS XFEM requires an enrichment area where nodes are enriched with additional functions to handle the discontinuities associated with cracks. Structured meshing was applied to ensure uniformity and reduce numerical artifacts.

Key meshing features include:

- **Mesh Type:** A structured tetrahedral mesh was employed for both single and two-inclusion setups.
- **Element Type:** The element type used is CPS4R, a 4-node bilinear plane stress quadrilateral with reduced integration and hourglass control. This choice aligns

with recommendations for XFEM implementations (Nuclear Regulatory Commission, 2020).

- **Accuracy and Stability:** Second-order accuracy and distortion control were applied to ensure the reliability of results.

The meshing details for the single and two-inclusion setups are depicted in the following figures:

3.1.2 Material Properties

(a) Lamé parameters (Elastic Properties)

The material properties for the host inclusion system are shown in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1. Material Properties of the host-inclusion system

	Young 's Modulus (GPa)	Poisson ratio	thermal expansion (*10 ⁻⁵ K ⁻¹)
Diamond	1139.1	0.0724	0.2661
Olivine	189.6	0.2499	2.6338

(b) Fracture parameters for Cohesive zone modelling

The fracture parameters used in cohesive zone modeling (CZM) are critical for accurately simulating crack initiation, propagation, and energy dissipation. In 2D CZM, the traction-separation law (TSL) governs the interaction across the crack surface and is defined by two

key parameters: fracture toughness (K_{IC}) and fracture strength (σ_{max}). These parameters describe the material's resistance to crack initiation and its behavior during crack propagation, respectively.

In this study, we adopted fracture parameters for single-crystal diamond based on reported values from literature (Field & Pickles, 1996; Hess, 2012; Liang et al., 2009). The fracture toughness (K_{IC}) of diamond ranges between 6–18 $\text{MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{0.5}$, and we selected a representative value of 16 $\text{MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{0.5}$ for our simulations. However, the fracture strength (σ_{max}) varies widely, with a theoretical upper limit of 4 GPa but typically observed to be less than 1 GPa for single-crystal diamonds. For simplicity and computational practicality, we assigned a smaller fracture strength of 450 MPa.

This choice of fracture strength was deliberate and justified by the nature of the 2D simulations, which were not intended to replicate realistic fracture behavior but rather to serve as a conceptual step before advancing to 3D models. Using a lower fracture strength made it easier to visualize and quantify crack propagation and fracture length, allowing us to evaluate the modeling framework's ability to simulate inclusion-host interactions effectively. Additionally, this approach ensured that fractures would propagate visibly under the applied conditions, enabling more straightforward analysis and validation of the methodology.

The TSL employed in this study assumes a linear softening response, meaning the traction decreases linearly with separation after crack initiation. This linear relationship simplifies the implementation and aligns with the assumptions of isotropic material behavior in 2D models. We used the maximum principal stress criterion for damage initiation, as it is suitable for 2D isotropic materials and provides reliable results for the simulated diamond-inclusion systems.

Based on the Griffith theory (or maximum strain energy release rate theory), the fracture resistance of a material is independent of mode mixity. Cracks propagate in the direction that maximizes energy release, allowing the fracture energy (Γ) to be calculated as:

$$\Gamma = J_c = \frac{K_{IC}^2}{E} \quad (3.1)$$

Here, Γ represents the energy required to propagate a crack, K_{IC} is the fracture toughness, and E is the elastic modulus of the material. Using a fracture toughness (K_{IC}) of 16 MPa·m^{0.5}, the fracture energy (Γ) was calculated to be approximately 224.738 N/m.

In applying cohesive strength in CZM-based FEA, cohesive strength is assumed to be about the same in shear and tensile directions. This assumption is based on the fact that in diamond, due to the enormous strength of the C-C bond, shear and tensile strength remains the same, at least up to the breaking point (Y. Zhang et al., 2005).

3.1.3 Boundary Conditions & Loading

Boundary conditions and loading are designed to replicate the practical conditions of the host-inclusion system under study.

Applied Boundary Conditions

- **Zero Displacement Constraints:** Two sides of the host are assigned zero displacement in both the x and y directions, ensuring the model remains fixed while allowing for the simulation of stresses and strains elsewhere.
- **Hydrostatic Pressure on Host:** The host material is subjected to a hydrostatic pressure of P_{end} at the outer boundaries to simulate the effects of exhumation.
- **Pre-stress in Inclusion:** The inclusion is pre-stressed using values derived from the transformation of entrapment conditions (P_{trap}, T_{trap}) to final conditions (P_{end}, T_{end}) based on the computational framework described earlier (Section 1.3), This pre-stress is applied as of $\sigma_i^{ua,inc}$ in Figure 3.5 (c).

Crack Average Growth Control

The crack propagation direction is modeled to occur orthogonal to the maximum tangential stress, which aligns with the crack growth criterion. However, for complex problems like this—featuring hydrostatic stresses in a confined inclusion area within a larger host—using only centroidal evaluations for crack initiation and propagation can lead to inaccuracies, even with finely meshed elements.

To address this, non-local averaging is implemented (Figure 3.6). This approach:

- Smoothens stress parameters within an enrichment radius, avoiding abrupt variations in localized stress evaluations.
- Ensures higher accuracy in determining crack initiation and propagation paths.

Figure 3.6. Non local averaging control

Unsymmetric Solver and Displacement Correction

The stiffness matrix associated with enrichment elements in XFEM is inherently unsymmetric, requiring specific adjustments for enhanced convergence. To address this, enabling unsymmetric matrix storage is recommended, as outlined by the (Nuclear Regulatory Commission, 2020). By default, this parameter is set to "NO" in Abaqus but was modified to "YES" in this analysis to improve solution convergence.

Additionally, convergence challenges may arise during crack propagation due to displacement jumps and sudden increases in local compliance. To mitigate these issues, the correction factor C_n^\square , is employed. This factor represents the ratio of the largest displacement correction to the largest incremental displacement during the iterative process in the Newton-Raphson method.

In this study, the default recommendations for C_n^α , from the Nuclear Regulatory Commission, (2020) were adopted without modification, ensuring robust displacement accuracy while maintaining computational stability.

Stabilization Techniques

- **Nonlinear Geometry:** Nonlinear geometric effects were disabled throughout the analysis to simplify computations and focus on material behavior.
- **Damage Stabilization Cohesive:** A stabilization parameter of $1E-5$ was applied to the cohesive damage model. This setting ensured smooth crack propagation and mitigated numerical instabilities.
- **Automatic Stabilization:** Automatic stabilization was activated with a default value of $2E-4$. This feature introduced artificial damping to control oscillations in the solution field, particularly during complex crack propagation phases.

Together, these measures ensured the convergence, accuracy, and computational efficiency of the XFEM simulations.

3.2 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the outcomes of numerical investigations, focusing on crack initiation, propagation, coalescence, and validation of the numerical framework through mesh convergence analysis.

3.2.1 Mesh convergence analysis

The accuracy and reliability of numerical simulations depend critically on achieving mesh convergence. In this study, convergence was evaluated for both single and multiple inclusion configurations under the conditions specified in Table 1.2:

Table 3.2. The entrapment conditions and final conditions for convergence analysis

	Entrapment Conditions		Final Conditions	
	P_{trap} (GPa)	T_{trap} (K)	P_{end} (GPa)	T_{end} (K)
Amount	6	1300	0	298

(a) Single Inclusion

Mesh convergence was validated using a single inclusion inside a diamond host. Figure 3.7 illustrates the percentage error, which was 0.9% between successive refinements, confirming numerical stability. Additionally, the absolute maximum principal stress distribution (Figure 3.8) adhered to the symmetry dictated by boundary conditions, further reinforcing the model's consistency.

(b) Two Inclusions

To study crack interaction, mesh convergence analysis was extended to two inclusions spaced 30 mm apart. As shown in Figure 3.9, the percentage error between successive refinements was 0.54%. Figure 3.10 demonstrates stress distribution symmetry akin to the single inclusion model, validating the framework's ability to analyze multi-inclusion systems.

3.2.2 Effect of Inclusion Shape on Crack Behavior

The effect of inclusion shape on fracture initiation and propagation was investigated by simulating inclusions with varying aspect ratios while maintaining a constant area/volume. Figure 3.11 depicts the different inclusion geometries considered in this study, ensuring that variations in crack behavior arise solely from changes in shape rather than size. This setup enables a detailed examination of how aspect ratios influence crack initiation thresholds and propagation patterns.

(a) Crack Initiation

The geometry of inclusions significantly affects fracture initiation. By fixing final conditions ($P_{end} = 0$ GPa, $T_{end} = 298$ K) and entrapment pressure ($P_{trap} = 6$ GPa), simulations revealed the entrapment temperature required for crack initiation. Figure 3.12 compares

fracture strength required for damage initiation across ellipsoidal inclusions with aspect ratios of 4:1:1 and 10:1:1, highlighting the independence of fracture toughness and inclusion size on initiation thresholds.

(b) Crack Propagation

The length of cracks propagated was influenced by the aspect ratio of the inclusions, with larger aspect ratios leading to longer cracks. Key findings include (Figure 3.13):

- Crack propagation was governed by internal stresses, with minimal contribution from stress concentration effects.
- Larger aspect ratios resulted in higher rates of crack propagation, as these inclusions required lower initial stresses for fracture initiation.

3.2.3 Crack Coalescence

The interaction of stress fields between inclusions significantly influences crack coalescence, with the spacing between inclusions playing a critical role in determining the threshold pressure required for coalescence.

Figure 3.14. Crack Length (mm) vs Inclusion pressure in a three inclusion system

Figure 3.14 demonstrates the variation in crack length as a function of inclusion pressure in a three-inclusion system. A dramatic increase in crack propagation rate is observed, with the crack length jumping from 6 mm to 10 mm at a threshold inclusion pressure of 1.98 GPa. This threshold marks the point at which the stress field interactions induce coalescence between the inclusions.

This phenomenon is driven by a positive feedback mechanism, wherein the mutual weakening of stress fields between the inclusions reduces the internal field strength. This, in turn, accelerates crack propagation and leads to coalescence. The interaction amplifies as the cracks propagate, with the stress concentration becoming increasingly localized between the inclusions.

Figure 3.15 provides a visualization of the absolute maximum principal stress for two inclusions separated by 20 mm. The figure highlights the stress field's distribution and illustrates how increased spacing diminishes the interaction strength between inclusions. Consequently, larger separations require higher pressures to induce crack coalescence, as the mutual weakening effect is less pronounced.

The results emphasize the critical role of inclusion spacing in determining coalescence behavior and underscore the importance of stress interactions in driving crack propagation.

3.3 CONCLUSIONS

The XFEM 2D modeling of diamond-hosted inclusions provided a foundational framework for understanding the mechanics of brittle fracture initiation and propagation in simplified systems. This study demonstrated the feasibility of modeling inclusion-host interactions using XFEM in a computationally efficient two-dimensional setup, paving the way for subsequent 3D modeling efforts.

The key findings from XFEM 2D simulations include:

1. **Fracture Initiation and Propagation:** The results confirmed that higher stress concentrations around inclusions correlate with increased fracture initiation and propagation. These observations provided initial insights into crack behavior in host-inclusion systems.
2. **Crack Coalescence:** The study successfully demonstrated crack coalescence, highlighting the potential for multiple fractures to merge under the influence of stress field interactions.
3. **Algorithmic Improvements:** Implementing control mechanisms, such as non-local averaging and enabling unsymmetric solvers, significantly improved the convergence behavior of XFEM simulations. These methodological advances enhanced the robustness and reliability of the 2D models.

However, the 2D nature of the simulations imposed inherent limitations. The simplified geometric representation of inclusions restricted the ability to replicate real-world conditions. Additionally, the use of reduced fracture strengths in the simulations, while intentional to enhance visibility of crack propagation, further highlighted the conceptual nature of these models.

Overall, XFEM 2D served as an essential exploratory step in the broader investigation of fracture mechanics in diamond-hosted inclusions. The findings from this chapter informed the transition to XFEM 3D, where more realistic geometries and conditions were incorporated, ultimately contributing to a more comprehensive understanding of inclusion-induced fractures. The methodological groundwork laid here underscored the importance of computational efficiency and parameter control in achieving reliable results in fracture modelling.

4. EXTENSION TO XFEM 3D

This chapter was published as an article in Engineering Fracture Mechanics with the title:

Investigation of microscale brittle fracture opening in diamond with olivine inclusion using XFEM and cohesive zone modelling

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The final published version of the article can be downloaded at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engfracmech.2024.110713>. The publication is open access and released under the terms of the CC-BY-NC license.

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4.1 ABSTRACT

Inclusions trapped in diamonds are a fundamental source of information to probe the Earth's interior, provided that the pressure conditions at which the diamond grew are correctly determined.

This study explores the traditional assumptions in geothermobarometry for olivine-in-diamond host-inclusion systems by employing extended finite element methods (XFEM) and cohesive zone models (CZM) to quantify the contributions of brittle fractures to the relaxation of the residual stress of inclusions. Our analysis was performed assuming that the host-inclusion system does not contain fluids and that the unfractured minerals are elastically isotropic. Our models show that the damage initiation is solely dependent on the shape of the inclusion and on the fracture strength of the diamond host, while the fracture nucleation is influenced by both the size of the inclusion and the toughness of the diamond. Our findings indicate that, in dry systems, the amount of relaxation of residual stress of the inclusion due to the opening of brittle fractures is much lower than that due to the elastic interaction between the host and the inclusion. Moreover, the pressure release due to fractures is not substantially affected by the shape of the inclusion. We also show that the total relaxation of the residual pressure due to the combined effect of the elastic interaction and of the brittle deformation is lower than what is observed in natural samples, even when assuming fracture strength and toughness lower than those reported from experiments on single crystals of diamond. Such discrepancies suggest that in natural olivine-diamond systems additional mechanisms such as viscous or plastic deformation and/or the presence of preexisting defects and fluids in the host might play a relevant role in the relaxation of the residual stress. These findings underscore the need for advanced numerical tools that consider the complex interplay of the geometry of the host-inclusion system, the fracture properties, and the presence of fluids and defects in order to build more accurate models to constrain the geological history of diamonds.

Latin Characters

- E [Pa]: Young's Modulus
- G_{IC} , G_{IIC} , and G_{IIIC} [J/m²]: Critical energy release rates for each fracture mode

- K_{IC} , K_{IIC} , and K_{IIIC} [$\text{MPa} \cdot \text{m}^{0.5}$]: Fracture toughness parameters for each fracture mode
- P [Pa]: Pressure
- T [K]: Temperature
- P_{end} [Pa]: Final pressure after exhumation
- T_{end} [K]: Final temperature after exhumation
- P_{thermo} [Pa]: Overpressure of the inclusion
- P_{trap} [Pa]: Pressure at entrapment conditions
- T_{trap} [K]: Temperature at entrapment conditions
- $V_{host}(P, T)$ [m^3]: Unit-cell volume of the host mineral at pressure (P) and temperature (T)
- P_{inc} [Pa]: Residual inclusion pressure
- $V_{inc}(P, T)$ [m^3]: Unit-cell volume of the inclusion mineral at pressure (P) and temperature (T)

Greek Characters

- ν [-]: Poisson's Ratio
- σ^{thermo} [Pa]: Isotropic stress tensor in Voigt notation representing uniform overpressure within the inclusion
- α [-]: Power-law criterion parameter for mixed-mode fracture behavior

Abbreviations and Special Functions

- **XFEM**: eXtended Finite Element Method
- **CZM**: Cohesive Zone Model
- **TSL**: Traction-Separation Law
- **EoS**: Equation of State
- f_{tol} : Tolerance for additional crack growth in ABAQUS XFEM
- $f_{\text{tol}^{\#}}$: Tolerance for existing crack extension in ABAQUS XFEM

Keywords:

Host-inclusion systems, Geological applications, Residual Stress Relaxation, Brittle Fracture, Extended Finite Element Method (XFEM)

4.2 INTRODUCTION

Inclusions trapped in diamonds are a fundamental source of information to probe the Earth's interior at the conditions at which diamonds grew. In order to constrain the complex history of growth and exhumation of diamonds, it is fundamental to determine the pressure (P) and temperature (T) of encapsulation of the inclusion minerals in the diamond host (e.g., Nestola et al., 2018; Pearson et al., 2014; Shirey et al., 2013). Entrapment pressures can be obtained in a variety of manners including elastic geothermobarometry, a method that exploits the contrast in elastic properties between the host and inclusion minerals to determine the pressure at which the inclusion has been enclosed in its host (Angel, Alvaro, et al., 2015; Angel et al., 2022; Angel, Nimis, et al., 2015; Anzolini et al., 2019; Howell et al., 2012; Kohn et al., 2023; Nestola et al., 2019). For the case of inclusion in diamonds, when the diamonds are studied at the Earth's surface, the inclusions are typically over-pressurized because the diamond is much stiffer and possesses a lower thermal expansion than all of the silicate minerals found as inclusions. Upon exhumation to ambient conditions, the diamond expands less than the inclusion, and, as a consequence, when the diamond is in the laboratory the inclusion crystal is constrained to have a smaller volume (i.e., higher pressure) than a free crystal of the same mineral would

have at room conditions. Elastic geothermobarometry has been applied to various types of inclusions in diamonds (Anzolini, 2018; Anzolini et al., 2016; Cohen & Rosenfeld, 1979; Harris et al., 1970; Howell et al., 2010; Howell, Wood, et al., 2012; Howell & Nasdala, 2008; Izraeli et al., 1999; Kueter et al., 2016; Nestola et al., 2011; Sobolev et al., 2000) under the main assumption that the rheology of both the diamond and the inclusion was elastic during the entire exhumation. In the case of inelastic (i.e., plastic, brittle, viscous) deformation of the host after diamond growth and inclusion entrapment, the inclusion's stress may be less than what expected if the behavior was purely elastic. In this case the pressure of the inclusion is said to be inelastically relaxed, and the amount of pressure relaxation should properly be accounted for in order to correctly estimate the P and T conditions of entrapment. The mechanism that leads to the inelastic relaxation of the inclusion's stress and the magnitude of the relaxation depend on a range of factors including among others the pressure and temperature (i.e., depth) at which the inclusion was entrapped, the velocity of the exhumation process, the presence of fluids (Campomenosi et al., 2023; Nimis et al., 2016; Zhong et al., 2024). The traces of brittle and viscous deformation in the diamond host around the inclusion can be detected by a variety of techniques, including X-ray micro-tomography (Mazzucchelli et al., 2016; Nimis et al., 2016; Rustioni et al., 2015; Wenz et al., 2019) and topography (e.g., Agrosi et al., 2017), and EBSD (e.g., Howell, Piazzolo, et al., 2012). The residual strain and stress of the inclusions can be determined using X-ray diffraction and, for specific phases, Raman spectroscopy (Anzolini et al., 2019; Howell, Wood, et al., 2012; Howell & Nasdala, 2008; Murri et al., 2018). By combining different techniques, it is therefore possible to determine the residual stress of the inclusion and to find evidence of inelastic processes that could have affected the stress of the inclusion. One example for which the inclusions pressures have been very carefully determined is that of diamonds from Udachnaya mine, for which the residual pressures determined on most of the inclusions are lower than 0.5 GPa (see Figure 4.1). This value of residual pressure would correspond to entrapment conditions at pressures and temperatures lower than the diamond stability field if the deformation of the host and the inclusion from entrapment conditions to the Earth's surface were purely

elastic. However, some exceptional residual pressure values, such as those from the Changma Kimberlite Belt in China, have been recorded to reach as high as 1.4 GPa (Wang et al., 2023). This suggests that the entrapment pressures recalculated with purely elastic models are underestimated, pointing to a possible release of the residual pressures of the inclusions due to fractures and/or viscous deformation (e.g., Zhong et al., 2018). Previous studies showed that most of the inclusions in these samples are surrounded by fractures which are filled by phases that are likely precipitated from a fluid (Angel et al., 2022; Nimis et al., 2016; Rustioni, 2016; Rustioni et al., 2016). As the presence of fractures in diamond-inclusions systems is common, and often leads to the underestimation of the entrapment conditions of these samples, we have investigated the fracture mechanism of the olivine-in-diamond system using numerical modeling. With this approach we can evaluate how fractures develop around olivine inclusions because of the overpressure developed in the inclusion during the exhumation. Our results also allow us to assess the amount of relaxation of the inclusion pressure due to fracture opening, compared to what expected from a purely elastic behavior.

4.3 METHODS

In our simplified model we split the calculation of the strain and stress of the inclusion into two steps. First, the strain of the inclusion is computed due to the elastic deformation of the cavity of the host diamond from entrapment to the final (P_{end}, T_{end}) conditions. This step assumes that during the fast exhumation of the diamond to the Earth's surface the behavior of the host is mainly elastic, without any viscous relaxation. In the second step, the elastic interaction between the host and the inclusion is accounted for, and the overpressure of the inclusion (i.e., the difference of the inclusion pressure with respect to the external ambient pressure) is calculated. The initiation and propagation of fractures are

evaluated as a consequence of the inclusion overpressure. Our calculations assume that both the host and the inclusions have isotropic elasticity and the fracture properties of the diamond host are also isotropic. Moreover, we assume that the system is dry and does not contain any fluid neither around the olivine inclusion nor as fluid inclusions in the diamond host.

Remark 1: Clarification on Terminology (Inclusion vs. Inhomogeneity)

To prevent any misunderstanding, we use the term 'inclusion' in this manuscript to refer to any material embedded within a host matrix, regardless of whether its material properties differ from those of the host. In several scientific communities, an inclusion with properties different from the surrounding matrix might typically be referred to as an 'inhomogeneity.' However, we choose to use the term 'inclusion' consistently throughout to align with geological terminology, recognizing the embedded material as an inclusion even when its properties differ significantly from the host.

4.3.1 The strain and stress of the inclusion upon exhumation

The strain generated in the inclusion upon exhumation is calculated by assuming that the initial (P_{trap}, T_{trap}) and final (P_{end}, T_{end}) conditions are hydrostatic and known. When the host-diamond is exhumed to the final external pressure and temperature (P_{end}, T_{end}) , the inclusion is constrained to the volume of the cavity at these conditions. We assume that the inclusion completely fills the cavity without empty spaces at both entrapment and at every step of the exhumation. As a first approximation, the volume change of the inclusion is imposed by that of the host, as calculated from entrapment to the final conditions (Angel et al., 2020; Mazzucchelli et al., 2019). By calling $V_{host}(P, T)$ and $V_{inc}(P, T)$ the unit-cell volume of the host and the inclusion, respectively, at a given P and T , the variation of the unit-cell volume of the inclusion is determined as:

$$\frac{V_{host}(P_{trap}, T_{trap})}{V_{host}(P_{end}, T_{end})} = \frac{V_{inc}(P_{trap}, T_{trap})}{V_{inc}(P_{thermo}, T_{end})} \quad (1)$$

The volume of the host at entrapment and final conditions are determined from the equation of state (EoS) of diamond reported by (Angel, Alvaro, et al., 2015). The volume of the olivine inclusion at entrapment conditions is determined from the volume EoS of Angel et al. (2018). The $V_{inc}(P_{thermo}, T_{end})$ is obtained from Eq. (1), and represents the unit-cell volume of the confined inclusion when the host is at room conditions (P_{end}, T_{end}). The corresponding pressure P_{thermo} can be determined by the equation of state (EoS) of the inclusion at the volume $V_{inc}(P_{thermo}, T_{end})$ and temperature T_{end} . Once the value of P_{thermo} of the inclusion is obtained from the equation of state, the components of the corresponding isotropic stress tensor (in Voigt notation; Voigt, 1910) are obtained as:

$$\sigma^{thermo} = [P_{thermo} \ P_{thermo} \ P_{thermo} \ 0 \ 0 \ 0]^T \quad (2)$$

This is a virtual stress state, which does not satisfy the mechanical equilibrium between the host and the inclusion mineral. The interaction between the host and the inclusion must be accounted for in order to obtain the final configuration of the system at mechanical equilibrium, and therefore the final stress and strain of the inclusion. Most models for Raman thermobarometry assume that the rheology is purely elastic, and therefore implement various elastic formulations of the inclusion problem to solve for the interaction between the host and the inclusion, depending if isotropic or anisotropic properties are used (e.g., Angel et al., 2014, 2017; Guiraud & Powell, 2006; Mazzucchelli et al., 2019; Morganti et al., 2020; Moulas et al., 2023; Zhang, 1998; Zhong et al., 2019). In our model, we evaluate two scenarios of interaction. In the first one, the interaction is assumed to be purely elastic, whereas in the second scenario, a fracture criterion is implemented in order to evaluate the final pressure of the inclusion due to fracture initiation and propagation.

4.3.2 The host-inclusion interaction

Table 4.1. Elastic properties of host and inclusion minerals

Mineral Type	Young's Modulus [GPa]	Poisson's Ratio [-]
Diamond	$1.14 \cdot 10^3$	0.0724
Olivine	$1.90 \cdot 10^2$	0.2499

The mechanical interaction between the host and the inclusion is evaluated by means of the Finite Element Method (FEM) using the software ABAQUS/CAE version 2020 (Dassault Systèmes Simulia Corp, 2012). To this aim, we developed several 3D finite element (FE) geometrical models in which spheroidal inclusions with various aspect ratios are included in a host with cubic shape (see Figure 4.2(a)). In order to avoid the effects of pressure on the inclusion due to its proximity to the host surface and to make the analysis insensitive to the shape of the host, the ratio between the longest axis of the inclusion and the side of the host is always maintained at or below $1/25$ for all models (Mazzucchelli et al., 2018; Zhong et al., 2021). Without loss of generality, in our analyses, we exploited the symmetry arising from the chosen geometry, isotropic elastic properties, as well as the loading and boundary conditions. Because of this choice, only $1/8$ of the entire 3D system is modeled and analyzed (see Fig. 2.2).

At the beginning of each FE analysis, the stress obtained from Eq. (2) is applied as a prestress to the inclusion, while a hydrostatic stress is applied to the external surfaces of the host and taken equal to the ambient pressure (namely equal to 10^5 Pa). As a consequence, the host-inclusion system is initially in a non-equilibrated configuration, since

the tractions at the host-inclusion interface are not balanced. Suitable Dirichlet boundary conditions are applied to the host to prevent rigid body motions, and the purely elastic interaction is evaluated with FEM assuming linear elasticity with the elastic properties (i.e., Poisson's ratio and Young's modulus) reported in Table 4.11.

The final residual stress and strain of the inclusion are the results of each finite element analysis. Since the inclusions are ellipsoidal and linear elasticity is assumed, the solutions from the FE analyses were compared to the strain and stress obtained from the analytical

solution of Eshelby (1957) for the same configuration, obtaining a maximum difference on the average pressure of the inclusion of less than 0.01% across all models. This allows us to check the elastic solution and perform a mesh convergence analysis in the elastic regime. In the finite element model, the regions with high stress concentrations and significant geometric distortions were carefully refined. These include the inclusion itself and its surrounding areas (considering an offset from the inclusion having a length approximately equal to twice its semiminor axis), which are critical for fracture propagation, as indicated in Figure 4.2. For these areas, we employed C3D8I elements from the ABAQUS element library, i.e., 8-node linear brick elements with incompatible modes. These elements were specifically chosen for their superior ability to handle complex stress states and effectively mitigate mesh distortion. Conversely, for the broader areas of the host material where a detailed stress analysis was less critical, we utilized 10-node quadratic tetrahedral elements (C3D10) from the Abaqus element library. This choice was made to optimize computational efficiency while still ensuring accurate results across regions that are less relevant for fracture propagation. The final chosen mesh information, comprising the type and total number of elements, according to the different critical (namely, the inclusion and its surrounding areas) or non-critical regions (i.e., the host far away from the inclusion) for different olivine shapes are summarized in Table 4.2.

Table 4.2. Type and total number of elements (to model the host, the inclusion, and the enrichment area around the inclusion) considered to build the Finite Element Abaqus solution for inclusion aspect ratios of 4:1:1 and 10:1:1.

Benchmark	# C3D10 elements in the Host	# C3D8I elements in the enrichment around the inclusion	# C3D8I elements in the Inclusion
4:1:1	29,276	250,104	58,792

10:1:1	21,860	142,080	38,208
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To study crack initiation, propagation, and their consequent impact on the stress and strain in the inclusions, we employed the eXtended Finite Element Method (XFEM) (Moës et al., 1999). In XFEM, aside from standard shape functions, enrichment functions are incorporated to model discontinuities such as cracks, based on the partition of unity (Melenk & Babuška, 1996). In addition to XFEM, we utilize the Cohesive Zone Model (CZM), which provides a phenomenological description of discrete fracture as a material separation across a surface, namely describing the material behavior in the fracture process zone using traction-separation laws (TSL) (Barenblatt, 1962). Within the CZM, the creation of a new fracture surface is accomplished by allowing initially coherent element boundaries to open according to a cohesive law that models a gradual loss of strength with an increasing separation. The cohesive law determines the work of separation, or fracture energy, required for the complete formation of a free surface (Camacho & Ortiz, 1996). In order to identify the locations of crack nucleation and propagation, we adopt the Rankine criterion that is widely adopted in modeling both brittle and quasi-brittle materials (J.-Y. Wu et al., 2019). According to this criterion, either a new crack emerges or a pre-existing crack extends when the maximum principal stress at an integration point exceeds the material's failure strength threshold. In our analyses, the crack propagation direction lies orthogonal to the maximum principal stress direction (Dassault Systèmes Simulia Corp, 2012; Wells & Sluys, 2001). This approach is often favored over other approaches like the maximum circumferential tensile stress criterion, largely because of its capacity for nonlocal calculations, providing a more generalized and robust solution (Unger et al., 2007; J.-Y. Wu et al., 2019).

Before the fracture initiation, the behaviour of the material is linear elastic. Then, the onset of fracture leads to a softening behaviour in the material and to a degradation of the stiffness. To model the post-peak softening behavior, a linear TSL within ABAQUS is

adopted. After reaching its peak, the traction decreases linearly until a material achieves a critical separation displacement, at which point the traction becomes zero (Camacho & Ortiz, 1996).

The inherent softening of the material after the fracture initiation may lead to issues in numerical convergence (Dassault Systèmes Simulia Corp, 2012; Duarte et al., 2017). In order to enhance convergence, we adopt a viscous regularization approach (Langenfeld et al., 2022), such that the tangent stiffness matrix of the softening material remains positive for sufficiently small-time increments. A small value of the viscosity parameter equal to 10^{-4} Pa·s is used within the viscous regularization, in order to improve the convergence without affecting the results. To this aim, we ensured that the energy dissipated due to this regularization remained below 5% of the model's internal energy, thereby preserving the physical meaning of our results. Further details on the evaluation of the parameters and outcome of viscous regularization in our models are reported in Appendix A.

The fracture toughness determines a material's resistance to crack propagation and is represented by the parameters K_{IC} , K_{IIC} , and K_{IIIC} for the normal, shear, and tangential modes, respectively. Since limited data are available on the shear and tangential modes of single-crystal diamonds, drawing insights from Zhang et al., (2005), we assume that $K_{IC} = K_{IIC} = K_{IIIC}$. This simplifying assumption, aligned with diamond's isotropic nature, facilitates our analysis by maintaining uniform fracture toughness across all modes.

Critical energy release rates G_{IC} , G_{IIC} , and G_{IIIC} for each mode are calculated using the relation $G_{iC} = \frac{K_i^c}{E}$ (with $i = \{I, II, III\}$) where K represents the respective mode's fracture toughness, and E is the Young's modulus. Although the relation for G_{IIIC} could theoretically include adjustments for the material's Poisson's ratio, given diamond's low Poisson's ratio ($\nu=0.0724$), its effect on G_{IIIC} is minimal. Therefore, for simplification and to ensure consistency in our computational model, we used $G_{IC} = G_{IIC} = G_{IIIC}$.

Thus, the mixed-mode fracture behavior is characterized by the power-law criterion:

$$\left(\frac{G_I}{G_{IC}}\right)^\alpha + \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_{IIC}}\right)^\alpha + \left(\frac{G_{III}}{G_{IIIC}}\right)^\alpha = 1 \quad (3)$$

with $\alpha=1$, indicating that all fracture modes equally influence the damage process in the diamond (Alfano & Crisfield, 2001). This approach aligns with the isotropic fracture behaviour of the material.

4.4 RESULTS

Soft inclusions in a stiff host develop a pressure higher than the external pressure during the exhumation from the entrapment conditions at crustal or mantle conditions to the Earth's surface. We assumed that the olivine inclusions were entrapped in their diamond host at pressure and temperature conditions equal to 5.5 GPa and 1473.15 K, respectively, a typical average condition for olivine inclusions in diamonds from the Udachnaya kimberlite (Agrosi et al., 2016; Nestola et al., 2011). Our elastic calculations show that the maximum overpressure (defined as the difference between the inclusion pressure and the external ambient pressure acting on the diamond host) developed by the olivine inclusions exhumed to ambient conditions is 1 GPa, and, therefore, we used this value as the highest limit of inclusion overpressure in our models.

4.4.1 Damage initiation and fracture nucleation: shape and size effects of inclusions

Our investigation delved into the influence of the inclusion shape and size on damage initiation and fracture nucleation. In this study, damage initiation refers to the point when the damage variable (D) in XFEM (referred to as STATUSXFEM in ABAQUS) becomes greater than 0 but less than 1 ($0 < D < 1$), indicating that the material is experiencing microcracking or inelastic deformation, as shown in Figure 4.3(b). Fracture nucleation occurs when the damage variable reaches a value of 1, meaning the material is fully

fractured and lost its load-bearing capacity, as depicted in Figure 4.3(c). We subsequently explored both the impact of the inclusion size and shape on damage initiation.

Figure 4.4 clearly shows that, for three distinct inclusion sizes with constant aspect ratios (here both the 4:1:1 and the 10:1:1 scenarios, with dimensions chosen to ensure equal volumes for different shapes, were investigated), a consistent critical fracture strength is required for damage initiation. Above this strength threshold, no damage occurs. This observation underscores the independence of damage initiation from the size of the inclusion. This observation aligns with the findings of Tanné et al., (2018), who conducted a damage initiation study for an elliptical hole in an infinite domain subjected to far-field loading. Additionally, we observed that, for damage initiation, the critical fracture strength is entirely independent of fracture toughness, as showcased in Figure 4.4.

In Figures Figure 4.4 to Figure 4.7, the precision of the critical fracture strength, overpressure, and fracture toughness values was determined manually. We incrementally adjusted these parameters in steps of 0.001 GPa (or 0.008 MPa·m^{0.5} for fracture toughness) and observed when either damage initiation or fracture nucleation occurred. A negative precision value indicates that the parameter was increased from lower values until damage initiation occurred, while a positive precision value indicates that the parameter was decreased from higher values until either damage initiation or fracture nucleation occurred, depending on the specific context.

Figure 4.4. Fracture strength needed for the damage initiation ($0 < D < 1$), for ellipsoidal inclusion of aspect ratios 4:1:1 and 10:1:1 with respect to different inclusion sizes and fracture toughness, for the inclusion overpressure $P_{thermo} = 1$ GPa. The results highlight that the damage initiation simply depends on the shape of the inclusion and is independent of fracture toughness and inclusion size. The critical fracture strength is the value above which no damage can initiate and is approximately 0.745 GPa and 0.792GPa for 4:1:1 and 10:1:1 shapes, respectively (with a precision of +0.001 GPa).

We also explored the minimum overpressure of the inclusion needed for damage initiation in elongated ellipsoidal inclusions with two aspect ratios (i.e., 4:1:1 and 10:1:1) by varying the fracture strength (see Figure 4.5). A constant fracture toughness is adopted for the diamond (namely, equal to $0.1 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{0.5}$). However, the results of Fig. 5 are not affected by this specific choice since the initiation of damage is controlled exclusively by the fracture strength of the material. Figure 4.5 shows that the minimum overpressure required to initiate damage in the diamond host around the olivine inclusion linearly depends on the magnitude of the fracture strength of the diamond host. For all values of fracture strength, more overpressure is required to initiate damage around the inclusion with an aspect ratio of 4:1:1. This indicates that the stress concentration at the tip of the inclusion, which increases with its aspect ratio, plays a key role in controlling the damage initiation. Furthermore, we observe that for low values of fracture strength, the curves in Figure 4.5 converge, meaning that the overpressure required to initiate damage becomes independent of the aspect ratio of the inclusion. For high fracture strength values, a lower overpressure is required to initiate damage around the inclusion with an aspect ratio of 10:1:1.

Assuming a maximum inclusion overpressure of 1 GPa for the host-inclusion system exhumed to room conditions, our observations suggest that a fracture strength of approximately 0.745 GPa is needed for damage initiation in an ellipsoidal inclusion with an aspect ratio of 4:1:1 (as discussed in Figure 4.4). However, to capture resolvable fracture propagation, we adopted a slightly lower fracture strength of 0.738 GPa. This value was chosen to ensure consistent observation and analysis of fracture propagation in all

subsequent models, particularly when examining the effects of inclusion shape and size after fracture propagation.

With the fracture strength set at 0.738 GPa, we then investigated how the aspect ratios affect the required overpressure for damage initiation, as depicted in Figure 4.6. We identified a critical overpressure threshold; damage initiation only occurs above this threshold for the specified fracture strength. Due to high stress concentrations at the tips of prolate inclusions, the critical overpressure decreases as the aspect ratio increases. This

analysis focuses solely on the initiation of damage, as previously explained, and is independent on the size of the inclusion and the toughness of the diamond.

Then, we turned our attention to understanding parameters affecting fracture nucleation. In our investigations, we maintain a constant fracture strength of 0.738 GPa. By systematically varying the size of the inclusion, we plotted the critical fracture toughness required for the nucleation of the first fracture, as illustrated in Figure 4.7.

Figure 4.7 reveals that fracture toughness significantly affects fracture nucleation, showing a linear scaling of the critical fracture toughness with the power 1/6 of the inclusion volume. Critical fracture toughness is established as the threshold value: brittle fractures will nucleate at or below this level, but not above it, for a given fracture strength. The dashed black line represents an extrapolation for the actual volume of natural inclusions, typically larger than $10^6 \mu\text{m}^3$. This extrapolation suggests that the critical fracture toughness of the diamond surrounding natural inclusions with a volume of $10^6 \mu\text{m}^3$ is approximately $1.35 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{0.5}$.

4.4.2 The influence on residual inclusion pressure (P_{inc}) due to the shape of the inclusions

We selected a fracture strength of 0.738 GPa and a low fracture toughness of $0.1 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{0.5}$ for our subsequent studies on fracture propagation in order to ensure the occurrence of brittle fractures—characterized by high fracture strength and low toughness. This choice aims to precisely study how these properties influence the mechanics of brittle fracturing, particularly in the context of different inclusion geometries.

The extent of the fractures developed around the inclusion is a consequence of the stress concentration and increases with the aspect ratio (see Figure 4.8). As shown in Figure 4.9, the extent of the fractures is tightly related to the amount of the inclusion pressure that is relaxed as a result of fracturing. Inclusions with an aspect ratio of 3:1:1 or less show an average residual pressure identical to that expected assuming a purely elastic behaviour, implying no significant relaxation due to fractures. The effect of fractures becomes resolvable for the 4:1:1 aspect ratio (Figure 4.9). The relaxation of pressure due to fractures further increases for inclusions with larger aspect ratios. However, inclusions that are more elongated (up to an extreme aspect ratio of 10:1:1) do not experience a significantly larger relaxation of pressure.

Figure 4.9. Relaxed pressure of the inclusion after the fracture opening as a function of the normalized aspect ratio of the inclusion. The latter is represented with the major axis as the denominator (e.g., aspect ratio 4:1:1 becomes 1/4). All these analyses are done by considering fracture strength = 0.738 GPa and fracture toughness = 0.1 MPa·m^{0.5}. A volume of approximately 4090 μm³ is assumed for all shapes. The relaxed pressure corresponds to the residual inclusion pressure (P_{inc}), calculated as the average pressure across all elements at the end of the simulation.

Figure 4.10 showcases the stress distribution for two distinct geometric configurations: 4:1:1 and 10:1:1. In their initial elastic analysis phases (depicted in subfigures (a) and (c)), both configurations exhibit a uniform stress distribution. However, the 10:1:1 shape inherently has a more relaxed profile as compared to the 4:1:1 shape. As fractures develop, as seen in Figure 4.10(b) and (d), this uniformity is lost. The 4:1:1 shape begins to display a non-uniform stress distribution because of the appearance of small fractures, whereas the

10:1:1 shape, which induces the growth of a larger fracture, exhibits a more pronounced deviation from uniform stress. This delineates the transformative effect of fractures on stress distribution within the inclusion.

4.4.3 The influence on residual inclusion pressure (P_{inc}) due to the size of the inclusion

Simulations were conducted to assess the impact of the size of the inclusion on the residual inclusion pressure (P_{inc}). The diamond host has a failure strength of 0.738 GPa and a

fracture toughness of $0.1 \text{ MPa} \cdot \text{m}^{0.5}$, while the aspect ratio of the inclusions is fixed to 10:1:1. The numerical results reported in Figure 4.11 show a distinct relationship between the volume of the inclusion and the residual inclusion pressure (P_{inc}). As the inclusion size increases, P_{inc} initially decreases because of the fracture propagation driven by the stress concentrations at the tip of the inclusion. However, with the current choice of fracture parameters, P_{inc} becomes independent on the inclusion size for inclusions having a volume larger than $33 \mu\text{m}^3$. This shows that, as the inclusion size increases, the system approaches a critical state where the available mechanical energy for crack propagation is fully utilized. Beyond this point, the material's inherent toughness and strength prevent further effective stress redistribution, limiting fracture propagation. Consequently, the residual inclusion pressure remains constant, reflecting that additional increases in inclusion size do not yield further stress intensification or fracture propagation due to the saturation of energy absorption capacity in the material (Anderson, 2017). The behaviour summarized in Figure 4.11 is also observed for natural fluid inclusions entrapped in mineral phases. Measurements of fluid inclusions in quartz with a wide range of sizes show that the internal pressure is higher in small inclusions and reaches a constant value for large inclusions (e.g., Fig. 3 in Campione et al., 2015).

4.5 DISCUSSION AND IMPLICATIONS

The determination of the pressure of entrapment of mineral inclusions in diamonds is fundamental in order to constrain the geological history of diamonds. Current models assume that the diamond host and its inclusions behave purely elastically during the fast exhumation from the Earth's mantle to the ambient conditions at the Earth's surface where diamonds are found. However, this assumption is challenged by the fact that measurements on natural diamonds often reveal extensive brittle deformation around the minerals inclusions contained in them, such as olivines, which are often surrounded by fluid rims (Nimis et al., 2016). Moreover, the measured residual pressure of such inclusions is too low to be explained by simple elastic models, as the recalculated entrapment conditions would place the diamond growth at pressures lower than the geological window of diamond

formation (Shirey et al., 2013). Even elastic models that include the effect due to the presence of a fluid rim around the inclusion cannot explain the reduced residual pressure observed in natural olivine inclusions, as the additional contribution arising from the opening of fractures is not accounted for (Angel et al., 2023). Therefore, a comprehensive understanding of the brittle fracture mechanisms around inclusions in diamonds is required in order to develop more accurate models of geobarometry. To this end, simulation modeling provides a straightforward way to test and explore different “what-if” scenarios. Namely, our models to delve into fracture openings in host-inclusion systems consider a combination of XFEM and CZM and our numerical results explore the effects of brittle fractures on damage initiation, fracture nucleation and propagation, with a particular emphasis on the roles of inclusion shape, size and fracture properties of diamond.

Our findings reveal that:

- Damage initiation is found to be independent of the inclusion’s size and fracture toughness of the diamond, depending solely on the inclusion's shape and the diamond’s fracture strength. Subsequently, once damage initiates, fracture nucleation becomes dependent on both the inclusion’s size and fracture toughness of the diamond.
- Critical values of fracture strength and toughness exist for propagation of fractures around olivine inclusions in diamond. In particular for a diamond’s fracture strength above 0.8 GPa and fracture toughness above $1.35 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{0.5}$ (for inclusions with volume $>10^6 \mu\text{m}^3$), no fracture nucleation is observed for the typical overpressure of olivine inclusions. The former is determined to be independent of inclusion’s size, while the toughness exhibits a dependency on size, with a linear relationship with the power 1/6 of the volume.
- Furthermore, our investigation reveals that when considering only the effect of inclusion’s shape, the relaxation of inclusion residual pressure due to brittle fractures is relatively low, approximately 5-6% of the inclusion overpressure

(P_{thermo}), bringing the residual pressure to about 0.76 GPa for an entrapment pressure-temperature conditions of 5.5 GPa and 1473.15 K. Moreover, our analysis highlights that the damage initiation is significantly influenced by the stress concentration induced by the aspect ratio of the inclusion. However, while the initial increase in aspect ratio significantly impacts fracture propagation, this effect diminishes for inclusions with extreme aspect ratios, such as 10:1:1. As a result, prolate inclusions with extreme aspect ratios do not experience a significantly larger relaxation of the residual pressure (see Figure 4.9).

Despite showing that the opening of fractures in diamond around olivine inclusions affects the relaxation of the inclusion pressure, the models herein presented do not fully explain the observations obtained from natural olivine inclusions in diamonds (Figure 4.1). Measurements of natural samples show that the residual pressure of fractured olivine inclusions in diamond is often below 0.5 GPa (Angel et al., 2022; Rustioni, 2016). A residual pressure of 0.5 GPa is considered a threshold value, as any pressure lower than this value would not be compatible with an entrapment in the diamond stability field, unless an inelastic process relaxes the pressure of the inclusion during the exhumation (Angel et al., 2022). The observation of olivine inclusions with a residual pressure below this threshold (see Figure 4.1) suggests that a higher degree of relaxation occurs in natural samples than our models predict. Moreover, fractures are also observed around olivine inclusions with an aspect ratio lower than 4:1:1, despite the fracture properties implemented in our model being significantly lower than the strength of 4 GPa and fracture toughness of 5-16 MPa $m^{0.5}$, reported for natural single crystal diamonds (Field & Pickles, 1996; Hess, 2012; Liang et al., 2009).

The lower residual pressure observed in natural inclusions might be due to other factors not included in our model, such as viscous relaxation. However, the quick ascent of the kimberlite magma that brings the diamonds from mantle depths to the Earth's surface conditions limits the amount of viscous relaxation (Zhong et al., 2018). Moreover, the viscous relaxation of the diamond host would reduce the inclusion overpressure, therefore

limiting the nucleation of fractures, a behavior that would not agree with the observation of extended fracture networks around natural olivine inclusions. Additionally, the exhumation rate may influence the brittle/ductile behavior of diamonds. High strain rates during exhumation, as highlighted by Luisier et al., (2023), can promote earlier fracture initiation due to induced brittle behavior, explaining the early fractures observed in natural samples. Furthermore, real inclusions often have edges or corners, unlike the ellipsoidal point singularities modeled in our simulations. These corners induce stress concentrations which could lead to earlier fracture initiation, a factor not captured by our models but observed in natural samples (Whitney et al., 2000). Fracture strength is known to decrease with the presence of defects and impurities, and it inversely correlates with the presence of pre-existing fractures (Field & Pickles, 1996). Similar to this, the strength of a material is reduced by the presence of inclusions (Anderson, 2017; Foroozmehr et al., 2017) and the toughness is reduced due to their size and distribution (Oh et al., 2002; Srivastava et al., 2014; Zhu et al., 2020). Our simulations show that the magnitude of the critical fracture toughness, which quantifies the highest value of toughness of the diamond host that still permits the opening of cracks, given a specific volume of the inclusion, increases as a function of the volume of the inclusion (see Figure 4.7). On the other hand, experimental studies found that the fracture toughness of a material decreases with increasing inclusion size (Oh et al., 2002; Zhu et al., 2020). Therefore, a natural diamond containing olivine inclusions has a lower fracture toughness than a perfect single crystal of diamond would have, and a critical threshold size of the inclusion, for which the toughness of the host diamond falls below the critical toughness necessary to open fractures around that inclusion, may exist. Such behaviour would explain the decrease of fractures intensity with inclusion size observed for olivine inclusions in diamonds by Synchrotron Radiation X-ray Tomographic Microscopy investigations (Rustioni et al., 2016). A similar dependency is commonly observed also for fluid inclusions in metamorphic rocks, for which a threshold size for the decrepitation of the inclusion is observed (e.g. Campione et al., 2015). Moreover, fluid rims are typically observed surrounding olivine inclusions in diamonds (Nimis et al., 2016). The presence of fluids can decrease the fracture strength of the

diamond host (Grassl et al., 2019; Lacazette, 1990), therefore promoting the fracture nucleation. Lower values of fracture strength and toughness would require less overpressure of the inclusion and less stress concentration to trigger the fracturing. Therefore, fracture could nucleate around inclusions with low aspect ratios and whose pressure is partially viscously relaxed, leading to a lower residual pressure of the inclusion compared to that predicted in the current models. These findings underscore the need for advanced numerical tools that consider the complex interplay of the geometry of the host-inclusion system, anisotropic material properties of host and inclusion, the fracture properties of host, and the presence of fluids and defects in order to build more accurate models to constrain the geological history of diamonds.

4.6 APPENDIX A. SENSITIVITY STUDIES TO DIFFERENT NUMERICAL PARAMETERS: TOLERANCES, PSEUDO-TIME STEP SIZE, AND VISCOSITY COEFFICIENT

In this appendix, a comprehensive sensitivity analysis for the numerical parameters needed to utilize XFEM within ABAQUS/CAE for the fracture simulations of the host-inclusion system is reported. The parameters under investigation include the pseudo-time step size, viscosity coefficient, and tolerances for damage initiation and fracture propagation.

Effect of tolerances

Tolerances have particular importance due to their potential influence on the simulation outcomes. Functioning as a pivotal feature within ABAQUS XFEM, tolerance parameters determine the numerical level of acceptance such that an additional crack is introduced, or the length of an existing crack is extended during equilibrium increments, called f_{tol} and f_{tol}^g , respectively, in ABAQUS/CAE. This is defined by an admissible range as $1 < f < 1 + f_{tol} / f_{tol}^g$, where f represents the ratio of fracture strength to the maximum principal stress of the element (Dassault Systèmes Simulia Corp, 2012).

While it is commonly recommended to use a reduced f_{tol} value, as advised in (Nuclear Regulatory Commission, 2020), it is crucial to find suitable tolerance values balancing the

trade-off between providing reliable analysis and keeping the computational time needed for simulations to an acceptable level. To investigate the influence of tolerance limits, we conducted a comprehensive study, considering two different levels outlined in Table A.1. The analysis ranges from stringent criteria, with both f_{tol} and f_{tol}^g set to 10^{-6} for both shapes, and finally, to more lenient criteria (i.e., f_{tol} and f_{tol}^g both equal to 10^{-5}).

Table A.1. Residual inclusion pressure for different the tolerance limits (f_{tol} and f_{tol}^g)

Shapes	Tolerance for additional crack [f_{tol}]	Tolerance for existing crack growth [f_{tol}^g]	Residual Inclusion Pressure [GPa]
4:1:1	10^{-6}	10^{-6}	0.8115
	10^{-5}	10^{-5}	0.8116
10:1:1	10^{-6}	10^{-6}	0.7591
	10^{-5}	10^{-5}	0.7591

Our studies highlight that using the stricter criterium leads to negligible changes in the solutions for the considered problems. Therefore, we identify $f_{tol} = f_{tol}^g = 10^{-5}$ as a reasonable choice for all analyses reported in the present work.

Effect of pseudo-time step size and viscosity coefficients

In our numerical sensitivity study, we specifically focused on the 10:1:1 shape due to its pronounced stress concentration at the inclusion tip, potentially leading to unstable brittle fractures and subsequent stiffness matrix degradation (as detailed in Section 2.2).

As outlined in Section 2.2, we introduced a numerical viscosity coefficient equal to 10^{-4} Pa·s to address convergence challenges. In Table A.2 we highlight that considering a viscosity coefficient equal to 10^{-4} Pa·s allows for larger pseudo-time steps (namely, from $5 \cdot 10^{-6}$ s to 10^{-5} s) without affecting results in terms of relevant quantities such as the residual inclusion pressure. Therefore, the usage of this approach resulted in a remarkable reduction in computational time, from 48 hours to 29 hours.

Table A.2. Effect of time increment on the residual inclusion pressure and execution time

Time increment [s]	Viscosity coefficient [Pa·s]	Residual inclusion pressure [GPa]	Execution time [h]
10^{-5}	10^{-4}	0.7591	29.46
$5 \cdot 10^{-6}$		0.7591	48.48

Then, for the optimal pseudo-time increment equal to $5 \cdot 10^{-6}$, we varied the viscosity coefficient (namely, we set it equal to $5 \cdot 10^{-5}$ Pa·s and 10^{-4} Pa·s) as highlighted in Table A.3, leading to negligible variations in terms of residual pressure in the inclusion.

Table A.3: Effect of viscosity coefficient on residual inclusion pressure

Viscosity coefficient [Pa·s]	Time increment [s]	Residual inclusion pressure [GPa]
10^{-4}	$5 \cdot 10^{-6}$	0.7591
$5 \cdot 10^{-5}$		0.7598

Figure A.1 illustrates the stabilization energy dissipation, that is the stabilization energy with respect to the total strain energy of the system, for various inclusion shapes, ranging from 4:1:1 to 10:1:1, using the actual mesh specified in the analyses detailed in Section 3.2. The parameters set for these simulations include a time increment of 10^{-5} seconds, a viscosity coefficient of 10^{-4} Pa·s, and equal tolerances for f_{tol} and f_{tol}^g , set to 10^{-5} . The stabilization energy always increases, while the strain energy may decrease. Therefore, Abaqus/Standard restricts the ratio of the incremental value of the stabilization energy to the incremental value of the strain energy for each increment to ensure that this value has not exceeded the accuracy tolerance, if the ratio of the total stabilization energy to the total strain energy exceeds the accuracy tolerance.

The default accuracy tolerance used by the adaptive automatic stabilization scheme is 0.05, that is a default tolerance suitable for most applications. In fact, we can observe that, for all the shapes, the stabilization energy remains within 5% with respect to the total strain energy.

Figure A.1. Stabilization energy dissipation versus increment number for different inclusion shapes (i.e., 4:1:1, 5:1:1, and 10:1:1). Throughout the simulation, the stabilization energy never exceeds 5% of the total internal energy. Stabilization energy dissipation is the stabilization energy percentage with respect to the strain energy of the system. In this context, the increment number refers to the discrete calculation steps within a load step where the solver updates the system's state and ensures convergence before proceeding to the next increment.

Remark 2: Additional ABAQUS features in the modelling strategy

An efficient strategy for addressing issues of unstable crack growth involves allowing multiple elements at and ahead of a crack tip to fracture without imposing a substantial reduction in the increment size upon meeting the fracture criterion (Dassault Systèmes Simulia Corp, 2012). To facilitate this, the 'unstable crack growth' feature is activated in ABAQUS for all analyses. Additionally, we opted for ABAQUS's nodal smoothing feature. This technique effectively smoothens stress/strain fields ahead of the crack, contributing to enhanced result consistency.

Furthermore, the following keywords are used in all simulations:

Table A.4. ABAQUS keywords.

*Damage Initiation	TOL ERA NCE =10 ⁻⁵	GROWTH TOLERAN CE =10 ⁻⁵	Criterion = MAXPS	POSITION =NONLOCAL	SMOOTH ING =NODAL	UNSTABLE GROWTH TOLERANCE
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**PART II: BRITTLE FRACTURES
AND EDGE SINGULARITIES:
NOVEL SIMULATION
FRAMEWORK WITH PHASE
FIELD MODELLING (PFM)**

5. FUNDAMENTALS OF PHASE-FIELD MODELLING FOR FRACTURE MECHANICS

5.1 THEORY OF PHASE FIELD MODELLING (PFM)

5.1.1 Basics of Phase-Field Modelling

Over the last two decades, phase-field models have achieved significant advancements in both theoretical development and practical applications, solidifying their role in fracture mechanics research. Despite this progress, ongoing efforts focus on refining the underlying principles of these models to address complex fracture phenomena (Kristensen & Martínez-Pañeda, 2020; Sidharth & Rao, 2023).

The phase-field approach to fracture mechanics is fundamentally grounded in Griffith's energy-based framework for analyzing cracks, first proposed in 1921. This groundbreaking work laid the foundation for modern fracture mechanics by introducing the concept of energy equilibrium in cracked solids (Griffith, 1921). According to Griffith's theory, the strain energy density, Ψ , is the potential energy supplied by the internal strain energy and external forces, and the total energy variation, $d\Pi$, associated with a small increment in the crack area, dA , can be expressed in the absence of external forces as:

$$\frac{d\Pi}{dA} = \frac{d\Psi}{dA} + \frac{dW_c}{dA} \quad (5.1)$$

In Eq. (5.1), W_c represents the work required to create new crack surfaces, while the term $\frac{dW_c}{dA}$ corresponds to the critical energy release rate, G_c , which characterizes the material's resistance to fracture. These principles form the foundation of variational methods in fracture mechanics and are fundamental to the phase-field method's capability to model the initiation and evolution of cracks. Building upon Griffith's energy balance, the total energy Π in the variational framework is defined as:

$$\Pi = \Psi_s + \Psi_c - W_{ext} \quad (5.2)$$

The external potential energy functional W_{ext} is given by

$$W_{ext}(u) = \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{b} \cdot \mathbf{u} dV + \int_{\partial\Omega_h} \mathbf{h} \cdot \mathbf{u} dA \quad (5.3)$$

where:

- \mathbf{b} is prescribed body force field per unit volume
- \mathbf{h} is a boundary traction field per unit area
- Ω is the domain occupied by the solid with volume V , and
- $\partial\Omega_h$ is the portion of the boundary over which the traction \mathbf{h} is applied.

Then, the stored strain energy $\Psi_s(\mathbf{u})$, a volume integral and the surface energy $\Psi_c(\Gamma)$, a surface integral is defined as

$$\Psi_s(u) = \int_{\Omega} \psi(\epsilon) dV, \quad \Psi_c(\Gamma) = \int_{\Gamma} G_c d\Gamma \quad (5.4)$$

where

- $\psi(\epsilon)$ is the strain energy density as a function of the strain ϵ ,
- Γ represents the crack surface within the domain.
- G_c is the critical energy release rate

Refer to Figure 5.1 for a schematic illustration of the domain, boundary conditions, and the crack surface.

Figure 5.1 illustrates $\Gamma \in \Omega$ as an admissible crack set, where the displacement field \mathbf{u} remains continuous across Γ . In the variational framework for fracture, it is essential to define an energy functional that governs the entire fracture process. Francfort & Marigo, (1998) conceptualized brittle fracture as an energy minimization problem, where the pair (\mathbf{u}, Γ) minimizes the total potential energy functional Π , expressed as:

$$(\mathbf{u}, \Gamma) = \text{Arg}\{\min \Pi(\mathbf{u}, \Gamma)\} \quad (5.5)$$

Equation (5.5) is commonly referred to as a free discontinuity problem (Braides, 1998; J.-Y. Wu, Nguyen, et al., 2020), where both the displacement field \mathbf{u} and the jump set Γ are

unknown a priori. To facilitate the numerical implementation of this problem, Bourdin et al., (2000) introduced a regularized variational fracture model. This approach builds on the elliptic regularization framework initially developed by Ambrosio & Tortorelli, (1990) for image segmentation. In this formulation, a zero-width crack is approximated by a diffuse crack with a finite width determined by the length parameter l , which characterizes the localization band's width. As $l \rightarrow 0$, the solution converges to that of the original problem, in accordance with the Γ convergence theorem (Braides, 1998).

To describe this transition, the phase-field parameter ϕ is introduced as a scalar damage field that smoothly interpolates between intact and fully broken material. Specifically, $\phi = 0$ corresponds to intact material, and $\phi = 1$ corresponds to fully damaged or cracked material. The gradient of ϕ , denoted as $\nabla\phi$, controls the diffusion of damage and regularizes the crack topology.

Within this regularized variational framework, the sharp crack surface Γ is approximated by the functional $\Gamma_l(\phi)$, expressed as

$$\Gamma \approx \Gamma_l(\phi) = \int_{\Omega} \gamma(\phi, \nabla\phi) dV \quad (5.6)$$

This allows the total surface energy to be represented as:

$$\Psi_c = \int_{\Gamma} G_c d\Gamma \approx \int_{\Omega} G_c \gamma(\phi, \nabla\phi) dV \quad (5.7)$$

Here, $\gamma(\phi, \nabla\phi)$ denotes the crack surface density functional, which depends on the phase-field parameter $\phi \in [0, 1]$ and its gradient $\nabla\phi$. By introducing this smooth approximation, the need for explicit tracking of the crack surface is eliminated, making the method particularly effective for complex fracture scenarios.

Then, the stored energy functional, which is now defined as:

$$\Psi_s(\mathbf{u}, \phi) = \int_{\Omega} g(\phi) \Psi_0(\epsilon(\mathbf{u})) dV \quad (5.8)$$

In this expression, $\Psi_0(\epsilon(\mathbf{u}))$ represents the free energy density of the unbroken material, which is a function of the strain tensor $\epsilon(\mathbf{u})$, while $g(\phi)$ is the energetic degradation function. The stress tensor can be defined as $\sigma(\mathbf{u}, \phi) = \frac{\partial \Psi_s(\mathbf{u}, \phi)}{\partial \epsilon} = g(\phi) \sigma_0$, σ_0 is the stress tensor of undamaged solid.

(a) Generic geometric crack surface density function:

The phase-field method for fracture modeling introduces a geometric crack surface density function $\gamma(\phi, \nabla \phi)$, which links the crack phase-field ϕ and its gradient $\nabla \phi$ to the fracture energy. This function is expressed as:

$$\gamma(\phi, \nabla \phi) = \frac{1}{c_0} \left[\frac{1}{l} \alpha(\phi) + l |\nabla \phi|^2 \right] \quad (5.9)$$

Here, c_0 is a scaling parameter ensuring accurate reproduction of fracture energy, given by:

$$c_0 = 4 \int_0^1 \sqrt{\alpha(\beta)} d\beta \quad (5.10)$$

(J.-Y. Wu, 2017; J.-Y. Wu, Nguyen, et al., 2020). The internal length scale parameter l governs the regularization of the sharp crack into a diffuse crack, and the geometric function $\alpha(\phi)$ must satisfy $\alpha(0) = 0$ and $\alpha(1) = 1$. Wu, (2017), for instance, proposed the following quadratic form for $\alpha(\phi)$:

$$\alpha(\phi) = \xi\phi + (1 - \xi)\phi^2 \in [0,1] \quad \forall \phi \in [0,1] \quad (5.11)$$

Depending on the value of ξ , the resulting damage model varies, as summarized in Table 5.1 (J.-Y. Wu, Nguyen, et al., 2020).

Table 5.1. Generic geometric crack function $\alpha(\phi)$ and the resulting crack phase field $\phi(x)$. Adapted from (J.-Y. Wu, Nguyen, et al., 2020).

$\alpha(\phi)$	ξ	c_0	$\phi(x)$	Damage model
ϕ^2	0	2	$\exp\left(-\frac{ x }{l_0}\right)$	AT2
ϕ	1	8/3	$\left(1 - \frac{ x }{2l_0}\right)^2$	AT1
$2\phi - \phi^2$	2	π	$\left(1 - \sin\left(\frac{ x }{l_0}\right)\right)$	PF-CZM

(b) Localized Bandwidth and Applications:

In phase-field models for brittle fracture, the quadratic geometric crack function $\alpha(\phi) = \phi^2$ with $\xi = 0$ (Bourdin et al., 2000; Miehe, Welschinger, et al., 2010) and the linear counterpart $\alpha(\phi) = \phi$ with $\xi = 1$ (Pham et al., 2011) are the most commonly adopted. These functions yield a localization bandwidth with infinite support and finite support ($4l$), respectively.

For both brittle and quasi-brittle failure, Wu's PF-CZM (J.-Y. Wu, 2017; J.-Y. Wu, Nguyen, et al., 2020) employs the geometric crack function function $\alpha(\phi) = 2\phi - \phi^2$ with $\xi = 2$, resulting in a sinusoidal distribution of the crack phase-field with a finite bandwidth of πl . This choice is particularly suited for capturing cohesive fracture behavior.

(c) Energetic degradation function for cohesive cracks:

In phase-field models, the energetic degradation function $g(\phi)$ relates the crack phase-field ϕ with the stored energy functional, dictating how mechanical fields respond to changes in the crack state. It must meet the following conditions:

- $g(0) = 1$, corresponding to the intact material state,
- $g(1) = 0$, representing the fully broken state, and
- $g'(1) = 0$, ensuring smoothness near the crack tip.

Moreover, $g'(\phi) < 0$ ensures that $g(\phi)$ is a monotonically decreasing function, transitioning smoothly between the intact and fully damaged states.

Several degradation functions have been proposed in the literature, each tailored to different fracture behaviors. Table 5.2 summarizes common choices for $g(\phi)$. The quadratic polynomial, introduced by Bourdin et al., (2000) within the context of the Ambrosio & Tortorelli, (1990) elliptic regularization, is among the earliest and most widely used forms. This function has been adopted in numerous studies for brittle fracture.

Cubic polynomials, such as those introduced by Karma et al., (2001), and the third variant proposed by Borden et al., (2016), include additional flexibility for cohesive fracture modeling. For example, Borden's approach introduces an elastic domain before crack initiation by incorporating an extra parameter.

Rational forms of $g(\phi)$, as proposed by Alessi et al., (2015) and Wu, (2017), are particularly proposed in the literature for quasi-brittle and cohesive fracture. While these functions can also be applied to brittle fracture, they are predominantly used in cases where more complex crack behaviors must be modeled. The specific details of Wu's degradation function and its applications will be discussed in the following section.

Table 5.2. Common choices of energetic degradation functions $g(\phi)$. Adapted from (J.-Y. Wu, Nguyen, et al., 2020).

$g(\phi)$	Authors	Parameter Definitions
$(1 - \phi)^2$	(Bourdin et al., 2000)	-
$3(1 - \phi)^2 - 2(1 - \phi)^3$	(Karma et al., 2001)	-
$(3 - s)(1 - \phi)^2 - (2 - s)(1 - \phi)^3$	(Borden et al., 2016)	s = scaling factor
$\frac{(1 - \phi)^2}{1 + (k - 1)Q(\phi)}, Q(\phi) = 1 - (1 - \phi)^2$	(Alessi et al., 2015)	k = damage regularization parameter
$\frac{(1 - \phi)^p}{(1 - \phi)^p + Q(\phi)}, Q(\phi) = a_1\phi(1 + a_2\phi + a_2a_3\phi^2)$	(J.-Y. Wu, 2017)	p, a_1, a_2, a_3 = model fitting parameters

5.1.2 Discussion on state-of-the-art phase-field damage models

Various phase-field damage models differ in their characteristic functions. In the standard phase-field model proposed by Bourdin et al., (2000, 2008) and later modified by Miehe, Hofacker, et al., (2010), the quadratic degradation functions $g(\phi) = (1 - \phi)^2$ and geometric function $\alpha(\phi) = \phi^2$ are utilized. This approach, referred to as the AT2 model, has been widely applied but exhibits certain limitations. Notably, the AT2 model lacks an elastic stage, meaning damage initiates even under low applied loads, resulting in a nonlinear global response from the onset.

To address this, Pham et al., (2011) proposed the AT1 model, which uses the linear geometric function $\alpha(\phi) = \phi$. The AT1 model introduces an elastic response before peak load, but, like AT2, it is limited to brittle fracture due to the dependency of the degradation function solely on the crack phase-field. Both AT1 and AT2 are also sensitive to the length scale parameter l , as noted by Mandal et al., (2019).

Wu, (2017) and Wu & Nguyen, (2018) proposed a unified phase-field damage model capable of handling both brittle and quasi-brittle failure. This model employs a generic rational energetic degradation function $g(\phi)$ and a parametrized polynomial geometric function $\alpha(\phi)$. The AT1 and AT2 models are encompassed as specific cases of this unified framework. Moreover, the model determines optimal functions for cohesive fracture based on strain localization analysis. Using calibrated parameters from standard material properties (e.g., Young's modulus E , failure strength f_t , and fracture energy G_c), the framework can accurately reproduce common traction-separation laws (TSLs) found in cohesive zone models (CZM), such as the linear and exponential laws proposed by Barenblatt, (1962). Consequently, this model is referred to as the phase-field regularized cohesive zone model (PF-CZM).

The PF-CZM offers several advantages, including:

- **Independence of the global response from mesh size and alignment:** Unlike conventional models, PF-CZM exhibits reduced mesh dependency, ensuring numerical stability across different mesh discretizations.
- **Reduced sensitivity to the length scale parameter l :** As discussed before traditional phase-field models require careful tuning of l to balance numerical accuracy and physical realism. The PF-CZM framework mitigates this sensitivity, providing more robust predictions across various materials and loading conditions.
- **Elimination of crack surface tracking:** The phase-field approach inherently models cracks as diffuse interfaces, eliminating the need for explicit crack tracking or remeshing techniques (as required in XFEM and cohesive zone models). This greatly simplifies implementation in standard finite element frameworks.
- **No additional penalty stiffness required to handle crack face penetration:** Unlike classical cohesive zone models (CZM), which often

require an artificial penalty stiffness to prevent crack face interpenetration, PF-CZM inherently avoids this issue due to its continuous phase-field representation of cracks. This eliminates numerical artifacts and ensures a more physically consistent fracture process.

Mathematical Formulation of PF-CZM

The characteristic functions for PF-CZM, as proposed by Wu, (2017) and Wu & Nguyen, (2018), are given as:

$$\begin{cases} \alpha(\phi) = \xi\phi + (1 - \xi)\phi^2 & \xi \in [0, 2] \\ g(\phi) = \frac{(1 - \phi)^p}{(1 - \phi)^p + Q(\phi)} & Q(\phi) = a_1\phi(1 + a_2\phi + a_2a_3\phi^2) \end{cases} \quad (5.12)$$

These functions can be generalized to recover AT1 and AT2 models as specific cases by selecting appropriate values of ξ , p , and the parameters a_1 , a_2 and a_3 . As shown in Table 5.1 the geometric crack functions ($\alpha(\phi)$) for both AT1 and AT2 can be recovered by using ξ parameter of PF-CZM. Similarly, the quadratic degradation function ($g(\phi)$) which happens to be the degradation function of both AT1 and AT2 can be recovered with $p = 2$, $a_1 = 2$, $a_2 = -\frac{1}{2}$ and $a_3 = 0$. Table 5.3 provides a detailed comparison of the AT1, AT2, and PF-CZM models, including their characteristic functions, length scales, and material parameters.

Wu, (2017) and Wu & Nguyen, (2018) suggested using the geometric crack function given in Equation (5.12a) with $\xi = 2$ and the energetic degradation function described in Equation (5.12b) with $p \geq 2$, as follows:

$$\begin{cases} \alpha(\phi) = 2\phi - 2\phi^2 \Rightarrow c_0 = \pi \\ g(\phi) = \frac{(1 - \phi)^p}{(1 - \phi)^p + Q(\phi)}, p \geq 2 \end{cases} \quad (5.13)$$

The parameters $a_1 > 0$, a_2 and a_3 are defined as follows:

$$a_1 = \frac{4}{\pi} \left(\frac{l_{ch}}{l} \right), a_2 = 2 \left(-\frac{2k_0 G_c}{f_t^2} \right)^{\frac{2}{3}} - \left(p + \frac{1}{2} \right),$$

$$a_3 = \begin{cases} 0 & p > 2 \\ \frac{1}{a_2} \left(\frac{1}{8} \left(\frac{w_c f_t}{G_c} \right)^2 - (1 + a_2) \right) & p = 2 \end{cases} \quad (5.14)$$

These parameters depend on the failure strength $f_t > 0$, the initial modulus (slope of the target traction-separation law, TSL) $k_0 < 0$, and ultimate crack opening $w_c > 0$ of a target softening curve $\sigma(w)$ to be approximated. Once the length scale l is given or calibrated, the parameters a_1 , a_2 and a_3 can thus be determined from the standard material properties (i.e., Young's modulus E_0 , failure strength f_t , fracture energy G_c) and the target softening curve.

Examples of Calibrated Parameters for Specific Softening Laws

For particular softening laws (illustrated in Figure 2.11, section 0) the optimal parameters are calibrated as follows:

- Linear softening curve: $p = 2, a_2 = -\frac{1}{2}, a_3 = 0$

$$\sigma(w) = f_t \max \left(1 - \frac{f_t}{2G_c} w, 0 \right), \quad k_0 = -\frac{f_t^2}{2G_c}, \quad w_c = \frac{2G_c}{f_t} \quad (5.15)$$

- Exponential softening curve: $p = 2.5, a_2 = 2^{5/3} - 3, a_3 = 0$

$$\sigma(w) = f_t \exp\left(-\frac{f_t}{G_c} w\right), \quad k_0 = -\frac{f_t^2}{G_c}, \quad w_c = +\infty \quad (5.16)$$

Table 5.3. Common phase-field models for brittle and cohesive fracture considered in this study. Irwin's internal length is defined as $l_{ch} = \frac{E_0 G_c}{f_t^2}$, with E_0 being Young's modulus of the material; f_t and G_c being the failure strength and fracture energy (toughness), respectively. Adapted from Mandal et al., (2019)

Model	$\alpha(\phi)$	$g(\phi)$	Length-scale	Parameters
AT2	ϕ^2	$(1 - \phi)^2$	$l = \frac{27}{256} l_{ch}$	E_0, ν_0, G_c, l
AT1	ϕ	$(1 - \phi)^2$	$l = \frac{3}{8} l_{ch}$	E_0, ν_0, G_c, l
PF - CZM	$2\phi - \phi^2$	$\frac{(1 - \phi)^p}{(1 - \phi)^p + Q(\phi)}$	Numerical param.	E_0, ν_0, G_c, f_t and a TSL

5.2 GOVERNING EQUATIONS OF THE COUPLED PROBLEM

5.2.1 Governing equations and damage evolution law

Taking into account the constitutive relations described above and considering the first variation of work density function with respect to the primal kinematic variables ϕ and u , we can write

$$\delta\pi(u, \phi) = \delta\Psi_s(u, \phi) + \delta\Psi_c(\phi, \nabla\phi) \quad (5.17)$$

where δ denotes the variation.

In the variational formulation of phase-field models, fracture evolution is governed by the stability condition (Marigo et al., 2016)

$$\delta\pi(u, \phi) \geq 0, \forall \delta\phi \geq 0 \quad (5.18)$$

This ensures that the phase-field variable evolves under admissible energy minimization conditions.

Then, the variation of the stored energy density is given as

$$\begin{aligned} \delta\Psi_s(u, \phi) &= \int_{\Omega} \left(\frac{\partial\Psi_s}{\partial\epsilon} : \delta\epsilon + \frac{\partial\Psi_s}{\partial\phi} : \delta\phi \right) dV \\ &= \int_{\Omega} (\sigma : \delta\epsilon - Y\delta\phi) dV = \int_{\Omega} (\sigma : \delta\epsilon + g'(\phi)\bar{Y}) dV \end{aligned} \quad (5.19)$$

The conjugate energy release rate associated with the crack phase field can be obtained as

$$Y = -\frac{\partial\Psi_s(u, \phi)}{\partial\phi} = -g'(\phi)\bar{Y} \quad (5.20)$$

\bar{Y} is the effective crack driving force, and represents the initial (undamaged) elastic strain energy, which can be written as

$$\bar{Y} = \Psi_0(\epsilon) \quad (5.21)$$

So, the variation of the stored energy density can be finally written as

$$\delta\Psi_s(u, \phi) = \int_{\Omega} (\sigma : \delta\epsilon + g'(\phi)\bar{Y}) dV \quad (5.22)$$

The variation of energy dissipation $\delta\Psi_c$ can be obtained as

$$\delta\Psi_c(\phi, \nabla\phi) = \int_{\Omega} G_c \delta\gamma(\phi, \nabla\phi) dV \quad (5.23)$$

where the variation of the crack density function is obtained as

$$\gamma(\phi, \nabla\phi) = \frac{1}{c_0} \left[\frac{1}{l} \alpha'(\phi) \delta\phi + 2l \nabla\phi \cdot \nabla\delta\phi \right] \quad (5.24)$$

The variation of the work density function can be then written as

$$\delta\pi(u, \phi) = \int_{\Omega} (\sigma : \delta\epsilon + g'(\phi) \bar{Y}) dV + \int_{\Omega} G_c \delta_{\phi}\gamma(\phi, \nabla\phi) dV \quad (5.25)$$

Applying Gauss's divergence theorem and the statement that above equations must hold for any kinematically admissible variations of virtual quantities. The coupled field equations are therefore given as follows

$$\nabla \cdot \sigma + b = 0 \text{ in } \Omega$$

$$g'(\phi) \bar{Y} + G_c \delta_{\phi}\gamma \geq 0 \text{ for } \dot{\phi} \geq 0 \text{ in } \Omega \quad (5.26)$$

It should be noted that Eq.(5.26) represents the damage evolution law. The variation of the crack surface density function $\delta_{\phi}\gamma$ is obtained as

$$\delta_{\phi}\gamma = \partial_{\phi}\gamma - \nabla \cdot \partial_{\nabla\phi}\gamma = \frac{1}{c_0} \left[\frac{1}{l} \alpha'(\phi) - 2l \Delta\phi \right] \quad (5.27)$$

Equation(5.26 (a)) is the macroscopic equilibrium condition while Equation(5.26 (b)) determines the evolution of the phase field, where $\Delta\phi$ denoting the Laplacian $\Delta\phi = \nabla \cdot \nabla\phi$. These field equations are supplemented by the following Neumann boundary conditions

$$\sigma \cdot n = h \text{ on } \partial\Omega_h \text{ and } \nabla\phi \cdot n = 0 \text{ on } \partial\Omega \quad (5.28)$$

Where n denotes the outward unit vector normal to the surface $\partial\Omega$.

The phase-field evolution Equation(5.26 (b)) can be rewritten as the following Karush-Kuhn-Tucker conditions (J.-Y. Wu, 2017; J.-Y. Wu, Nguyen, et al., 2020)

$$\dot{\phi} \geq 0, \quad f(Y, \phi) \leq 0, \quad \dot{\phi} f(Y, \phi) = 0 \quad (5.29)$$

Where the damage criterion $f(Y, \phi) \leq 0$ is defined as

$$g'(\phi)\bar{Y} + G_c \delta_\phi \gamma \leq 0 \quad (5.30)$$

5.3 CRITICAL NUMERICAL IMPLEMENTATION ASPECTS OF PHASE FIELD DAMAGE MODELS

5.3.1 Fracture driving force ψ_0^+ and irreversibility.

To prevent cracking under compressive strain states, the driving force for fracture can be decomposed into active ψ_0^+ and inactive ψ_0^- parts. Accordingly, the elastic strain energy density can be defined as (Miehe, Welschinger, et al., 2010)

$$\psi_0(\epsilon) = \psi_0^+(\epsilon) + \psi_0^-(\epsilon) \quad (5.31)$$

Such that

$$\psi(\epsilon, \phi) = g(\phi)\psi_0^+(\epsilon) + \psi_0^-(\epsilon) \quad (5.32)$$

Where the energetic degradation function $g(\phi)$ is only applied to the tension part ψ_0^+ of the initial strain energy.

The stress tensor can be defined as

$$\sigma(u, \phi) = \frac{\partial \psi_0}{\partial \epsilon} = g(\phi) \frac{\partial \psi_0^+(\epsilon)}{\partial \epsilon} + \frac{\partial \psi_0^-(\epsilon)}{\partial \epsilon} \quad (5.33)$$

The variationally consistent approach, as proposed in the original AT2 model, is often referred to as the isotropic formulation:

$$\psi_0^+(\epsilon) = \frac{1}{2} \epsilon : \mathbf{C}_0 : \epsilon = \frac{1}{2} \lambda \text{tr}^2(\epsilon) + \mu \text{tr}(\epsilon^2), \psi_0^-(\epsilon) = 0 \quad (5.34)$$

where \mathbf{C}_0 is the undamaged elastic stiffness tensor and λ and μ are the Lamé parameters. In the context of the AT1 and AT2 models, damage under compression is prevented by decomposing the strain energy density following typically two approaches. One is the so-called volumetric-deviatoric split, proposed by (Amor et al., 2009), which reads

$$\psi_0^+(\epsilon) = \frac{1}{2} K \langle \text{tr}(\epsilon) \rangle_+^2 + \mu (\epsilon' : \epsilon'), \psi_0^-(\epsilon) = \frac{1}{2} K \langle \text{tr}(\epsilon) \rangle_-^2 \quad (5.35)$$

Here, K is the bulk modulus, $\langle a \rangle_{\pm} = \frac{a \pm |a|}{2}$, and $\epsilon' = \epsilon - \text{tr}(\epsilon) \mathbf{I}/3$. The second one is the so-called spectral decomposition, proposed by (Miehe, Welschinger, et al., 2010), which builds upon the spectral decomposition of the strain tensor $\epsilon^{\pm} = \sum_{a=1}^3 \langle \epsilon_I \rangle_{\pm} \mathbf{n}_I \otimes \mathbf{n}_I$, with ϵ_I and \mathbf{n}_I being, respectively, the principal strains and principal strain directions (with $I = 1, 2, 3$). The strain energy decomposition then reads

$$\Psi_0^\pm(\epsilon) = \frac{1}{2} \lambda (\text{tr}(\epsilon))_\pm^2 + \mu \text{tr}[(\epsilon^\pm)^2] \quad (5.36)$$

The constitutive matrix can be computed from stress tensor such as $C = \partial\sigma/\partial\epsilon$, the details of derivation of stiffness tensor for each decomposition can be seen in APPENDIX.A.

Considering the damage to be an irreversible process (i.e. $\dot{\phi} \geq 0$), a history field variable H is introduced ensuring that the following condition is always met

$$\phi_{t+\Delta t} \geq \phi_t \quad (5.37)$$

Where $\phi_{t+\Delta t}$ represents the phase field variable in the current time increment, while ϕ_t is the phase field variable in the previous increment. This history variable must satisfy the Kuhn-Tucker conditions

Consequently, the history field for a current time step t , over a total time T , can be written as follows

$$H = \max\left(\bar{Y}_0, \max_{n \in [0, T]} \bar{Y}_n\right), \quad \bar{Y}_0 = \frac{f_t^2}{2E_0} \quad (5.38)$$

6. PFM 2D SIMULATIONS OF FRACTURE IN HOST-INCLUSION SYSTEMS

6.1 FINITE ELEMENT DISCRETIZATION

To derive the discrete form of the governing equations, we first express the weak form of the coupled phase-field problem. The weak form corresponding to the governing equations is given by:

$$\int_{\Omega} (\boldsymbol{\sigma} : \boldsymbol{\delta\epsilon} - \mathbf{b} \cdot \boldsymbol{\delta\mathbf{u}}) dV + \int_{\partial\Omega_h} (\mathbf{h} \cdot \boldsymbol{\delta\mathbf{u}}) dA = 0$$

$$\int_{\Omega} [g'(\phi)\bar{Y}\delta\phi + G_c\delta\gamma] dV = 0 \quad (6.1)$$

where

$$\delta\gamma = \frac{1}{c_0} \left[\frac{1}{l} \alpha'(\phi) \delta\phi + 2l \nabla\phi \cdot \nabla\delta\phi \right]$$

Using Voigt-notation in a 2D space, the displacement field \mathbf{u}_h and the phase field ϕ_h can be discretized as

$$\mathbf{u}_h = \sum_{i=1}^m N_i^u \hat{\mathbf{u}}_i \quad \text{and} \quad \phi_h = \sum_{i=1}^m N_i^\phi \hat{\phi}_i \quad (6.2)$$

Where the shape function matrix is expressed as

$$N_i^u = \begin{bmatrix} N_i & 0 \\ 0 & N_i \end{bmatrix}, \quad N_i^\phi = N_i \quad (6.3)$$

Here, N_i denotes the shape function associated with node i , m is the total number of nodes per element, and $\widehat{\mathbf{u}}_i = \{u_x, u_y\}^T$ and $\widehat{\phi}_i$ are the displacement and phase field values at node i , respectively. Consequently, the corresponding derivatives can be discretised as

$$\boldsymbol{\epsilon} = \sum_{i=1}^m \mathbf{B}_i^u \widehat{\mathbf{u}}_i \quad \text{and} \quad \nabla \phi = \sum_{i=1}^m \mathbf{B}_i^\phi \widehat{\phi}_i \quad (6.4)$$

where the strain-displacement matrices associated with a given node i are expressed as

$$\mathbf{B}_i^u = \begin{bmatrix} \partial N_i / \partial x & 0 \\ 0 & \partial N_i / \partial y \\ \partial N_i / \partial y & \partial N_i / \partial x \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{B}_i^\phi = \begin{bmatrix} \partial N_i / \partial x \\ \partial N_i / \partial y \end{bmatrix} \quad (6.5)$$

Considering this finite element discretisation and the fact that Equation (6.1) must hold for arbitrary values of $\delta \mathbf{u}$ and $\delta \phi$, the discrete equation corresponding to the equilibrium condition can be expressed as the following residual with respect to the displacement field

$$\mathbf{r}_i^u = \int_{\Omega} (\mathbf{B}_i^u)^T \boldsymbol{\sigma} dV - \int_{\Omega} (\mathbf{N}_i^u)^T \mathbf{b} dV - \int_{\partial \Omega_h} (\mathbf{N}_i^u)^T \mathbf{h} dA \quad (6.6)$$

Similarly, the residual with respect to the evolution of the crack phase field can be expressed as

$$r_i^\phi = - \int_{\Omega} \left[N_i^T \left(g'(\phi) \bar{Y} + \frac{\alpha' G_c}{c_0 l_0} \right) + \frac{2l_0}{c_0} G_c B_i^T \nabla \phi \right] dV \quad (6.7)$$

The Newton-Raphson method is employed to obtain the solutions for which $r_u = \mathbf{0}$ and $r_\phi = \mathbf{0}$, given the nonlinearity of the residuals. An iterative scheme is adopted to solve for the displacement \mathbf{u} and the phase ϕ . The tangent stiffness matrices can be readily computed by taking the first derivative of the residual vectors, and read

$$K_{ij}^{uu} = \frac{\partial r_i^u}{\partial u_j} = \int_{\Omega} (B_i^u)^T \left(\frac{\partial \sigma}{\partial \epsilon} \right) B_j^u dV \quad (6.8)$$

$$K_{ij}^{\phi\phi} = \frac{\partial r_i^\phi}{\partial \phi_j} = \int_{\Omega} \left[N_i^T \left(g'(\phi) \bar{Y} + \frac{\alpha' G_c}{c_0 l_0} \right) N_j + \frac{2l_0}{c_0} G_c B_i^T B_j \right] dV \quad (6.9)$$

Standard Gauss quadrature rules are used to evaluate the above integrals. The details of computation of material jacobian $\left(\frac{\partial \sigma}{\partial \epsilon} \right)$ are shown in APPENDIX.A.

The above system of nonlinear equations is generally solved using an incremental time-stepping procedure. Over the time interval $[0, T]$, all state variables are evaluated at discrete time steps t_n for $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N$. At each time step t_n , the solution is computed iteratively within a typical time increment $\Delta t = t_{n+1} - t_n$. The nonlinear system of equations is then iteratively solved, ensuring that all state variables are updated at the instant t_n . Various numerical algorithms can be employed to solve this system, and different implementation strategies are discussed in the following sections.

6.2 PFM MODELLING IN ABAQUS: UEL IMPLEMENTATION

In this research, a Phase Field Model (PFM) for fracture was implemented in Abaqus using the User Element (UEL) subroutine. This implementation enabled customized calculations of stiffness matrices and nodal forces, facilitating detailed fracture simulations tailored to diamond-hosted inclusion systems. The process involved addressing certain intrinsic

limitations of Abaqus while leveraging creative solutions to ensure accurate modeling and visualization.

A key aspect of the UEL subroutine is the storage of solution-dependent variables (SVARS) at integration points. However, an inherent limitation of UEL-based implementations is the inability to visualize these integration point variables in Abaqus/Viewer. This constraint arises because Abaqus only retrieves the stiffness matrix and the right-hand-side nodal force vector from the UEL subroutine; variables such as stresses, strains, and shape functions are not directly accessible as output.

To overcome this limitation, an auxiliary dummy mesh was introduced. This mesh consists of standard Abaqus elements, such as CPE4 elements in 2D and C3D8 elements in 3D, which mimic the UEL-defined elements in terms of node count and integration points. The material response at each integration point within this auxiliary mesh is defined using a User Material (UMAT) subroutine. This approach enables the definition of constitutive matrices and stresses based on strain values, even though these auxiliary elements do not influence the global solution.

In the auxiliary mesh:

1. Stress components and constitutive matrices are set to zero to ensure no impact on the global solution.
2. Data from the UEL subroutine, such as state variables, is stored in a Fortran module. This data is then transferred to the UMAT subroutine.
3. Within the UMAT, information is stored in the built-in array STATEV for each corresponding element and integration point. By requesting solution-dependent variables (SDVs) as field output, the results become accessible for visualization in Abaqus/Viewer.

This innovative combination of UEL and UMAT (Figure 6.1) subroutines addresses the visualization challenge effectively. The setup not only ensures accurate implementation of the PFM for fracture simulations but also allows seamless visualization of the results, making it a robust tool for investigating the fracture behavior in diamond-hosted inclusion systems (Martínez-Pañeda et al., 2018; J.-Y. Wu et al., 2019).

Figure 6.1. User subroutine flowchart for the implementation of a coupled deformation - phase field fracture model inspired by Navidtehrani et al., (2021).

6.2.1 AM/Staggered algorithm

Two primary approaches are employed to solve the coupled phase-field and displacement system: the staggered scheme and the monolithic scheme. The staggered approach, initially proposed by Miehe et al.,(2010), is widely used for phase-field modeling due to its robustness in handling snap-back instabilities. In this method, the displacement field and the phase field are solved sequentially, minimizing the internal potential energy at each step through a Newton-Raphson iteration. This approach, popularized further by Bourdin et al., (2000), is robust but conditionally stable, requiring small time increments to converge reliably. For each iteration of a specific time increment the displacement and phase field subproblem solved simultaneously. The solution procedure is repeated until the final solution converges. Among many feasible convergence criteria, e.g., the one pass criterion (Miehe, Hofacker, et al., 2010), the damage-based criterion (Amor et al., 2009; Bourdin et al., 2000, 2008), the energy based criterion (Ambati et al., 2015), the residual-based criterion (Seleš et al., 2019; Wick, 2017; P. Zhang et al., 2018), etc., the last one is adopted since it is intrinsically incorporated in Abaqus. The details of the implementation and the convergence criterion is shown in Figure 6.2 and Section 6.2.3 respectively.

6.2.2 Quasi-Newton (BFGS) monolithic algorithm

In contrast, the monolithic approach solves the displacement and phase fields simultaneously, offering unconditional stability and the advantage of using larger time increments (Kristensen & Martínez-Pañeda, 2020; J.-Y. Wu, Huang, et al., 2020; J.-Y. Wu

& Huang, 2020). Despite its efficiency, the monolithic method often struggles with convergence issues, particularly in highly nonlinear problems. To address this, advanced quasi-Newton methods such as the Broyden-Fletcher-Goldfarb-Shanno (BFGS) algorithm have been successfully implemented, significantly improving the convergence behavior of monolithic solvers.

The following linearized system, with initial stiffness matrix K , is solved in an iteratively:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} u \\ \phi \end{Bmatrix}_{n+1} = \begin{Bmatrix} u \\ \phi \end{Bmatrix}_n - \begin{bmatrix} K^{uu} & 0 \\ 0 & K^{\phi\phi} \end{bmatrix}_n^{-1} \begin{Bmatrix} r^u \\ r^\phi \end{Bmatrix}_n \quad (6.10)$$

In quasi-Newton methods, unlike standard Newton methods, the stiffness matrix K is not updated at every iteration. Instead, if convergence is not achieved after a predefined number of iterations, an approximate stiffness matrix \tilde{K} is introduced. This approximated matrix \tilde{K} satisfies the following:

$$\tilde{K}\Delta z = \Delta r \quad (6.11)$$

where

$$z = \begin{Bmatrix} u \\ \phi \end{Bmatrix}$$

$\Delta z = z_{n+1} - z_n$. Likewise, $\Delta r = r_{n+1} - r_n$. In the BFGS algorithm, the approximated stiffness matrix is updated in the following way:

$$\tilde{K}_{n+1} = \tilde{K}_n - \frac{(\tilde{K}_n \Delta z)(\tilde{K}_n \Delta z)^T}{\Delta z^T \tilde{K}_n \Delta z} + \frac{\Delta r \Delta r^T}{\Delta z^T \Delta r} \quad (6.12)$$

Although the non-diagonal coupling terms of the initial stiffness matrix have been omitted (6.10), the approximation in Equation (6.12) still couples the displacement and phase fields. Furthermore, if the stiffness matrix is symmetric, the update to the approximate stiffness matrix can alternatively be expressed in terms of its inverse (Kristensen & Martínez-Pañeda, 2020; Matthies & Strang, 1979; J.-Y. Wu & Huang, 2020).

$$\widetilde{K}_{n+1}^{-1} = \left(I - \frac{\Delta z \Delta r^T}{\Delta z^T \Delta r} \right) \widetilde{K}_n^{-1} \left(I - \frac{\Delta z \Delta r^T}{\Delta z^T \Delta r} \right)^{-1} + \frac{\Delta z \Delta z^T}{\Delta z^T \Delta r} \quad (6.13)$$

This approach provides significant computational savings while preserving symmetry and positive definiteness, if originally present. The BFGS algorithm is widely implemented in commercial finite element software (such as Abaqus), often paired with a line search algorithm.

6.2.3 Convergence criteria and implementation in Abaqus

The default convergence criteria provided by Abaqus are employed for both the monolithic and staggered solution schemes without modification. In the simulations, the default convergence criterion of Abaqus is adopted

$$r_{max} \leq R_n q_z \text{ and } c_{max} \leq c_n a_{max} \quad (6.14)$$

where r_{max}^α represents the largest residual in the balance equations for the displacement field ($z = u$) or the damage field ($z = d$) and q_z is an overall time-averaged flux achieved during the current loading step. The largest correction to the field variable (c_{max}) is compared to the largest incremental change in the corresponding solution variable (a_{max}). The default tolerances $R_n = 0.005$ and $C_n = 0.01$ are used.

As strong nonlinearities are typically involved in crack propagation problems, the number of iterations required for convergence can become excessive. Abaqus employs stringent default controls on iterations, which often reduce the incremental step size to maintain stability. To address this issue, fixed incremental steps can be implemented by specifying relevant control parameters, as detailed in the Abaqus keyword manual (e.g., *Controls, parameters = time incrementation).

In certain scenarios, such as critical increments, the Newton-based monolithic algorithm and the Alternating Minimization (AM) staggered algorithm may require more than 1000

iterations to converge. This highlights the computational challenges posed by strong nonlinearities and underscores the need for efficient solution strategies.

For all simulations presented in this study, unless explicitly stated otherwise, the 4-node quadrilateral bilinear element (Q4) is employed for mesh discretization for all the 2D simulations. The damage subdomain is pre-identified and discretized with a finer mesh size ($h = l/5$), while coarser elements are used for the rest of the domain. The phase-field cohesive zone model (PF-CZM) employed is shown to be largely insensitive to both the length scale parameter (l) and mesh size/alignment, as corroborated by previous studies. In each simulation, a single set of parameters—length scale parameter $l = 1/3$ and mesh size $h=l/5$ is adopted. This ensures computational efficiency while preserving accuracy in capturing damage evolution.

While these criteria ensure robust convergence, strong nonlinearities often involved in crack propagation can lead to excessive iterations and frequent reductions in the incremental step size. To address these challenges, fixed incremental steps can be specified using control parameters as described in the Abaqus manual. However, critical increments in Newton-based monolithic algorithms or staggered algorithms often require over 1000 iterations to converge.

6.3 NUMERICAL RESULTS

6.3.1 Validation: Single Edge Notch (SEN) Test:

The Single Edge Notch (SEN) test is conducted to validate the implementation of the phase field model (PFM) using the User Element (UEL) subroutine in Abaqus. The test setup is illustrated in Figure 6.4, which shows a square plate with a length of 1 mm and unit out-of-plane thickness. A horizontal notch of 0.5 mm length is introduced at the mid-height of the left edge. The bottom edge of the plate is fixed, and a horizontal displacement is applied at the top edge whereas we restrain the vertical displacement at the top edge of the specimen.

. This setup simulates the initiation and propagation of cracks under shear loading conditions. The damage model employed is the AT2 model with volumetric-deviatoric decomposition.

The material parameters used for the SEN test are:

- **Young's modulus (E_0):** 2.1×10^5 MPa
- **Poisson's ratio (ν):** 0.3
- **Failure strength (f_t):** 2000 MPa
- **Fracture toughness (G_c):** 2.7 N/mm

(a) Validation Against Established Results

In the first step of the validation, the staggered solution scheme implemented in the UEL subroutine was compared against an established solution by Marengo et al., (2021). The comparison is depicted in Figure 6.5, which plots the force-displacement curves. The close agreement between the two curves demonstrates the accuracy of the UEL implementation for simulating brittle fracture using the AT2 phase field damage model.

(b) Efficiency of the Monolithic BFGS Algorithm

While the staggered algorithm is robust and commonly used, it requires smaller time increments to ensure stability and convergence. In contrast, the monolithic Broyden-Fletcher-Goldfarb-Shanno (BFGS) algorithm solves the coupled displacement and phase field equations simultaneously, enabling larger time increments and improved computational efficiency.

To evaluate the efficiency of the monolithic BFGS algorithm, simulations were performed using time steps of 0.002s, 0.005s, and 0.008s. Figure 6.6 shows the force-displacement curves obtained using the monolithic BFGS algorithm compared to the staggered scheme

and benchmark results. The monolithic BFGS algorithm achieved comparable accuracy while significantly reducing computational cost.

The computational performance of the staggered and monolithic algorithms is summarized in Table 6.1. The staggered scheme with a time step of 0.001 s required 20 hours to complete the simulation. In contrast, the monolithic BFGS algorithm with a time step of 0.008 s completed the simulation in just 2.29 hours, representing a ninefold reduction in execution time.

Table 6.1. Execution time for staggered and monolithic BFGS algorithms at different time steps. The monolithic BFGS algorithm with a time step of 0.008 s achieves a ninefold reduction in computation time compared to the staggered scheme.

Method	Execution time (hr)
0.001 s, staggered newton scheme	20
0.002 s, monolithic bfgs scheme	4.7
0.005 s, monolithic bfgs scheme	2.7
0.008 s, monolithic bfgs scheme	2.3

The SEN test served as an effective benchmark to validate the implementation of the phase field model for brittle fracture in Abaqus. The staggered algorithm demonstrated accuracy and robustness, closely matching the benchmark results. However, the monolithic BFGS algorithm significantly outperformed the staggered scheme in terms of computational efficiency, achieving comparable accuracy with much larger time increments. This highlights the potential of monolithic algorithms for solving complex fracture problems in a time-efficient manner.

6.3.2 Application to host-inclusion systems

(a) Initial 2D Simulations:

In this section, we tested the methods and approaches developed in the previous sections on our primary simulation problem: the host-inclusion system, at first considering a 2D problem. This step served as a precursor to extending the problem to 3D. By utilizing the Phase-Field Cohesive Zone Model (PF-CZM) for damage modeling, we leveraged its distinct advantages over traditional models like AT2, as outlined in section 5.1.2. PF-CZM is particularly well-suited for accurately capturing complex fracture behavior in brittle systems while addressing some of the shortcomings of conventional models such as mesh sensitivity and length scale parameter sensitivity (please refer Section 5.1 and APPENDIX.D for further information) .

The fracture and material properties used in this section are identical to those in the XFEM 2D simulations (Section 3.1.2), ensuring consistency across models and approaches. Likewise, the problem domain geometry, boundary conditions, and force application were kept consistent with the XFEM 2D setup to allow for a consistent comparison between the two approaches. The monolithic BFGS solver, validated earlier, was utilized due to its superior convergence properties and computational efficiency compared to the staggered scheme. This comprehensive setup allowed us to explore the advantages of PF-CZM in resolving fracture phenomena while building upon the insights gained from XFEM 2D simulations.

Figure 6.7. (a) Meshing of whole host and single inclusion system (b) Meshing of enrichment zone with the single inclusion The host-inclusion system features a fine mesh (2×10^{-3} m) around the inclusion to resolve the length scale parameter ($l = 2 \times 10^{-2}$ m). The domain dimensions, boundary conditions, and force application are identical to those used in the XFEM 2D simulations.

(a) Volumetric-Deviatoric Decomposition: Challenges and Insights

The first attempt involved using the volumetric-deviatoric decomposition proposed by Amor et al., (2009). We used the normalized positive strain energy density ($pp = \psi_e^+ / \psi_e$) and negative strain energy density ($pn = \psi_e^- / \psi_e$) such that $pp + pn = 1$ to visualize the contribution to fracture. As illustrated in Figure 6.8, the normalised positive strain energy density (pp) was not confined solely to the crack tip but was also present all around the inclusion. This behavior led to fracture growth in compression-dominated regions, as it is well known that the volumetric-deviatoric decomposition fails to fully prevent fracture propagation under compression, thereby destabilizing the solution and causing convergence issues (Hesammokri et al., 2023; J.-Y. Wu, Nguyen, et al., 2020).

The underlying cause of this issue lies in the decomposition framework, which assumes fractures propagate due to both bulk tensile deformation and shear deformation (both compressive-shear and tensile shear contributions). In the context of the host-inclusion system, we observed that compressive shear dominated around the inclusions, driving unwanted fracture propagation in these regions.

(b) Switch to Miehe's Spectral Decomposition

To address these challenges, we adopted Miehe et al.'s spectral decomposition (Miehe, Welschinger, et al., 2010), which effectively suppress the creation of cracks under compression. This method ensures that only tensile cracks propagate by suppressing compressive effects entirely. The results, depicted in Figure 6.9, demonstrate a marked improvement in fracture behavior:

- The positive strain energy density (pp) is now localized exclusively at the crack tip, while the inclusion's surrounding regions show almost negligible positive energy.
- This change eliminated crack propagation under compression and significantly improved convergence stability.

The differences between these two decomposition methods are further visualized in Figure 6.10. In the top image, volumetric-deviatoric decomposition leads to fractures propagating all around the inclusion, driven by the dominance of positive strain energy in those regions. In contrast, the bottom image shows spectral decomposition successfully localizing fractures to the crack tip, aligning with the expected tensile fracture behavior.

Figure 6.8. Simulation results showing the volumetric-deviatoric decomposition applied to a 2D host-inclusion system just before damage initiation ($0 < \phi < 1$). Top: normalised positive strain energy density (ψ_e^+/ψ_e) dominates not only at the crack tip but also around the inclusion. Bottom: normalised negative strain energy density (ψ_e^-/ψ_e) with widespread compressive stresses failing to suppress tensile cracks.

(b) Fracture propagation in systems with multiple inclusions:

Following the validation of the Phase-Field Model (PFM) for single inclusion systems, and finding the best decomposition models, we extended our simulations to systems containing multiple inclusions to evaluate fracture coalescence and interaction. The setup involved two inclusions with a spacing of 20 mm, consistent with the configurations used in the XFEM 2D simulations. This extension allowed us to compare the XFEM 2D results with the newly implemented PFM 2D framework, particularly focusing on fracture propagation patterns and crack lengths.

The results for the multiple-inclusion system demonstrated the interaction of cracks propagating from each inclusion. As shown in Figure 6.11, the cracks initiated at the tips of each inclusion and propagated towards each other. The coalescence of fractures is observed when the cracks converged, forming a continuous crack path between the inclusions. This behavior aligns with the expectations for brittle materials under tension, where crack interaction plays a significant role in fracture mechanics. The coalescence

mechanism demonstrates the robustness of the PFM in capturing complex crack propagation and interaction phenomena, which are essential for modeling real-world systems.

To further validate the PFM approach, we compared the results for crack length and fracture patterns between XFEM 2D (conducted in earlier sections) and PFM 2D simulations. The comparison, illustrated in Figure 6.12, highlights the similarity in crack lengths between the two approaches, confirming the consistency of the PFM implementation. Both methods produced comparable results, demonstrating that PFM is a reliable alternative for modeling fracture propagation in systems with multiple inclusions. Moreover, the PFM showed improved numerical stability and convergence, addressing some of the limitations encountered with XFEM, such as complex crack propagation and remeshing requirements.

6.4 CONCLUSION

This chapter presented a comprehensive investigation of the Phase-Field Method (PFM) in 2D, systematically addressing challenges in fracture modeling while laying the groundwork for extending the methodology to 3D. By building on insights from earlier sections, significant advancements were achieved in accurately modeling host-inclusion systems and identifying optimal configurations for robust and reliable fracture simulations. The study validated the PFM framework through rigorous testing, demonstrating its effectiveness and numerical stability.

The single-edge notch (SEN) test served as a benchmark to validate the PFM implementation using the monolithic BFGS solver. The results exhibited excellent agreement with published data, confirming both the accuracy of the custom user-element subroutine and the computational efficiency of the BFGS algorithm compared to the staggered approach. This validation reinforced confidence in the PFM framework, ensuring its applicability to complex fracture scenarios. Among the damage models tested, the Phase-Field Cohesive Zone Model (PF-CZM) emerged as the most suitable for brittle fracture simulations. Unlike traditional models such as AT2, PF-CZM demonstrated superior performance in handling complex crack interactions, effectively addressing mesh sensitivity and length-scale parameter dependency issues.

In exploring fracture propagation dynamics, a comparative analysis of volumetric-deviatoric and spectral decomposition techniques revealed critical insights. While volumetric-deviatoric decomposition led to destabilization through creation of cracks under compression, the implementation of spectral decomposition effectively suppressed these effects. This adjustment enabled stable fracture propagation driven solely by tensile forces, significantly enhancing the robustness of the PFM framework for host-inclusion systems. Additionally, extending simulations to multiple inclusions demonstrated the capability of the PFM to capture fracture coalescence and crack interactions, further validating its reliability. The results showed strong consistency with previous XFEM 2D studies, underscoring the versatility and accuracy of the PFM approach in handling complex multi-inclusion scenarios.

These advancements in PFM 2D form the foundation for extending the methodology to 3D simulations. The validated monolithic BFGS solver will be instrumental in ensuring computational feasibility in 3D models, while the PF-CZM damage model, with its ability to capture brittle fracture behaviors, is well-suited for addressing the complexities of fracture mechanics in three-dimensional host-inclusion systems. Furthermore, the

adoption of spectral decomposition will remain essential in suppressing compressive effects and ensuring numerical stability during 3D fracture simulations.

By systematically testing and optimizing the PFM framework in 2D, this chapter serves as a critical bridge to the more advanced 3D simulations. The robust methodologies established here provide a solid foundation for tackling the challenges of modeling fractures in diamond-hosted inclusions in 3D, advancing the understanding of stress relaxation mechanisms and improving geobarometric models. These findings mark an important step forward in developing accurate and reliable tools for studying the mechanical behavior of host-inclusion systems.

7. EXTENSION TO PFM 3D

7.1 MODELING ELLIPSOIDAL INCLUSIONS: A COMPARATIVE STUDY WITH XFEM ON COHESIVE FRACTURES

7.1.1 Introduction

In Part 1, we explored the behavior of ellipsoidal inclusions under brittle fracture conditions using the Extended Finite Element Method (XFEM). While XFEM successfully captured crack initiation and propagation, these simulations were performed under high fracture strength assumptions for diamond. However, natural diamond inclusions often exhibit quasi-brittle behavior, where fractures develop cohesively under lower fracture strength conditions.

To address this, we employ the Phase-Field Model (PFM) to investigate cohesive fractures in ellipsoidal inclusions. This study extends the PFM framework to 3D, allowing us to

analyze how reducing fracture strength impacts residual pressure relaxation and fracture behavior. Additionally, a comparative analysis with XFEM 3D is conducted to assess the capabilities of each method in capturing cohesive fracture mechanisms.

This chapter aims to:

- Investigate the effects of lower fracture strength on residual pressure relaxation and crack evolution.
- Compare PFM 3D results with XFEM 3D simulations to evaluate their consistency and respective advantages.
- Determine whether cohesive fracture mechanisms explain discrepancies observed in residual pressure relaxation.

By focusing on cohesive fractures in ellipsoidal inclusions, this chapter provides a direct link between XFEM and PFM, establishing a critical comparison between two advanced computational frameworks. The insights gained here will form the basis for further exploration of edge singularities in subsequent chapters.

7.1.2 Methods and computational framework details

The ellipsoidal inclusions were assigned a prestress of 1 GPa, representing the overpressure due to the elastic deformation of the diamond host during exhumation. The inclusion geometry was maintained with an aspect ratio of 10:1:1, consistent with previous analyses in section 4. The numerical framework utilized the same hybrid meshing strategy as described earlier, with C3D8I elements used in critical regions for enhanced accuracy and C3D10 elements employed in less critical regions for computational efficiency.

PFM simulations were carried out using the PF-CZM model, incorporating Miehe spectral decomposition (Miehe, Hofacker, et al., 2010) to filter out compressive contributions, H field irreversibility to prevent crack healing, and a BFGS solver for efficient convergence.

The residual pressure results from PFM were compared to those obtained from XFEM, which relies on cohesive zone modeling governed by traction-separation laws. This comparative approach highlights the differences and synergies between the two methods for modeling fracture initiation and propagation.

7.1.3 Results and Discussion

The residual inclusion pressure (P_{inc}) as a function of fracture toughness for PFM and XFEM is presented in Figure 7.1. Both models exhibit a similar trend, where residual pressure increases linearly with fracture toughness. The maximum difference between the two methods is approximately 0.5%, confirming XFEM's capability to model brittle fractures under isotropic conditions. However, PFM offers additional insights into cohesive fracture mechanisms, capturing finer details of pressure relaxation.

To further analyze the factors influencing residual pressure, we examine its dependence on inclusion volume. As shown in Figure 7.2, residual pressure decreases with increasing inclusion volume, stabilizing at a plateau. This trend suggests that larger inclusions facilitate more efficient stress redistribution. The total relaxation due to fracture for smaller inclusions is approximately 12%, highlighting the efficiency of quasi-brittle mechanisms in stress release. By comparison, purely brittle fracture relaxation accounts for only 6% (Puhan et al., 2024), underscoring the need to consider additional deformation mechanisms beyond brittle fracture to explain natural observations.

Figure 7.1. Average inclusion pressure plotted against fracture toughness for PFM and compared with XFEM for a shape with aspect ratio 10:1:1. The failure strength is set to 0.2 GPa. Here, average inclusion pressure and residual pressure (P_{inc}) are used interchangeably, both referring to the pressure remaining in the inclusion after fracture. The residual pressure is computed by averaging the pressure values across all inclusion elements in the simulation.

7.1.4 Discussion and implications

This study provided a comparative analysis of ellipsoidal inclusions using PFM and XFEM frameworks, focusing on residual pressure relaxation and fracture behavior. These two complete different numerical approaches show a close agreement in residual pressure predictions, with differences under 0.5%.

The findings confirm that reducing fracture strength leads to enhanced relaxation, but the impact still remains limited compared to the discrepancies observed in natural inclusions. This highlights the necessity of further refinements in geobarometry frameworks, particularly for modeling quasi-brittle fractures.

7.2 APPLICATION TO SINGLE CUBOIDAL INCLUSION

7.2.1 Introduction

In this section, we transition from ellipsoidal inclusions to cuboidal inclusions analyzed under the Phase-Field Model (PFM) framework. The limitations observed in the ellipsoidal geometry—particularly the discrepancies in critical fracture properties and residual pressure—highlight the need to explore alternative shapes that may better align with experimental findings.

The focus of this subchapter is on single cuboidal inclusions, which inherently feature sharp edges and corners. These geometric attributes are hypothesized to introduce localized stress concentrations, significantly influencing fracture initiation and propagation. Thus, by systematically varying the fillet radius of the edges, we investigate how these sharp edges affect:

- Critical fracture properties, including fracture strength and toughness.
- Residual pressures due to post-fracture relaxation.
- The effect of size on residual pressures

This study examines two specific cuboid configurations: one with four sharp edges and another with a single sharp edge, to investigate how stress concentration influences fracture propagation and pressure relaxation (Figure 7.3). Each configuration is analyzed under controlled conditions, with comparisons drawn to the ellipsoidal inclusion results to establish the impact of shape on fracture behavior. The insights gained here serve as a foundation for advancing to more complex multi-inclusion systems in later sections.

7.2.2 Methods

(a) Prestress Initialization

The initial prestress applied to the cuboidal inclusion is consistent with the XFEM 3D simulations and set to 1 GPa to account for the elastic deformation of the diamond host during exhumation. The details of the prestress calculation and its physical significance are elaborated in Section 4.3.1. This prestress provides a comparative baseline for understanding the effect of cuboidal geometries on stress localization and fracture behavior.

For the PFM 3D simulations, the prestress was applied using hydrostatic pressure conditions, assuming isotropic elasticity and a dry host-inclusion system.

(b) Geometric and meshing Setup

The cuboidal inclusion geometry introduces new considerations for stress localization and crack behavior. The meshing strategy ensures that the stress field is accurately captured while minimizing computational effort.

To reduce computational cost, symmetry conditions are applied:

- Cuboids with four edge singularities → 1/8th symmetry is modeled (Figure 7.3(a)).
- Cuboids with a single edge singularity → 1/4th symmetry is used, with one symmetry lost in the x-plane (Figure 7.3 (b)).

Since sharp edges naturally induce high stress concentrations, a fillet radius is introduced to regulate singularity intensity. This fillet radius smooths the transition at the edges, modifying stress localization and fracture evolution (Figure 7.4).

A targeted meshing strategy was implemented to ensure accurate stress resolution while maintaining computational efficiency:

- The inclusion and its surrounding area (offset by twice the smallest cuboid edge length) are meshed using C3D8I elements, which are well-suited for handling high-stress gradients.
- The broader host domain is meshed using C3D10 elements (quadratic tetrahedral elements) to balance computational cost and accuracy.
- The ratio of the longest cuboid edge to the host's side length was maintained at or below $1/50$, consistent with earlier XFEM 3D simulations, to eliminate boundary effects.

The final meshing strategy, as implemented in the simulations, is illustrated in Figure 7.5 and Figure 7.6. These figures show the 3D meshed models used in the numerical analysis, highlighting the symmetry reductions applied in each configuration. in Figure 7.5 presents the 1/8th symmetry model used for cuboids with four edge singularities, while Figure 7.6 displays the 1/4th symmetry model for cuboids with a single edge singularity. In both cases, the refined meshing near the inclusion ensures that the length-scale parameter required for fracture propagation is accurately resolved.

A mesh sensitivity analysis was conducted to ensure stress convergence and fracture propagation accuracy, confirming the robustness of the simulation framework. The final meshing parameters are summarized in Table 7.1.

Table 7.1. Summary of mesh details for cuboidal inclusions. The fillet radius of the edge singularities was set to $0.01 \mu\text{m}$. Mesh details include the number of elements in the host region, enriched area around the inclusion, and within the inclusion itself for configurations with 1 and 4 edge singularities.

Benchmark	# C3D8I elements in the Inclusion	# C3D8I elements in the enrichment around the inclusion	# C3D10 elements in the rest of the host
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Cuboid with 4 Edge singularities	69,732	115,584	77,070
Cuboid with 1 Edge singularity	57,239	168,767	96,831

(c) Fracture modeling

The PF-CZM is employed to simulate the fracture behavior of cuboidal inclusions in the diamond host. Building on the theoretical framework developed in the PFM 2D analysis, the model is adapted for 3D simulations to capture the complex stress states and crack propagation mechanisms. Miehe spectral decomposition (Miehe, Hofacker, et al., 2010) is applied to exclude compressive contributions, ensuring that fracture propagation was driven by tensile forces alone. To enforce fracture irreversibility, the History variable method is implemented, effectively preventing the healing of fractures during the simulation.

A monolithic BFGS solver is utilized for its computational efficiency and robustness in solving large, nonlinear systems. The simulations employed a combination of C3D8, C3D8I, and C3D10 elements, selected based on their respective strengths in handling critical stress regions and computational efficiency. Detailed stiffness formulations for these elements are provided in APPENDIX.B. Fracture properties for the diamond host, including critical fracture strength and toughness, are assigned based on experimentally determined values for single-crystal diamond, ensuring that the model accurately reflects the physical behavior of the system.

7.2.3 Results

The concepts of damage initiation ($0 < D < 1$) and fracture nucleation ($D = 1$) are previously defined in the XFEM 3D chapter (Section 4.4.1). In this section, these definitions are extended to analyze the fracture behavior of cuboidal inclusions using the Phase-Field Model (PFM).

(a) Critical Fracture Strength and Toughness

The first set of results (in Figure 7.7) highlights the relationship between critical fracture strength, fillet radius, and olivine volume. For inclusions with sharp edges, a smaller fillet radius (namely, $0.01 \mu\text{m}$) resulted in a higher critical fracture strength of around 7.8 GPa, whereas a larger fillet radius ($0.13 \mu\text{m}$) reduced the strength to around 2.7 GPa. Interestingly, these values were found to be independent of the olivine inclusion's volume or the diamond's fracture toughness. This underscores the dominant role of geometric stress concentration in determining damage initiation.

These findings conceptually align with observations from ellipsoidal inclusions, as described in Section 4.4.2, where geometric singularities drove fracture initiation. However, the quantitative results differ significantly, reflecting the distinct stress localization mechanisms inherent to cuboidal geometries (Puhan et al., 2024).

Figure 7.7. Critical fracture strength defines the minimum stress required to initiate fracture nucleation in the diamond host. This figure illustrates the variation in critical fracture strength as a function of fillet radius (0.01 μm and 0.13 μm) for olivine inclusions, highlighting the dominant role of geometric stress concentration in fracture initiation. The critical fracture strength is the value above which no fracture can initiate and is approximately 7.762 GPa for the sharpest inclusion (0.01 μm) and 2.748 GPa for the more rounded inclusion (0.13 μm), with a precision of +0.001 GPa. These results demonstrate that fracture initiation is dictated by the shape of the inclusion rather than fracture toughness or inclusion size.

The critical fracture toughness (Figure 7.8) defines the material property threshold below which fracture nucleation occurs. For smaller olivine inclusions, the toughness values for both fracture strength conditions (3 GPa and 5 GPa) converge, indicating that fracture nucleation is primarily governed by material strength in these cases. This observation

supports the conclusions of (Tanné et al., 2018), where strength-driven mechanisms dominate at smaller scales.

As olivine volume increases, the toughness curves diverge significantly. For a fracture strength of 3 GPa, the critical fracture toughness reaches $2.5 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{0.5}$, which is markedly higher than the previously observed $1.4 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{0.5}$ for ellipsoidal inclusions. This highlights the increasing influence of toughness as the inclusion size grows. In contrast to smaller inclusions, where stress concentration alone dictated fracture behavior, larger inclusions exhibit a greater dependency on toughness properties, consistent with the scaling relationships observed in fracture mechanics.

The higher critical toughness observed for 3 GPa fracture strength can be attributed to the reduced brittleness of the system. With a lower fracture strength, the material exhibits greater resistance to sudden failure, requiring more toughness (higher energy dissipation) to initiate and sustain crack propagation. In contrast, for higher fracture strength (5 GPa), the material is inherently more brittle, meaning fracture occurs at lower toughness thresholds.

Figure 7.8. Critical fracture toughness represents the material property threshold below which fracture nucleation occurs. This figure shows the variation of critical fracture toughness with olivine volume under two fracture strength conditions (3 GPa and 5 GPa), emphasizing the increasing influence of toughness for larger inclusions. The critical fracture toughness, denoted by the dashed lines with a precision of $+0.008 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{0.5}$, is defined as the threshold above which fracture will not nucleate.

(b) **Residual Pressure Trends**

The residual inclusion pressure as a function of the fillet radius is presented in Figure 7.9. The results show that decreasing the fillet radius leads to enhanced stress concentration at the edges of the cuboidal inclusion, which in turn promotes fracture initiation and propagation. This increase in stress concentration results in a greater degree of pressure relaxation for sharper edges. However, as the fillet radius becomes smaller, the reduction in residual pressure begins to plateau, indicating that the effect of further sharpness on pressure relaxation diminishes. This behavior is consistent with observations for ellipsoidal inclusions discussed

in Section 4.4.2, where increasing stress concentration due to geometric features initially led to greater relaxation but eventually plateaued. These findings highlight the critical role of geometric singularities in driving fracture behavior while emphasizing the limitations of geometry alone in fully relaxing inclusion pressures.

(c) **Impact of Edge Singularities**

The impact of edge singularities on residual pressure relaxation is illustrated in Figure 7.10. Inclusions with a single edge singularity develop only one fracture, resulting in limited stress

redistribution and higher residual pressures, stabilizing at approximately 0.785 GPa. In contrast, inclusions with four edge singularities experience multiple fractures, facilitating greater stress redistribution and enhanced pressure relaxation, with residual pressures stabilizing at around 0.72 GPa.

This value is slightly lower than the 0.76 GPa plateau observed for ellipsoidal inclusions modeled using XFEM (Puhan et al., 2024). However, it is important to recognize that the PFM simulations were conducted with a higher fracture toughness ($0.34 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{0.5}$) compared to XFEM ($0.1 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{0.5}$). The choice of a higher toughness in PFM was dictated by computational constraints, as a larger length scale parameter reduces mesh refinement requirements.

Despite this difference, separate XFEM simulations (though not included in Puhan et al., 2024 but now presented in APPENDIX.E) confirm that for large inclusion volumes ($\sim 10^6 \mu\text{m}^3$, corresponding to natural inclusions typically found in diamonds), the plateau pressure remains at 0.76 GPa, even when the toughness is set to $0.34 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{0.5}$.

This result demonstrates that fracture toughness variations do not significantly alter the final plateau pressure once the system has fully fractured. At sufficiently high inclusion volumes, stress redistribution through fracturing reaches a final state beyond which further changes in volume or toughness have no effect. Thus, the comparison between point singularities (XFEM) and edge singularities (PFM) remains valid, reinforcing the dominant role of geometric singularities in governing fracture initiation and pressure relaxation.

Figure 7.10. Residual inclusion pressure as a function of inclusion volume for cuboids with 1 and 4 edge singularities. Cuboids with 1 edge singularity exhibit higher residual pressures due to limited fracture development, while cuboids with 4 edge singularities show increased pressure relaxation as fractures are more pronounced. All these analyses are done by considering fracture strength = 0.738 GPa and fracture toughness = $0.34 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{0.5}$. The ratio of the length scale parameter to the mesh size is kept constant in all analyses and is always greater than or equal to 5, as suggested by Mandal et al., 2019.

7.2.4 Discussion and Implications

The investigation of cuboidal inclusions provides significant insights into the role of geometric singularities, fracture formation, and stress redistribution in host-inclusion systems under exhumation conditions. The relationship between fillet radius and residual pressure highlights the critical influence of edge sharpness in stress localization and fracture initiation. Smaller fillet radii create sharper edges, which enhance stress concentration and promote more effective fracture propagation. However, the effect plateaus at very small

radii, indicating a smaller pressure relaxation. This behavior is consistent with observations from ellipsoidal inclusions, where stress concentration initially increased relaxation but eventually stabilized due to geometric constraints.

Inclusions with multiple edge singularities further demonstrate the importance of geometric complexity in driving fracture behavior. Inclusions with a single edge singularity produce one fracture, leading to limited stress redistribution and higher residual pressures of approximately 0.785 GPa. Conversely, in our symmetric model, inclusions with four edge singularities produce one fracture per 1/8th section, leading to four total fractures. This symmetry-driven fracture pattern facilitates greater stress redistribution and reduces residual pressures to around 0.72 GPa. This level of relaxation is slightly lower than that observed for ellipsoidal inclusions with four fractures (0.76 GPa, Puhan et al., 2024), which can be attributed to the higher critical fracture strength of cuboidal inclusions. This higher strength allows fractures to initiate earlier, leading to more effective stress redistribution and pressure relaxation.

Despite these improvements, the residual pressures modeled for cuboidal inclusions remain higher than those observed in natural inclusions, indicating the potential role of additional relaxation mechanisms. Processes such as plastic deformation, viscous relaxation, and fluid interactions may further contribute to pressure relaxation and warrant future exploration. While cuboidal inclusions provide a clearer understanding of the interplay between edge singularities, fillet radius, and stress distribution, these results also highlight the limitations of geometric approaches alone in fully replicating natural behaviors.

By addressing the effects of fillet radius and edge singularities on fracture propagation and pressure relaxation, this study refines our understanding of stress redistribution in diamond-hosted inclusions. These findings provide a foundation for developing more comprehensive geobarometric models, incorporating additional mechanisms to achieve better alignment with natural observations.

7.3 APPLICATION TO TWO CUBOIDAL INCLUSIONS

7.3.1 Introduction

In this section, we focus on simulating the relaxation processes in host-inclusion systems containing two cuboidal inclusions, specifically analyzing the stress interactions between the two inclusions in close proximity. The motivation arises from the observation that single inclusions with geometric singularities could not fully relax residual pressures, particularly when considering edge effects. By extending the analysis to two inclusions, we aim to explore how stress interactions and crack coalescence influence fracture propagation and pressure relaxation.

Key points of interest include:

- The influence of stress interactions on crack growth.
- The behavior of residual pressure as cracks propagate and interact.
- The conditions under which crack coalescence occurs, leading to further stress relaxation.

7.3.2 Model Setup

The model consists of two cuboidal inclusions embedded symmetrically in a diamond host, separated by a distance of 2.2 μm . To accurately capture stress interactions and crack coalescence between the inclusions, we consider 1/4th of the system, compared to the 1/8th symmetry used in the single-inclusion setup (see Figure 7.11). The host region surrounding both inclusions is meshed with C3D8I elements for detailed resolution of stress gradients and fracture propagation, while the broader host region utilized C3D10 elements for computational efficiency. Each inclusion retained a fillet radius of 0.1 μm at the sharpest edge, introducing significant stress concentrations that allowed the study of interaction effects between inclusions. Material properties—including a fracture strength of 0.738 GPa, a length scale parameter of $1\text{e-}2$ μm , and varying fracture toughness—remained consistent with those used in the single-inclusion analysis. Finally, boundary

conditions and loading followed the same assumptions outlined in Section 7.2.2, with prestress applied using hydrostatic pressure conditions, assuming isotropic elasticity and a dry host-inclusion system.

7.3.3 Results

(a) Crack Growth and Stress Interaction

The results demonstrate that as fracture toughness decreases (i.e., brittleness increases), cracks initiate and propagate from the sharpest edges of the two inclusions. The interaction of stress fields between the inclusions accelerates crack growth as they approach one another. Figure 7.12 shows the crack propagation and coalescence at a fracture toughness of $0.22\ \text{MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{0.5}$, highlighting

- Nonlinear Crack Growth: Crack length increases nonlinearly with decreasing fracture toughness (see Figure 7.13), due to mutual stress weakening between the two inclusions, as their stress fields interact.

- Crack Coalescence: At a critical fracture toughness of $0.22 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{0.5}$, cracks from both inclusions coalesce. This coalescence marks a significant structural weakening of the host, where stress redistribution becomes more prominent.

(b) Residual Pressure Behavior

Residual inclusion pressures (P_{incl}) is evaluated as a function of fracture toughness and crack length (Figure 7.13). The results show that:

- The residual pressure decreases slightly as the crack length increases due to stress relaxation.
- The most notable drop in residual pressure occurs at the point of crack coalescence, confirming that coalescence facilitates a more effective stress redistribution within the host-inclusion system.
- Despite coalescence, the residual pressures remain above 0.5 GPa, indicating that additional relaxation mechanisms (e.g., plastic deformation, fluid-mediated processes) are required to fully replicate observed natural values.

Figure 7.12. Phase field variable (ϕ) distribution illustrating fracture propagation and coalescence between two cuboidal inclusions at a fracture toughness of $0.22 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{0.5}$, corresponding to the onset of crack merging.

- (a) Top-down view (XY projection) showing a half-domain cut through the mid-plane, capturing the symmetrical crack growth from each inclusion and their coalescence within the host.
- (b) Side view (XZ projection) showing a further quarter-domain section, highlighting the through-thickness extent of the coalesced fracture. Red regions denote fully developed cracks ($\phi \approx 1$), while blue areas remain undamaged.

Crack coalescence reflects stress interaction between inclusions and demonstrates a localized redistribution of stress, although the resulting pressure relaxation remains limited.

7.3.4 Discussion and Implications

The results show that stress interactions between the two inclusions significantly affect crack growth and pressure relaxation. The cracks propagate nonlinearly due to mutual stress weakening, leading to larger cracks compared to single inclusions. At a fracture toughness of $0.22 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{0.5}$, the cracks coalesce, which enhances stress redistribution but does not fully relax residual pressures.

This behavior highlights the importance of stress interactions in multi-inclusion systems, as crack coalescence is a critical event for pressure relaxation. However, the persistence of residual pressures above 0.5 GPa suggests that other mechanisms, such as plastic deformation or fluid infiltration, may also contribute to stress relaxation. In any case, these findings emphasize the role of geometric features and inclusion proximity in driving fracture behavior, providing new insights into the mechanical processes occurring in natural diamond-hosted inclusions.

8. CONCLUSIONS

This thesis has systematically advanced the understanding of fracture mechanisms in diamond-hosted inclusions, addressing key discrepancies between numerical models and experimental observations. By exploring a wide range of geometries, material properties, and numerical frameworks, it has tackled longstanding challenges in geobarometry while developing robust computational tools for inclusion-host systems.

The early XFEM 2D studies provided a foundational understanding of brittle fracture initiation and propagation in simplified systems. These simulations revealed the influence of stress concentration and crack coalescence on fracture behavior, highlighting how inclusion shape significantly impacts residual pressure relaxation. However, the limitations of a two-dimensional framework, including oversimplified geometries and reduced parameter variability, underscored the necessity of transitioning to more realistic 3D simulations.

XFEM 3D simulations were pivotal in revealing the nuanced interplay between inclusion geometry, fracture toughness, and residual pressure relaxation. While ellipsoidal inclusions produced critical insights into fracture initiation thresholds, the results demonstrated that

brittle fractures alone contribute only marginally to pressure relaxation ($\sim 5\text{--}6\%$), leaving residual pressures at ~ 0.76 GPa under typical entrapment conditions (Puhan et al., 2024). These findings confirmed that XFEM modeling of ellipsoidal singularities, despite successfully capturing brittle fracture behaviors, cannot fully explain the lower residual pressures (below 0.5 GPa) observed in natural inclusions (Angel et al., 2022; Rustioni, 2016). Moreover, the fracture properties determined through XFEM (~ 0.8 GPa fracture strength and ~ 1.35 MPa \cdot m $^{0.5}$ fracture toughness) remained significantly below those reported experimentally for diamond (Field & Pickles, 1996; Liang et al., 2009), further emphasizing the need for alternative modeling approaches.

The well-documented limitations of XFEM in handling complex fracture propagation necessitated a transition to Phase-Field Modeling (PFM). PFM 2D simulations validated advanced numerical techniques and identified the Phase-Field Cohesive Zone Damage Model (PF-CZM) with Miehe's spectral decomposition and the BFGS algorithm as the optimal framework for brittle and quasi-brittle fractures. This methodology proved particularly effective in suppressing compressive effects while accurately resolving tensile-driven fracture mechanisms. Building on this groundwork, PFM 3D simulations explored the role of geometric singularities, such as edge effects in cuboidal inclusions. The results demonstrated that sharper edges, characterized by smaller fillet radii, induce higher stress concentrations, leading to earlier fracture initiation and enhanced pressure relaxation. For cuboidal inclusions with four edge singularities, residual pressures were reduced to ~ 0.72 GPa. The enhanced critical fracture properties deduced through PFM (~ 6 GPa fracture strength and ~ 2.5 MPa \cdot m $^{0.5}$ fracture toughness) addressed several critical discrepancies observed in XFEM, aligning more closely with experimentally reported values for diamond.

Across both XFEM and PFM frameworks, the dependency of fracture behavior on inclusion geometry and size was carefully analyzed. Our simulations revealed that critical fracture toughness increases with inclusion size, which quantifies the highest toughness value at which fractures around the inclusion can propagate. However, experimental studies

indicate that the fracture toughness of natural diamond decreases with increasing inclusion size due to the presence of defects and natural heterogeneities (Oh et al., 2002; Zhu et al., 2020).

This inverse relationship between inclusion size and material toughness in experimental studies suggests that a critical threshold inclusion size may exist, beyond which the toughness of the diamond host falls below the critical fracture toughness required to nucleate and propagate fractures. Such behavior aligns with the observed decrease in fracture intensity with increasing inclusion size in natural samples (Rustioni et al., 2016). A similar dependency is reported in fluid inclusions within metamorphic rocks, where a threshold inclusion size governs decrepitation (Campione et al., 2015)

The analysis of systems containing two cuboidal inclusions further underscored the significance of stress interactions and crack coalescence in driving fracture propagation. Mutual stress weakening induced non-linear crack growth, leading to larger fractures and marginally greater relaxation compared to single-inclusion systems. However, even under these conditions, residual pressures remained above 0.5 GPa, highlighting the necessity of incorporating additional relaxation mechanisms, such as plastic deformation, fluid infiltration, or viscous relaxation, to replicate the conditions observed in natural samples (Angel et al., 2023).

The comparative study of ellipsoidal inclusions under cohesive fracture conditions revealed critical differences between brittle and quasi-brittle fractures. By simulating lower fracture strength values, quasi-brittle fractures achieved nearly double the relaxation observed in brittle fractures, bringing residual pressures closer to natural values. This result underscored the potential of cohesive fractures to address key geobarometric discrepancies while emphasizing the need to integrate ductile deformation mechanisms within the host material in future modeling efforts.

Despite the significant progress achieved, this thesis highlights the limitations of current modeling approaches. The persistence of higher-than-expected residual pressures across all simulated systems suggests that mechanisms beyond fracture—such as anisotropic host properties, rapid exhumation rates, and the complex geometries of inclusions—require further investigation (Luisier et al., 2023) .

Moreover, the role of fluid rims, commonly observed surrounding olivine inclusions in natural diamonds (Nimis et al., 2016), cannot be overlooked. Fluids reduce the fracture strength and toughness of the diamond host (Grassl et al., 2019; Lacazette, 1990), promoting earlier fracture nucleation at lower stress levels. Such behavior underscores the need for advanced numerical tools capable of capturing the interplay between fluid-mediated weakening, host anisotropy, and the presence of defects.

In conclusion, this work establishes a comprehensive framework for understanding the intricate interplay between geometry, material properties, and fracture mechanics in host-inclusion systems. By advancing numerical methodologies and addressing key gaps in geobarometric models, it makes a significant contribution to the fields of computational geomechanics and the geological history of diamond-hosted inclusions. These findings not only enhance our understanding of stress relaxation mechanisms but also provide a foundation for future research integrating inelastic processes and the complex dynamics inherent in natural systems.

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APPENDIX.A. COMPUTATION OF STRESS AND MATERIAL TENSORS FOR VOLUMETRIC-DEVIATORIC AND SPECTRAL DECOMPOSITIONS

A.1. VOLUMETRIC-DEVIATORIC DECOMPOSITION

This section details the stress and stiffness matrix computations using the volumetric-deviatoric approach, as introduced in Section 6.1.

In the volumetric-deviatoric decomposition, the strain is split into volumetric and deviatoric components, ensuring that different mechanical contributions are accurately represented. The evolution of the phase field is driven by the positive volumetric strain energy and the deviatoric strain energy component. The stress function and the associated material tensors are defined as follows:

A.1.1. Stress tensor:

$$\sigma = g(\phi)[K\langle\text{tr}(\epsilon)\rangle\mathbf{I} + 2\mu\epsilon'] - K\langle-\text{tr}(\epsilon)\rangle\mathbf{I} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

- $\langle\text{tr}(\epsilon)\rangle$ and $\langle-\text{tr}(\epsilon)\rangle$ are the positive and negative parts of the trace of the strain tensor, respectively.
- K is the bulk modulus.
- μ is the shear modulus.
- ϵ' is the deviatoric strain component.
- $g(\phi)$ is the degradation function dependent on the phase-field parameter ϕ .

A.1.2. Material tensor:

The material Jacobian $\mathcal{C} = \partial\sigma/\partial\epsilon$ is computed as:

$$\mathbf{C} = g(\phi)KH_\epsilon(\text{tr}(\epsilon))\mathbf{I} + 2\mu g(\phi)\left(\mathbf{I} - \frac{1}{3}\mathbf{I} \otimes \mathbf{I}\right) + KH_\epsilon(-\text{tr}(\epsilon))\mathbf{I} \quad (\text{A.2})$$

Where:

- $H_\epsilon(x)$ is the Heaviside function: $H_\epsilon(x) = 1$ for $x \geq 0$, and $H_\epsilon(x) = 0$ for $x < 0$.
- \mathbf{I} represents the second-order identity tensor.
- $\mathbf{I} \otimes \mathbf{I}$ is the fourth-order identity tensor for isotropic elasticity.

A.2. SPECTRAL DECOMPOSITION

The spectral decomposition approach extends the strain energy decomposition into tensile and compressive components, enabling a more refined analysis of crack propagation.

A.2.1. Stress tensor:

The Cauchy stress is expressed as:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = g(\phi)[\lambda\langle\text{tr}(\epsilon)\rangle\mathbf{I} + 2\mu\epsilon^+] - \lambda\langle-\text{tr}(\epsilon)\rangle\mathbf{I} + 2\mu\epsilon^- \quad (\text{A.3})$$

- $g(\phi)$ is the degradation function associated with the phase-field parameter ϕ .
- $\langle\text{tr}(\epsilon)\rangle$ and $\langle-\text{tr}(\epsilon)\rangle$ are the positive and negative parts of the trace of the strain tensor.
- λ and μ are the Lamé parameters.
- ϵ^+ and ϵ^- are the tensile and compressive strain tensors, respectively.

A.2.2. Material tensor

The material Jacobian $\mathbf{C} = \partial\boldsymbol{\sigma}/\partial\epsilon$ is computed as:

$$C = \lambda\{g(\phi)H_\epsilon(\text{tr}(\epsilon)) + H_\epsilon(-\text{tr}(\epsilon))\}J + 2\mu\{g(\phi)P^+ + P^-\} \quad (\text{A.4})$$

- Where H_ϵ is the Heaviside function, such that $H_\epsilon(x) = 1$ for $x \geq 0$ or $H_\epsilon(x) = 0$ for $x < 0$.
- $J \equiv J_{ijkl} = \delta_{ij}\delta_{kl}$, with δ_{ij} being the Kronecker delta.
- P^+ and P^- are the tensile and compressive projection tensors.

A.2.3. Projection tensor (P^+)

Also, the projection tensor $P^+ = \partial_\epsilon[\epsilon_+(\epsilon)]$ is computed as (Miehe, 1998)

$$\begin{aligned} P_{ijkl}^+ &= \sum_{a=1}^3 \sum_{b=1}^3 H_\epsilon(\epsilon_a) \delta_{ab} n_{ai} n_{aj} n_{bk} n_{bl} \\ &\quad + \sum_{a=1}^3 \sum_{b \neq a}^3 \frac{1}{2} \frac{(\langle \epsilon_a \rangle_+ - \langle \epsilon_b \rangle_+)}{\epsilon_a - \epsilon_b} n_{ai} n_{bj} (n_{ak} n_{bl} \\ &\quad + n_{bk} n_{al}) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.5})$$

Where:

- Where n_{xi} is the i^{th} component of the principal strain directions vector n_x .
- ϵ_a are the principal strains.
- In cases where $\epsilon_a = \epsilon_b$, the term $\frac{(\langle \epsilon_a \rangle_+ - \langle \epsilon_b \rangle_+)}{\epsilon_a - \epsilon_b}$ is replaced by $H_\epsilon(\epsilon_a)$.

A.2.4. Projection Tensor (P^-)

The compressive projection tensor is:

$$P^- = I - P^+ \quad (\text{A.6})$$

Where I is the fourth-order identity tensor.

APPENDIX.B. NUMERICAL PERFORMANCE AND STIFFNESS FORMULATIONS OF C3D8, C3D8I, AND C3D10 ELEMENTS

This appendix presents the stiffness matrix formulations for C3D8 (8-noded brick elements), C3D10 (10-noded tetrahedral elements), and C3D8I (8-noded brick elements with incompatible modes) from the ABAQUS element library. These formulations incorporate the B-bar method to mitigate volumetric locking, which is particularly relevant for nearly incompressible materials.

However, in our simulations, parasitic shear stresses were observed in regular C3D8 and C3D10 elements, leading to inaccuracies. To address this issue, the C3D8I element was employed, as discussed in section 7.2.2, to minimize these effects. While the formulations in this appendix focus on the 2D case for clarity, they can be readily extended to 3D.

B.1. B-MATRIX DECOMPOSITION IN 2D

The classical B matrix for strain-displacement relation is:

$$\mathbf{B} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial N^1}{\partial x_1} & 0 & \dots \\ 0 & \frac{\partial N^1}{\partial x_2} & \dots \\ \frac{\partial N^1}{\partial x_2} & \frac{\partial N^1}{\partial x_1} & \dots \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{B.1})$$

whereas the volumetric component of the B matrix is

$$\mathbf{B}_{vol} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial N^1}{\partial x_1} & \frac{\partial N^1}{\partial x_2} & \dots \\ \frac{\partial N^1}{\partial x_1} & \frac{\partial N^1}{\partial x_2} & \dots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{B.2})$$

and its volume-averaged volumetric strain B matrix reads

$$\overline{\mathbf{B}}_{vol} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} \overline{\frac{\partial N^1}{\partial x_1}} & \overline{\frac{\partial N^1}{\partial x_2}} & \dots \\ \overline{\frac{\partial N^1}{\partial x_1}} & \overline{\frac{\partial N^1}{\partial x_2}} & \dots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{B.3})$$

where

- $\frac{\partial \overline{N_a}}{\partial x_j} = \frac{1}{|V_{el}|} \int_{V_{el}} \frac{\partial N_a}{\partial x_j} dV,$

N_a is the shape function, x_j is the spatial coordinates, and $|V_{el}|$ is the volume of the element.

The final B_{bar} matrix incorporates the volume-averaged strain. To achieve this, we introduce B_{dev} as the deviatoric component of the strain-displacement matrix B , defined as:

$$B_{dev} = B - B_{vol} \quad (B.4)$$

The total matrix is then expressed as:

$$B_{bar} = B_{dev} + \overline{B_{vol}} \quad (B.4)$$

B.2. ELEMENT STIFFNESS FORMULATIONS FOR BOTH C3D8 AND C3D10

The element stiffness matrix for C3D8 is formulated as:

$$K_{el} = \int_{V_{el}} B_{bar}^T C B_{bar} dV \quad (B.5)$$

where

- C : isotropic elasticity tensor in Voigt's notation
- V_{el} : Volume of the element

B.3. STIFFNESS FORMULATIONS FOR C3D8I

In this type of elements internal degrees of freedoms are introduced to account for incompatible modes, which improve the element's bending behavior. The primary effect of these additional modes is to eliminate parasitic shear stresses that arise in standard displacement elements when subjected to bending (Wriggers, 2009). The formulation followed recommendations from Simo & Armero, (1992).

In the incompatible mode formulation, the displacement gradient $\frac{\partial u}{\partial x}$ is augmented with an additional, incompatible displacement gradient field \tilde{G}

$$\tilde{G}(\xi) = \frac{j(0)}{j(\xi)} \xi_1 \left. \frac{\partial \xi_a}{\partial x_j} \right|_{\xi=0} \quad (\text{B.6})$$

- Where ξ is the parametric coordinates.
- $j(\xi)$ is the Jacobian of the parametric transformation at the location ξ , and $j(0)$ is the Jacobian at the center of the element.

So, with the new B matrix the strain tensor can be written

$$\text{as } \epsilon = [B_{bar} \ B_\alpha] \begin{bmatrix} u \\ \alpha \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{B.7})$$

α is additional degrees of freedom and B_α is the corresponding incompatible gradient matrix defined as:

$$B_\alpha = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{j(0)}{j(\xi)} \xi_1 \left. \frac{\partial \xi_1}{\partial x_1} \right|_{\xi=0} & 0 & \dots \\ 0 & \frac{j(0)}{j(\xi)} \xi_1 \left. \frac{\partial \xi_1}{\partial x_2} \right|_{\xi=0} & \dots \\ \frac{j(0)}{j(\xi)} \xi_1 \left. \frac{\partial \xi_1}{\partial x_2} \right|_{\xi=0} & \frac{j(0)}{j(\xi)} \xi_1 \left. \frac{\partial \xi_1}{\partial x_1} \right|_{\xi=0} & \dots \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{B.8})$$

B.3.1. Pseudo-code to compute the stiffness matrix for C3D8I element

The following algorithm is used to compute the stiffness matrix and RHS vector of C3D8I elements

1. Begin for loop over the integration points
 - Compute the displacement gradient (B_{bar}) and incompatible gradient (B_α) matrices
 - Update the stiffness matrix sub-blocks:

$$K_{uu} = K^{uu} + \int B_u^T C B_u dV$$

$$K_{\alpha u} = K^{\alpha u} + \int B_\alpha^T C B_u dV$$

$$K_{u\alpha} = K^{u\alpha} + \int B_u^T C B_\alpha dV$$

$$K_{\alpha\alpha} = K^{\alpha\alpha} + \int B_\alpha^T C B_\alpha dV \quad (B.9)$$

2. End for loop over the integration points: Compute the element stiffness matrix as:

$$K^{el} = K_{uu} - K_{u\alpha} K_{\alpha\alpha}^{-1} K_{\alpha u} \quad (B.10)$$

B.3.2. Stress Computation and update pseudo-code

1. Begin for loop over the integration points
 - Update the incompatible displacement (dof)

$$d\alpha = -K_{\alpha\alpha} K_{\alpha u}^{-1} du \quad (B.11)$$

- Compute incremental strains:

$$d\epsilon = B_u du + B_\alpha d\alpha \quad (B.12)$$

- Update total strains and stresses

$$\epsilon = \epsilon + d\epsilon, \sigma = C\epsilon \quad (\text{B.13})$$

2. End for loop over the integration points: Compute the residual force:

$$RHS = RHS - \int B_u^T \sigma dV \quad (\text{B.14})$$

B.4. COMPARISON AND VALIDATION

A comparison was conducted to evaluate the accuracy of different finite element formulations. Table B.1 presents the maximum principal stress values at the tip of an ellipsoidal inclusion, computed using different element types. The simulation setup is identical to that described in Section 4, but considers only elastic behavior.

The accuracy of each element was assessed by comparing the numerical results to the theoretical solution derived from Eshelby's inclusion theory, which is detailed in APPENDIX.C.. The results in Table B.1 indicate that the C3D8I element exhibits the smallest error relative to the theoretical solution, demonstrating its superior performance in this context.

Table B.1. Comparison of the maximum principal stress at the tip of the ellipsoidal inclusion for different element types with respect to the theoretical result

Element Type	Maximum Principal Stress (GPa)	Error (%)
Theory	0.8077	0.0
C3D8	0.8989	10.15
C3D8I	0.7978	1.25

The C3D8I element effectively reduces shear locking while producing results that closely align with the theoretical benchmark. This is illustrated in Figure B.1, which presents a plot of the maximum principal stress (GPa) as a function of the distance from the inclusion tip within the host material.

APPENDIX.C. ESHELBY SOLUTION OUTSIDE COMPARISON TO XFEM

This section provides a theoretical validation of the XFEM 3D numerical results for minimum overpressure versus fracture strength. Eshelby's solution allows for the computation of displacement, strain, and stress states both inside and outside the inclusion, offering a comprehensive understanding of the elastic fields.

C.1. A BRIEF OVERVIEW OF THE ESHELBY SOLUTION

C.1.1. Inside the Inclusion

Uniform Stress and Strain Fields:

- Within the ellipsoidal inclusion, the stress and strain fields are **uniform**. This uniformity is due to the constant nature of the Eshelby tensor (S_{ijkl}) within the inclusion.
- The eigenstrain (e_{kl}^{eigen}) induces a homogeneous strain field inside the inclusion, described by:

$$\epsilon_{ij} = S_{ijkl} \epsilon_{kl}^{eigen} \quad (C.1)$$

Where S_{ijkl} is determined by the inclusion geometry and material properties.

C.1.2. Outside the Inclusion

- **Position-Dependent Elastic Field:**
 - Outside the inclusion, the stress and strain fields vary as functions of position due to the influence of the inclusion geometry and material mismatch.
 - The stress field at a point x which is outside of the inclusion is computed using:

$$\begin{aligned}\epsilon_{ij} &= D_{ijkl}(x)\epsilon_{kl}^{eigen} \\ \sigma_{ij}(x) &= C_{ijkl}D_{klmn}(x)\epsilon_{mn}^{eigen}\end{aligned}\tag{C.2}$$

where $D_{ijkl}(x)$ is the position-dependent tensor derived from Eshelby's solution. The variation reflects the non-uniform displacement gradients caused by the inclusion. The solution of $D_{ijkl}(x)$ is detailed in the work by (Meng et al., 2012).

The numerical and theoretical results exhibit a remarkable similarity, with both showing a linear relationship between fracture strength and minimum overpressure. The close agreement validates the theoretical framework provided by Eshelby's solution in accurately predicting the stress and strain fields at the stress concentration points of the inclusion.

For both aspect ratios 4:1:1 and 10:1:1, the numerical data points align seamlessly with the theoretical lines, confirming the reliability of the XFEM 3D methodology. This strong correlation indicates that the theoretical predictions serve as a robust benchmark for validating numerical models.

This validation further reinforces the theoretical framework, showing its capability to model fracture behavior in ellipsoidal inclusions across a range of aspect ratios, as previously discussed in detail in the XFEM paper.

Figure C.1. Comparison of Numerical and Theoretical Results for Minimum Overpressure vs. Fracture Strength. This plot compares the minimum overpressure required to induce fracture against the fracture strength for ellipsoidal inclusions with aspect ratios 4:1:1 and 10:1:1. The numerical results (red and green dots) from XFEM 3D simulations align closely with the theoretical predictions (blue and black dots) computed using Eshelby's solution.

APPENDIX.D. COMPARISON OF PF-CZM WITH TRADITIONAL DAMAGE MODELS (PF-AT1 AND PF- AT2)

D.1. INTRODUCTION

This appendix investigates the role of the length scale parameter in the Phase-Field Cohesive Zone Model (PF-CZM) compared to the traditional PF-AT1 model. Both models use the same fracture properties—fracture strength of 0.25 GPa and fracture toughness of $0.26 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{0.5}$ and the same mesh size, ensuring a consistent numerical environment.

D.2. SETUP

- Fracture Properties: Identical fracture strength (0.25 GPa) and toughness ($0.26 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{0.5}$) were used for both models.
- Mesh Size: A uniform mesh size of $h = 1 \times 10^{-2} \mu\text{m}$ was applied for all simulations to ensure a consistent comparison.
- Length Scale Parameter:
 - (a) For PF-CZM, l acts purely as a numerical parameter and does not influence material properties. The primary simulation was conducted with $l = 0.12 \mu\text{m}$
 - (b) For PF-AT1, the length scale parameter serves a dual role (numerical and material input) and must satisfy material constraints. As a result, l was set to $0.4 \mu\text{m}$.

D.3. RESULTS

D.3.1. Damage Band Behavior

The damage band behavior is illustrated in Figure D.1:

- **PF-AT1** (Left): A **thick damage band** forms due to the dual nature of the length scale parameter, which is inherently larger for quasi-brittle materials. This corroborates the findings reported by Mandal et al., 2019.
- **PF-CZM** (Right): The damage band remains sharp and localized because the length scale parameter acts solely as a numerical control.

D.3.2. Length Scale Sensitivity in PF-CZM

To further evaluate the sensitivity of PF-CZM to the length scale parameter, additional simulations were performed with $l=0.1 \mu\text{m}$, $0.12\mu\text{m}$, and $0.15\mu\text{m}$. The results, summarized in Table D.1, show minimal variability in residual pressures, with a difference of only 0.35% across the tested range.

Table D.1. Residual pressures (P_{incl}) for varying length scale values (l) in PF-CZM.

Length scale(l) (mm)	P_{inc} (GPa, Residual pressure)
0.1	0.7322
0.12	0.7311
0.15	0.7297

D.4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This comparison highlights the fundamental differences in the treatment of the length scale parameter between PF-AT1 and PF-CZM:

1. PF-AT1:

- The length scale parameter must satisfy both material properties (fracture strength and toughness) and numerical requirements.
- For quasi-brittle materials, this results in a large l and a thick damage band, as observed in Figure D.1.
- Reducing l improves localization but alters the fracture properties, limiting accuracy.

2. PF-CZM:

- The length scale parameter acts purely as a numerical control, ensuring that material properties remain unaffected.
- This results in sharp and localized damage bands, even for larger length scale values.
- Residual pressure predictions exhibit minimal sensitivity to variations in length scale parameter (l), as demonstrated in Table D.1, making PF-CZM robust and reliable for fracture modeling.

In conclusion, PF-CZM overcomes the limitations of PF-AT1 by decoupling the length scale parameter from material inputs. This makes PF-CZM a superior choice for modeling quasi-brittle fractures, where precision in stress relaxation and damage localization is essential.

APPENDIX.E. XFEM VALIDATION OF PLATEAU PRESSURE AT HIGHER FRACTURE TOUGHNESS

E.1. RESIDUAL PRESSURE RELAXATION IN XFEM SIMULATIONS (PUHAN ET AL., 2024)

To establish a baseline for the effect of fracture toughness on residual pressure relaxation, we reference previously published XFEM simulations (Puhan et al., 2024). These simulations were conducted with a fracture strength of 0.738 GPa and a fracture toughness of $0.1 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{0.5}$, showing that the residual inclusion pressure decreases with increasing inclusion volume. At sufficiently large inclusion volumes, the pressure stabilizes at approximately 0.76 GPa, indicating the onset of a plateau.

The reason this plateau was reached at smaller volumes is that the lower fracture toughness enabled brittle fracturing at smaller scales, leading to earlier stabilization of stress relaxation.

E.2. ADDITIONAL XFEM SIMULATIONS FOR EXTENDED VOLUME RANGE

To further validate the role of fracture toughness in defining the pressure plateau, additional XFEM simulations were performed at a higher fracture toughness of $0.34 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{0.5}$ (Figure E.2). The objective was to determine whether the same plateau pressure is reached and, if so, whether it occurs at larger inclusion volumes due to the increased resistance to fracturing.

The results confirm that at higher toughness, the residual inclusion pressure initially decreases more gradually with increasing volume, as fractures are delayed due to the higher energy required for nucleation. However, at sufficiently large inclusions ($\geq 10^6 \mu\text{m}^3$, which

corresponds to the natural inclusion size range in diamonds), the pressure again stabilizes at approximately 0.76 GPa, just as observed in the previous XFEM simulations at lower toughness.

These findings, which were discussed in the main body (Section 7.10), further reinforce the interpretation that once full fracture development occurs, toughness variations no longer significantly alter the final plateau pressure. The key takeaway is that:

- Lower toughness ($0.1 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{0.5}$) leads to an earlier plateau since brittle behavior is achieved at smaller inclusions.
- Higher toughness ($0.34 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{0.5}$) delays fracture initiation, meaning larger inclusions are needed before reaching the plateau.
- Regardless of toughness, the plateau stabilizes at 0.76 GPa once fracturing has fully evolved, confirming that brittleness governs the plateau, not the absolute toughness value.

This directly supports the comparison between edge singularities (PFM) and point singularities (XFEM) discussed in the main text. The key argument was that edge singularities promote earlier fracture initiation and greater stress redistribution, leading to enhanced relaxation. Thus, the results in this appendix provide an independent validation that the plateau observed in PFM at $0.34 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{0.5}$ is fully consistent with XFEM predictions, ensuring that the comparison between geometric singularities remains robust.

